

Cancer screening in Europe

Rapid review 1

What is the evidence for extending existing screening programmes to lung, prostate, gastric, ovarian and oesophageal cancers?

To download the latest version of this document, together with the full Evidence Review Report that it informed, please visit:

www.sapea.info/cancerscreening

SAPEA

Science Advice for Policy by European Academies

The text of this work is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution licence which permits unrestricted use, provided the original author and source are credited. The licence is available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>. Images reproduced from other publications are not covered by this licence and remain the property of their respective owners, whose licence terms may be different. Every effort has been made to secure permission for reproduction of copyright material. The usage of images reproduced from other publications has not been reviewed by the copyright owners prior to release, and therefore those owners are not responsible for any errors, omissions or inaccuracies, or for any consequences arising from the use or misuse of this document.

This document has been produced by the SAPEA consortium. The information, facts and opinions set out in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The SAPEA Consortium is not responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained in this report by anyone, including the European Union institutions and bodies or any person acting on their behalf.

- DOI: -forthcoming
- Downloadable from <https://www.sapea.info/cancer-screening/>

Version history

Version	Date	Summary of changes
1.0	2 March 2022	First published version

Publisher

SAPEA
c/o acatech
Pariser Platz 4a
10117 Berlin, Germany

Contact

SAPEA Communications Office
Rue d'Egmont 13
1000 Brussels, Belgium
contact@sapea.info

Rapid Review 1

What is the evidence for extending existing screening programmes to lung, prostate, gastric, ovarian and oesophageal cancers?

Rapid Review Details

Review conducted by:

A team led by the Specialist Unit for Review Evidence (SURE) for SAPEA (Science Advice for Policy by European Academies).

Review Team:

- Dr Nicholas Courtier, Senior Lecturer Radiography, School of Healthcare Sciences, Cardiff University, UK
- Dr Hui-Ling Ou, Research Associate, Cambridge Centre Lung Cancer Early Detection Group, University of Cambridge, UK
- Dr Alison Weightman, Director Specialist Unit for Review Evidence, Cardiff University, UK
- Louise Edwards, Hub Manager, Academia Europaea, Cardiff University, UK

Method:

This is one of three rapid reviews - a lighter form of a full systematic review that takes account of time constraints. The top-line results are included in the main SAPEA Evidence Review Report, with cross-referencing between the documents.

The review summarises a valuable subset of the evidence base, emphasising the findings from recent randomised and other controlled clinical trials. To meet deadlines, a pragmatic and precise search strategy was employed; it is possible that further controlled trials would have been identified if there had been time for a detailed and sensitive systematic search. The timeline also precluded any statistical or meta-analysis of findings unless these were available from published systematic reviews. No formal critical appraisal was carried out although information is provided on whether the trial included a power calculation. Data extraction and summary were undertaken by different reviewers and, although reviewed by another author, these have not been independently checked for accuracy and consistency.

Acknowledgements:

The advisory group for the review team, comprising the Chairs of the Expert Workshop, Professor Ole Petersen (Academia Europaea), members of SAPEA, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (Advisors) and the SAM Unit. Kate Brain (Professor of Health Psychology, Cardiff University) for reviewing and commenting on the draft pre-publication and Professor Jacek Jassem (Head, Department of Oncology & Radiotherapy, Medical University of Gdańsk).

Disclaimer: The authors of this work declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

What is the evidence for extending existing screening programmes to lung, prostate, gastric, ovarian and oesophageal cancers?

TOPLINE SUMMARY

Who is this summary for?

To support the work of SAPEA in providing evidence to the European Commission's Group of Chief Scientific Advisors on cancer screening in Europe.

Background

This review is one of three rapid reviews conducted on the topic of cancer screening in Europe. It was produced specifically for the expert workshop convened to discuss the scientific basis for extending existing screening programmes to other cancers throughout the EU. This final version has been revised to address feedback received on earlier drafts and supplements the workshop report (available on the SAPEA website).

Aim

To examine the published evidence base for the question, *'Based on findings from controlled clinical and randomised controlled trials on efficacy, harm-benefit and cost effectiveness, what is the evidence for extending existing screening programmes to lung, prostate, gastric, ovarian and oesophageal cancers?'*

Rapid review method

A literature search was conducted in August 2021 for controlled trials published since 2007, supplemented with studies from published systematic reviews. Trials were included if they examined screening for first diagnosis of lung, gastric, prostate, ovarian or oesophageal cancers and included data on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost-effectiveness.

Key findings

Gastric cancer [2 trials]:

- Detection rates for gastric cancers by endoscopic screening were low. Precursor lesions are also detected
- Compliance rates for endoscopic screening were approximately 45%
- Screening via gastric juice MicroRNAs has not yet been assessed in randomised controlled trials
- Limited data from two trials not identified within this rapid review, but included in an identified systematic review, suggest a 79-80% sensitivity and specificity for cancer identification by breath analysis
- No cost-effectiveness data were identified

Lung cancer [13 trials]:

- Higher lung cancer incidence as well as early-stage disease are found in the screening arm, compared to control
- Reduced lung cancer mortality but not overall mortality is observed in the screening arm, compared to control with mild gender variation: 29% in women and 13% in men
- The harms due to false-positive screening results may be minimal

- There are short-term psychosocial harms observed, due to involvement or suspicious results of screening, but this may resolve in the long run
- Four trials provided data on healthcare costs

Oesophageal cancer [5 trials]:

- Endoscopic screening can improve the detection rate of oesophageal cancer, compared to the control group
- Compliance rates were less than 50%
- A single trial estimated the healthcare costs to detect one cancer/one early-stage cancer
- A trial of biomarker-based screening in higher risk individuals has shown a promising effect on early diagnosis of Barrett's Oesophagus and subsequent cancer development

Ovarian cancer [5 trials]:

- No improvement of cancer mortality is observed in the screening arm compared to the control arm
- The psychosocial harms are minor for screening *per se*, unless high-level repeat screenings are required
- A single trial provided data on healthcare costs

Prostate cancer [8 trials]:

- Screening via low threshold prostate specific antigen (PSA) results in a small absolute reduction in prostate cancer/any cause mortality (one death fewer per 1000 men screened over 10 years)
- Any mortality benefit tends to be balanced against overdiagnosis and overtreatment of low-risk disease
- Longer follow-up is required to fully evaluate real-world costs
- One trial suggests that using MRI scanning to indicate biopsy may reduce the risk of overdiagnosis in men with abnormal PSA

Strength of evidence

No formal critical appraisal was carried out within this rapid review but the evidence is from randomised and other controlled clinical trials, with the least theoretical potential for bias. Clinically important inconsistency across trials reduces the level of confidence for some findings.

Full report

Table of Contents

1.	Background.....	5
1.1	Purpose of this review	5
1.2	Research question	5
2.	Results	5
2.1	Summary of the evidence base	5
	Gastric cancer	5
	Lung cancer.....	6
	Oesophageal cancer	9
	Ovarian cancer	11
	Prostate cancer	12
2.1	Summary of the evidence base [table]	14
2.2	Bottom line results	67
3.	Discussion.....	69
3.1	Summary.....	69
3.2	Strengths and limitations of this Rapid Review.....	70
3.2.1	Strengths	70
3.2.2	Limitations.....	70
4.	References.....	71
5.	Rapid review method	78
5.1	Eligibility criteria.....	78
5.2	Literature search strategy.....	78
5.3	Resources list	78
5.4	Study selection process	79
5.5	Study selection flow chart.....	79
5.6	Data extraction.....	80
5.7	Quality appraisal.....	80
5.8	Synthesis	80
6.	Additional information	80
6.1	Conflicts of interest	80
6.2	Acknowledgements	80
7.	About the review team	80
8.	Brief reference lists on topics related to the rapid review	80

1. Background

This Rapid Review is one of three reviews being conducted to support the work of Expert Groups convened to assist the European Commission Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM) in developing policy guidance in relation to cancer screening. As described in the Scoping Paper¹, this review supported the first of the Expert Group workshops convened to discuss the question, **“What is the scientific basis of extending such screening programmes to other cancers e.g. lung, prostate and gastric cancers, and ensuring their feasibility throughout the EU?”**

An advisory group was formed to provide guidance to the review team, comprising the Chairs, Professor Ole Petersen (Academia Europaea), members of SAPEA, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors and the SAM Unit.

1.1 Purpose of this review

Following detailed discussions with the advisory group, the question for the rapid review to inform the first workshop was:

“Based on findings from controlled clinical and randomised controlled trials on efficacy, harm-benefit and cost effectiveness, what is the evidence for extending existing screening programmes to lung, prostate, gastric, ovarian and oesophageal cancers?”

1.2 Research question

Rapid Review Question
Based on findings from controlled clinical and randomised controlled trials on efficacy, harm-benefit and cost effectiveness, what is the evidence for extending existing screening programmes to lung, prostate, gastric, ovarian and oesophageal cancers?

2. Results

2.1 Summary of the evidence base

In all, 84 trial reports have been summarised. We provide a narrative overview of the identified evidence below. A summary of each included trial is provided in Section 2.2.

Gastric cancer

Trial data about gastric cancer screening are scarce.

¹ Scientific Advice Mechanism. European Commission’s Group of Chief Scientific Advisors. [Scoping Paper: Cancer Screening](#). 22 April 2021

Efficacy

GC detection rates in the two available reports on endoscopic screening (Zeng et al, 2020; Xiao et al, 2020) were low (0.04% and 0.4%): equivalent rates for pre-cursor lesions (2.22% and 0.3%) and low-grade benign lesions (7.9%). Detection of early-stage lesions was higher in high-risk areas and in males aged 60 to 69.

Gastric cancer-specific mortality: Mortality data are not available from existing preliminary trial data (after one-off screening). Case-control data has indicated organised endoscopic screening may plausibly reduce gastric cancer-specific mortality² but this has not been tested in rigorous RCT. The detection rates of low-grade, high-grade pre-cursor lesions and low-grade dysplasia in the current trial data (Zeng et al, 2020; Xiao et al, 2020) suggest potential for reduced GC incidence/mortality reduction.

Harm-benefit

Screening compliance rates of approximately 45% in the two reports could be indicative of an unacceptably invasive procedure. The low endoscopy complication rate (0.3 per 1000 screened) can be balanced against the 0.4% detection rate for cancerous lesions and 0.3% rate for pre-cursor precancerous lesions (Zeng et al. 2020). The complication rate was lower in high-risk areas.

Cost-effectiveness

Healthcare costs of screening are not reported in the trial data. The low compliance and gastric cancer detection rates/prevalence suggest that endoscopy is unlikely to be a cost-effective mass screening tool. More targeted approaches, e.g. older men, precision medicine, or novel pre-endoscopic screening tests may be indicated.

Novel pre-endoscopic screening tests excluded from review

A non-systematic review summarises four studies exploring gastric juice MicroRNAs as potential biomarkers of gastric cancer (Virgilio et al. 2018). This body of evidence has been excluded as no component study is a controlled clinical trial.

A systematic review summarises 24 studies of breath analysis as a novel pre-endoscopic screening test (Haddad et al. 2020). None of the component studies were identified by our rapid review search strategy; most were case-control variants, though design reporting is often superficial. Summary information is included here from two controlled trials that reported quantitative results on efficacy.

- The predictive probabilities of a set of volatile organic compounds tested in a sample of 335 generated an area under the ROC curve of 0.85: 80% sensitivity and 81% specificity for the diagnosis of OGC oesophagogastric cancer (Markar et al. 2018).
- A breath-based algorithm correctly classified three patients with gastric cancer and 570 of the 723 cancer-free screened participants : 100% sensitivity, 79% specificity, and 79% accuracy (Broza et al. 2019).

Lung cancer

13 lung cancer trials were included. Most trials took place in Europe (DANTE, Depiscan, DLCST, ITALUNG, LungSEARCH, LUSI, MILD, NELSON, UKLS), three in the United States (LSS, NLST and PLCO) and one in China (ChiCTR-Shanghai). The sample size ranged from 765 to 53,542 participants, with the majority male. Most of the RCTs recruited former and current smokers whilst only 3 trials (ChiCTR-Shanghai, PLCO and UKLS)

² Jun et al (2017). A case control study that does not meet the inclusion criteria for this review. <http://dx.doi.org/doi:10.1053/j.gastro.2017.01.029>

included passive or non-smokers. Three trials (Depiscan, NLST and LSS) compared LDCT screening with CXR screening, instead of a non-screening group. One trial (PLCO) compared CXR screening to a non-screening group. UKLS did not reveal data specifically in the control group.

Efficacy

Lung cancer Incidence: By pooling data from 9 RTCs (DANTE, Depiscan, DLCST, ITALUNG, LUSI, MILD, NELSON, LSS and NLST), the overall lung cancer incidence was higher in the LDCT screening group compared to the control group (RR 1.26; 95%CI 1.10-1.45). Around 22.4% lung cancer cases in the screening arm were non-screening detected (SD 17%). There is a consistent trend across different trials that more stage I cancers (mean 44% vs 26%) and less stage IV diseases (29% vs 43%) were detected in the screening arm than in the control arm (Hunger et al., 2021). The most extreme ratio among RCTs covered by this review was reported in the ChiCTR-Shanghai trial, where 94.1% lung cancers detected in the screening arm were stage I disease compared to 20% in the non-screening control (Yang et al., 2018). In PLCO where CXR screening was used to compare to the non-screening group, the lung cancer incidence was similar between the two arms (RR 1.06; 95%CI 0.99-1.13; P = 0.09) (Paul Flores et al., 2018). The certainty of the evidence is moderate to high that the lung cancer incidence is higher in the screening arm (especially the incidence of early-stage disease) compared to the control arm.

Lung cancer and overall mortality: A meta-analysis study pooling data from 8 RTCs (DANTE, DLCST, ITALUNG, LUSI, MILD, NELSON, LSS and NLST) revealed that among 44,299 LDCT screening participants, a total of 1549 lung cancer deaths were observed, while 1705 lung cancer deaths were observed in 43,579 participants of control group. The RR was calculated 0.88 (95%CI 0.79-0.97), suggesting a 12% reduction of lung cancer mortality in the LDCT screening arm compared to the control arm. A further analysis excluded LSS and NLST, where CXR was utilised as control arm, and the RR was estimated at 0.80 (95% CI 0.70-0.92). A gender variation was also observed, as the RR was 0.71 (95%CI 0.60-0.86) for women and 0.87 (95%CI 0.77-0.97) for men (Hunger et al., 2021). The PLCO trial, where the CXR screening arm was compared to the non-screening control arm, provided slightly different results. The overall mortality rate after a 17-year follow-up was 0.966 for men (RR; 95%CI 0.943-0.989; P=0.004) and 1.002 for women (Pinsky et al., 2019). Across RCTs covered by the current review, there was no statistically significant difference found regarding the all-cause mortality (Hunger et al., 2021; Pinsky et al., 2019). One study evaluated the impact of screening intensity on the mortality rate by comparing the biennial screening protocol with the annual protocol in the MILD trial. There was no statistically significant difference found in terms of overall mortality (HR 0.8; 95%CI 0.57-1.12) and lung cancer mortality (HR 1.10; 95%CI 0.59-2.05) (Pastorino, Sverzellati, et al., 2019). Altogether, the evidence is moderate in terms of the lung cancer and all-cause mortality.

Lung cancer detection rate and sensitivity/specificity: A meta-analysis of 9 RTCs (DANTE, Depiscan, DLCST, ITALUNG, LSS, LUSI, MILD, NELSON and NLST) found that the positive or indeterminate scan results were ranging from 3.6% to 24.2%, with most of them (84% to 96%) being false positive. As a result, some false positive cases underwent invasive workups, yet the complication rates associated with them were low (0.2-1.7%) (Hunger et al., 2021). Another study pooled cumulative data on screening arms from 5 UK-based lung cancer screening programmes including UKLS, Lung Screen Uptake Trial, Manchester Lung Health Checks, Liverpool Healthy Lung Project and Nottingham Lung Health MOT (Balata et al., 2021). In total, 11,815 LDCT screenings were performed across 5 programmes between 2016 and 2020, among which 85.5% were categorised as negative, 10.5% as indeterminate and 4% as positive. The overall detection rate of lung cancer was 2.1% (range 1.7-4.4% across 5 sites) while the FPR was 1.9% (219 of 11,815 scans). Invasive investigation and surgical resection for benign disease were 0.5% (61 of 11,815) and 0.07% (8 of 11,815), respectively, with no major complications or deaths reported. These studies provide moderate evidence suggesting that harms from false positive results may be minimised.

In terms of screening sensitivity and specificity, the ChiCTR-Shanghai trial reported an overall sensitivity of 98.1%, specificity of 78.2% with PPV 6.3% and NPV 99.9% ([Yang et al., 2018](#)). The sensitivity in the LUSI trial was estimated at 83-91% without data on the specificity ([Becker et al., 2020](#)).

Two studies provided evidence on screening intervals versus lung cancer detection and predictive rates. Performance between annual and biennial screening protocols in MILD were comparable with the overall detection rate of lung cancer, both 0.56%, as well as the specificity (99.2% in both arms), sensitivity (73.5% in biennial arm vs 68.5% in annual arm, $P = 0.62$), PPV (42.4% in biennial arm vs 40.6% in annual arm, $P = 0.83$) and NPV (99.8% in biennial arm vs 99.7% in annual arm, $P = 0.71$) ([Sverzellati et al., 2016](#)). Likewise, the final screening round of the NELSON trial (with a 2.5-year interval) also demonstrated similar lung cancer detection rate and PPV compared to former rounds (with 1- or 2-year interval) ([Yousaf-Khan et al., 2017](#)).

The accuracy of using serial LDCT ($n = 161$, as standard protocol) or PET-CTB ($n = 100$) as following workups was evaluated in the DANTE trial. The diagnostic accuracy was 91% for the LDCT arm with sensitivity 100%, specificity 91%, PPV 26% and NPV 100%. On the other hand, the accuracy was 90% for PET-CTB with sensitivity 98%, specificity 81%, PPV 85% and NPV 97% ([Lopci et al., 2019](#)).

In summary, the evidence is low to moderate because of consistency across RCTs, despite a lack of meta-analysis involving several trials.

Harm-benefit

Risk of radiation: The risk of screening-related radiation was analysed and reported in two controlled trials (ITALUNG and NLST). Based on the NLST screening settings and an average effective dose of 1.5mSv, it was estimated the lung cancer excess risk due to LDCT screening was 0.07-0.23% for men and 0.14-0.85% for women depending on models used for estimation ([Pinsky, 2014](#)). One analysis evaluated the risk of X-ray exposure between multi-detector CT and single-detector CT scanners using the ITALUNG settings. The cumulative effective dose to the screening arm was 3.35 Sv per 1000 subjects over 4 years with the multi-detector CT and 5.87-7.12 Sv, using the single-detector CT. The risk of lifetime fatal cancers associated with the screening intervention was 11.7 per 100,000 using the multi-detector CT and 20.5-24.9 per 100,000 using the single-detector CT. Assuming a 10% screening efficacy, the risk-benefit ratio was estimated between 0.32 and 0.02 depending on different settings ([Mascalchi et al., 2006](#)). In summary, the evidence regarding the risk of radiation is low to moderate as analyses were performed in RCTs with multi-round screenings yet settings or equipment might be distinct.

Risk of overdiagnosis and incurred harm: The highest overdiagnosis rate was reported in the DLCST trial after ≥ 4 years of follow-up post-last screening, which was 69.1% ([Hunger et al., 2021](#)), whereas the risk of overdiagnosis after longer follow-up (≥ 11 -year) was 8.9% in NELSON ([Paci et al., 2020](#)) and 3.1% in NLST ([Team, 2019](#)). The risk of overdiagnosis can be quantified as the excess of cumulative incidence of lung cancer in the screening arm, which was reported as 0.89 (RR; 95%CI 0.67-1.18) in the ITALUNG trial ([Paci et al., 2020](#)) and 25.4% (95%CI -11.3-64.3) in the LUSI trial ([Gonzalez-Maldonado et al., 2020](#)). In general, the estimated overdiagnosis rate across other trials ranges from 0% to 67.2% ([Jonas et al., 2021](#)). The evidence regarding the risk of overdiagnosis is low, due to huge variation and varied follow-up periods across different trials.

Psychosocial harms: Studies linked to seven RCTs (DANTE, DLCST, ITALUNG, MILD, NELSON, NLST and UKLS) offered data on the influence of screening on the health-related quality of life. The participation of trials might have little negative psychosocial consequences for both screening and control arms ([Hunger et al., 2021](#)) while the trial allocation might lead to short-term distress of participants in the screening arm with overall scores of distress, anxiety and depression within the normal range ([Field et al., 2016](#)). A positive or

indeterminate screening result also led to short-term distress and anxiety especially in individuals who were referred to MDT (close to clinical threshold). Yet no long-term adverse effect was observed (Field et al., 2016). Analyses across several trials reported that patient anxiety may come along with false-positive results where indeterminate results led to the distress of patients due to potential lung cancer diagnosis in the short-term; such anxiety or distress, however, may be resolved in the long run (Jonas et al., 2021; Pinsky, 2014). In summary, the evidence regarding the health-related quality of life, anxiety or distress is moderate because of consistency across different RCTs.

Change of smoking behaviours: A recent systemic review examined studies across 4 RCT trials (DLCST, LSS, NELSON and NLST) and 3 cohort studies (not included in this current rapid review) and found no obvious smoking cessation or abstinence between screening and control groups (Jonas et al., 2021). A positive or indeterminate LDCT result may increase the rate of smoking cessation and continued abstinence (Hunger et al., 2021). Altogether there is limited evidence to conclude the influence of screening on a change of smoking behaviours.

Cost-effectiveness

There are four studies reporting the cost-effectiveness of the screening programmes (DANTE, DLCST, NLST and UKLS). Two of them provide details of costs incurred under corresponding protocols.

In the DANTE trial, a retrospective analysis was carried out to evaluate the cost-effectiveness between 2 nodule work-ups: serial LDCT (n = 161, as standard protocol) and PET-CTB (n = 100). Based on the Italian National Health Service, the average inpatient's costs for both protocols were €12,121 while the average outpatient's costs were €694 and €1,462 for LDCT and PET-CTB, respectively. Hence, the general effective costs in the outpatient settings were 94 % for LDCT and 90% for PET-CTB. When it comes to diagnostics of nodules ≥ 9 mm, the effective costs in the outpatient settings would be 74 % for LDCT and 90% for PET-CTB (P = 0.018). Under inpatient conditions, the effective costs were 17% for LDCT and 84% for PET-CTB (P < 0.001) (Lopci et al., 2019).

A simulation analysis based on the UKLS trial also revealed information of screening-related health economics. With UKLS protocol, the mean gross current costs were £687,617 (95% CI £479,173-£899,794), consisting of £282,490 for CT scans; £72,592 for the MDT work-up and £332,534 for cancer treatments. An additional 10% of gross cost may incur for the screening invitation and selection, rendering the costs to £754,877 (95%CI £544,824 to £966,304). The gross cost avoided for cancer management when presented symptomatically was estimated at £213,658, around 28% of the management costs after screen detection. Altogether the ICER was estimated at £8466 per QALY gained (95%CI £5516 to £12634) while the QALYs gained per person screened was 0.03 (Field et al., 2016). Despite similar QALYs gained per person in NLST (0.0201, 95%CI 0.0088 to 0.0314), the mean ICER was \$81,000 per QALY gained with wide variations (95%CI 52,000 to 186,000) due to distinct screening implementations (Black et al. 2014).

A report related to the DLCST trial demonstrated a 60% increase of total annual healthcare cost for LDCT screening, among which 12% could be attributed to more lung cancer cases detected. For the control arm, a 48% increase of costs was estimated as the lung function tests and smoking counselling were provided instead (Jensen et al., 2020). Altogether the evidence of cost-effectiveness is low due to different implementations and following work-ups across RCTs.

Oesophageal cancer

Limited data from four controlled trial studies was available to evaluate the efficacy of endoscopic screening for oesophageal cancers. All reports are from China, with questionable generalisability to typical disease prevalence in European settings. Only preliminary post-screening data is available. Datasets range

from 20 to 150,000 participants, with study regions being dichotomised as being high-risk/non-high-risk in some cluster trials. In addition to cancer detection, a protein biomarker trefoil factor 3 (TFF3) used together with a special specimen collection device – Cytosponge® – has shown promising effect on early diagnosis of Barrett’s oesophagus in higher risk individuals, in the UK primary care setting, and consequent development of adenocarcinoma (Fitzgerald et al., 2020a; Fitzgerald et al., 2020b; Swart et al., 2021).

Efficacy

Based on three study findings (He et al. 2019, Xiao et al. 2020, Zeng et al. 2020), the detection rate of high-grade lesions is in the range 0.7– 0.3%. Squamous cell carcinoma accounted for between 0.13 and 0.22 of cases, with the remainder being in-situ disease and pre-cancerous lesions. [moderate confidence as consistent findings but risk of bias]. An early-stage detection rate of about 70% was achieved [moderate confidence], with data suggesting a trend for earlier stage disease in a screened relative to control group (Chen-Tao Guan 2018) [low confidence: single study, risk of bias, publication bias risk]. Detection rates were unsurprisingly higher in ‘high-risk’ areas. Individual risk factors associated with high-grade lesions were age, male gender and family history of OC.

No follow-up reports are available to evaluate effect on mortality. Baseline data suggest that the endoscopic excision of early-stage cancer, detected cancer precursor lesions, plus surveillance and management of low-grade lesions have some potential to reduce OC-specific mortality as follow-up accrues.

Harm-benefit

The absence of mortality data limits an evaluation of harms/benefit. Compliance rates from those invited to screening were less than 50% across trials. This high proportion of non-enrolled target population would dilute any beneficial effect of organised screening.

The age-specific prevalence of high-grade oesophageal lesions detected was 744 per 100,000 in ESECC trial (He et al. 2019). This rate increased to 902 when all detected upper gastrointestinal lesions were included i.e. other UGI high-grade lesions were usefully detected. The equivalent rate for serious complication from endoscopy was 30 per 100,000. Trials used endoscopy plus Lugol staining as the standard detection protocol. A small RCT of the novel detection method of narrow band imaging has demonstrated potential to reduce the number of biopsies per patient to detect high-grade dysplasia and improve patient tolerance compared to standard staining (Chaber-Ciopinska et al. 2018).

Cost-effectiveness

A single trial report estimates the healthcare cost to detect one OC and one early-stage OC at \$26,347 and \$37,687, respectively (at 2018 costs) (Li et al. 2019). These costs would likely reduce significantly if protocol-driven costs were stripped out and initial costs were amortised in a real-world programme. The cost of one oesophageal cancer detection was approximately nine times lower than for gastric cancer, due to higher prevalence. The cost of oesophageal screening will be relatively higher in low-risk regions. Economic analysis from the Barrett’s oesophagus trial 3 (Swart et al., 2021) estimated a 97% probability of Cytosponge®-TFF3 being more cost-effective than usual care of endoscopy on GP advice.

Ovarian cancer

There were 14 studies and 2 systematic reviews identified according to the searching criteria and the information across 5 RCTs was extracted. The size of RCTs ranges from 592 (QUEST) to 202,638 (UKCTOCS) women with one taking place in Japan (SCSOCS), two in the US (PLCO and QUEST) and two in the UK (UKCTOCS and UK Pilot). Most RCTs used both CA125 blood test and TVS as screening methods (mostly sequentially except for the USS group in UKCTOCS) while the UK Pilot trial only used CA125 test for screening.

Efficacy

Cancer incidence and detection efficiency

The incidence of ovarian cancer was reported in 4 RCTs and no statistically significant difference was found between the screening group and non-screening group ([Henderson et al., 2018](#); [Kobayashi et al., 2008](#); [Menon et al., 2021](#); [Prorok et al., 2018](#)). There was indeed a trend of more early-stage (I/II) diseases and less late-stage (III/IV) diseases found in the screening arm compared to the control arm ([Kalsi et al., 2021](#); [Lai et al., 2016](#); [Menon et al., 2021](#)).

In general, the sensitivity and PPV of using TSV alone for ovarian cancer detection was lower than the sequential method of CA125 + TSV (sensitivity 61.5-74% vs 89.4-89.5%; PPV 8.3-11.8% vs 23.3-35.1%) while the specificity was comparably high (99.9% vs 99.8%) ([Buhling et al., 2017](#); [Kalsi et al., 2021](#)).

Survival, cancer and all-cause mortality

One study reported an improved survival of patients diagnosed with ovarian cancer in the screening arm compared to the control arm of the PLCO trial (RR 0.66; 95%CI 0.47-0.93) ([Lai et al., 2016](#)). Yet no improvement in terms of ovarian cancer or all-cause mortality was observed across all RCTs examined, regardless of the screening protocols ([Henderson et al., 2018](#)).

The evidence on cancer incidence, detection efficiency, cancer and all-cause mortality is moderate to strong because of consistency across different RCTs.

Harm-benefit

Risk of overdiagnosis and complications

The risk of overdiagnosis was evaluated in two RCTs (PLCO and UKCTOCS) and found that there might be a possible risk of overdiagnosis ([Gentry-Maharaj et al., 2015](#); [Prorok et al., 2018](#)).

The FPR was ranging from 4.2% to 44.2% for CA125 screening with minor complications incurred, while the FPR was reported 10-12% for TUV or combined screening with higher complications occurring in women receiving false-positive surgery due to CA125 test + TVU examination ([Henderson et al., 2018](#)).

The evidence on the risk of overdiagnosis is moderate while the evidence for FPR and complications was low to moderate due to heterogeneity across different RCT settings.

Psychosocial harms

Psychosocial harms were evaluated in terms of mental and physical health, cancer worry, sexual activity and functioning. In QUEST, which was designed specifically for this purpose, and another independent study, no psychosocial morbidity difference was found between the screening and control arms. There was a higher level of cancer worry/anxiety observed in women who required repeat screenings ([Andersen et al., 2007](#); [Barrett et al., 2014](#)). Similarly, the ovarian cancer screening per se did not affect sexual activity and

functioning unless repeated screens were required due to positive/indeterminate results ([Fallowfield et al., 2017](#)).

The evidence on psychosocial harms is low to moderate because data were only available for 2 RCTs.

Cost-effectiveness

The cost-effectiveness analysis was only reported in UKCTOCS, the largest RCT for ovarian cancer screening available. One study reported an ICER between \$106,187 and \$155,256 when women started screening at the age of 50 (Moss 2018). The other reported that the USS vs non-screening returned an ICER of £625,801 per LYG while the MMS vs non-screening returned an ICER of £91,452 per LYG with CA125-ROCA cost of £20. Provided CA125-ROCA cost of £15, the predictive extrapolation over the expected lifetime of women in the UKCTOCS-MMS protocol estimated an ICER of £30,033 per LYG whilst the Markov model estimated an extrapolated QALY of 0.0581 and the ICER of £46,922 per QALY, approaching the NICE (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, UK) threshold for cost-effectiveness ([Menon et al., 2017](#)).

The evidence on cost-effectiveness is limited because only data from a single, though largest, RCT is available.

Prostate cancer

Efficacy

Meta-analysis of five RCTs powered for the primary endpoint of **PCa-specific mortality** concluded that screening has a very small reduction in PCa mortality at 10 years (IRR 0.96, 95% CI 0.85–1.08) ([Ilic et al. 2018](#)); [low confidence, inconsistency, risk of bias] This equates to one PCa death fewer per 1000 men screened over 10 years³.

A pooled IRR of 0.99 (95% CI 0.98–1.01) and consistent trial results ([Hugosson et al. 2017](#), [Martin et al. 2018](#), [Pinsky et al 2019b](#), [van Leeuwen et al. 2013](#)) demonstrate no effect on **all-cause mortality** [moderate certainty, risk of bias] although statistical power to detect differences in all-cause mortality is uncertain. One fewer death from any cause would occur per 1000 men screened over 10 years (95% CI -3 to +1).

The main evidence for PCa-specific mortality is from three large RCTs including over 300,000 screened men with 10 to 17 years median follow-up:

- The multi-national European ERSPC reported 20% reduction in PCa mortality at 16-years; RR between screened and non-screened groups = 0.80 [95% CI, 0.72–0.89] P <.001) ([Hugosson et al. 2019](#);
- US PLCO (RR = 0.93 [95% CI, 0.81–1.08] P= .38) [Pinsky et al 2019a](#) and UK CAP (RR = 0.96 [95% CI, 0.85–1.08] P= .50) ([Martin et al. 2018](#)) at 17 and 10 years follow-up, respectively.

The positive ERSPC trial used quadrennial screening (in most centres), an optimal PSA threshold for detection of localised/high-risk disease biopsy (3ng/mL) and long follow-up period (16 years). The effect size of screening in PLCO is likely to be reduced by a high prevalence of contamination (opportunistic screening) in the control group ([Pinsky et al 2019b](#)). A modelling paper argues that screening has lowered the expected risk of PCa mortality in both PLCO arms, consistent with ESPRC, after controlling for US contexts ([Tsodikov et al 2017](#)). Simulation of respective trial parameters and contexts were found to

³ This review was criticised post-publication on the basis that it compared five incompatible trials. See Carlsson SV in Responses: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k3519>

account for the discrepancy in mortality findings between the two trials (de Koning et al. 2018). The group equivalence reported in the large UK CAP trial of one-time screening may be biased by 40% screen adherence and a median follow up of 10 years. (Martin et al. 2018)

Harm-benefit

Any mortality *benefit* from low PSA threshold screening is balanced against **overdiagnosis** and overtreatment of low-risk disease.

Screening consistently increased PCa incidence of early, and at a lower rate, advanced and metastatic disease (Osses et al. 2018) [moderate confidence, risk of bias]: meta-analysis of major trials estimates seven more diagnoses of prostate cancer (95% CI +1 to 15) per 1000 men screened (Ilic et al 2018). Excess PCa incidence persisted in all trials (range 10% to 60%) despite substantial control group contamination and long follow-up e.g. 41% at 16 year ESRPC follow-up Hugosson et al. 2019. Earlier diagnosis in screened men needs to be accounted for, as the RR between groups fell from 1.91 at 9 years to 1.57 at 13 years (Schroder et al. 2014).

For every single PCa death saved by screening 1000 men over 10 years, approximately 1, 3, and 25 more men will experience biopsy- and treatment-related sepsis, urinary incontinence, and erectile dysfunction, respectively (Ilic et al. 2018).

Low specificity of PSA results in false-positive rates up to 80% (Prorok et al 2021). False-negative rates are scarce but may be in the order of 15% for all grades and 2% for high-grade disease (Ilic et al. 2018). HRQOL at 15 year follow-up was similar between screened and non-screened men with PCa in FinRSPC (Talala et al. 2020). Risk -based screening (e.g. Stockholm3 test) can stratify an MRI-targeted biopsy approach to detect clinically significant disease and reduce overdiagnosis (Nordström et al. 2021).

Cost-effectiveness

Limited published evidence is available on the impact of organised PCa screening on healthcare costs. Longer follow-up is required to fully evaluate cumulative real-world costs.

A simulation based on ESRPC data screening every four years in men aged 55 to 69 years estimates an increase of 652 life-years and 366 QALYs per 10,000 men screened. A cost of €54,918 cost per QALY gained. (Karlsson et al 2021). Modelling of ESRPC data evaluated the optimal parameters to be biennial screening within the age range 55–59 years, which generated an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio of \$73,000 per QALY gained. (Heijnsdijk et al 2021).

An individual registry-based analysis found little difference in healthcare costs between FinRSPC arms of ESRPC with slightly lower mean overall costs and slightly higher prostate-cancer-specific costs in the screened group [low confidence, due to low statistical power and control group contamination] Booth et al 2018.

2.1 Summary of the evidence base [table]

Gastric cancer

Trial	Trial Details	Participants	Outcomes	Results	Notes
<p>Screening of GC in China Zeng et al. 2020</p>	<p>Cluster RCT China 2015-2017 In I group, participants from high-risk areas screening by endoscopy. High-risk participants in non-high-risk areas advised for endoscopy One-off</p>	<p>N = 149,956* I = 75,421 C = 74,535 S = 37,922 *from 3 high-risk areas and 4 non-high-risk areas across China (risk category based on crude mortality rate of GC during 1973–1975) 40–69 yrs Plus No personal history of cancer no endoscopy in previous 3 years Report after screening baseline complete</p>	<p>1. Detection rate Early detection rate (proportion of stage 0/I among all positive cases). i.e. includes high-grade dysplasia/in-situ disease and stage I invasive GC 2. Compliance rate</p>	<p>Uptake: 152,172 (66.0%) of 230,583 invited attended the baseline survey. Compliance: Overall compliance rate was 43.8%: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>High-risk areas:</i> 27,111 in I group and 32,893 in C group. Compliance rate = 42.2% (26,633/63,123 eligible individuals invited had endoscopy). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Non-high-risk areas:</i> 48,310 in I group and 41,642 in C group: 23,532/48,310 identified as high-risk for further endoscopy 48.0% (11,289/23,532 invited had endoscopy) Outcomes: - GC incidence/detection rate: Among 37,922 subjects who underwent endoscopy, overall gastric detection (rate) for combined pre- and malignant lesions was 284 (0.8%); 0.9% vs 0.3% in high- and low-risk areas, respectively. Older age group (OR = 8.7, 95%CI 5.8–13.2), male (3.0, 95%CI 2.3–3.9) and high-risk areas (3.4, 95%CI 2.4–4.8) were risk factors for positive detection.</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y Trial of endoscopic cancer screening of whole oesophagus and stomach cancer and gastric cancer High-risk participants in non-high-risk areas categorised based on bespoke questionnaire</p>

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage: 117 (0.3%) of cases were high-grade dysplasia and 167 (0.4%) GC, with 2977 (7.9%) cases of intestinal metaplasia/low-grade dysplasia. 214 (75.4%) and 70 (24.6%) were early stage vs. advanced stage disease. In high risk areas, 81.5% of detection was early stage vs 33.3% in non-high-risk areas. - Cancer-specific mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Harms: overall, 0.3 per 1000 screened had complications from endoscopy (8 cases with bleeding, 2 oesophageal perforation, 1 gastric perforation, 1 gastro-spasm). 	
<p>Screening of GC in non-high-risk areas</p> <p><u>Xiao et al. 2020</u></p>	<p>Cluster RCT</p> <p>China</p> <p>2015-2017</p> <p>Upper endoscopic screening with biopsy of suspicious lesions</p> <p>One-off</p>	<p>N =19,981*</p> <p>I = 10,416</p> <p>C = 9565</p> <p>S = 2388</p> <p>*across non-high incidence areas i.e. urban settings</p> <p>40–69 years</p> <p>Plus</p> <p>No personal history of cancer no endoscopy in previous 3 years</p>	<p>1. UGC mortality</p> <p>2. UGC detection rate</p> <p>Incidence rate</p> <p>Survival rate</p> <p>Stage at diagnosis</p> <p>Feasibility</p>	<p>Uptake: 20,156 (74.3%) of 27,116 subjects contacted consented to participate.</p> <p>Compliance: 5242 (50.3%) of I group were estimated to be high-risk (based on bespoke questionnaire). 2388 (45.6%) underwent endoscopic screening. Older age and higher household income were positively associated with compliance.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/detection rate: 1276/1488 pathologies detected were not cancerous or pre-cancerous. One stage I gastric cancer (0.04%), and 53 (2.22%) 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>Trial of endoscopic cancer screening of whole oesophagus and stomach cancer and gastric cancer</p> <p>Study conducted in one of non-high-risk centres in the national screening of upper gastrointestinal cancer in China study</p>

		Report after screening baseline complete		<p>pre-cancerous gastric lesions were detected.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage: Older age (OR= 1.04,; 95% CI 1.01–1.08) and male gender (OR = 2.34, 95% CI 1.33–4.17) correlated with a higher risk of gastric precancerous lesions. - Cancer-specific mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
--	--	--	--	--	--

	<p>Uptake: Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial</p> <p>Compliance: Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening</p> <p>N=Total number in trial; I=in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S=No. screened</p>
UGC	Upper gastrointestinal cancer

Lung Cancer

Trial	Trial Details	Participants	Outcomes/Results	Notes
<p>ChiCTR-Shanghai (Qian et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2018)</p>	<p>China</p> <p>2013-2014</p> <p>1) Biennial LDCT screening for 3 rounds (I)</p> <p>2) Unscreened control (C)</p>	<p>N = 6717</p> <p>I = 3512</p> <p>C = 3145</p> <p>S = 3473*</p> <p>Mean age 59.8 y (45-70 y)</p> <p>46.8% Male</p> <p>≥ 5 y follow-up</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: The compliance rate was 98.9% at the baseline.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: Within the 2-year follow-up, a total of 51 lung cancer cases were confirmed (1.5%) of which 10 cases were in the non-screening group (0.3%). 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>NLST eligible criteria shows poor performance in Chinese population, where the detection rate of lung was 1.4% (45/3256). Low tobacco use among Chinese women (2.4%)</p>

	Criteria: D ≥ 4 mm	<p>Population: general</p> <p>Baseline smoking status: 10.3% former smoker ^a; 21.3% current ^b smoker; 23.5% passive ^c smoker</p> <p>*Interpreted from the given compliance rate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: Among 3512 LDCT participants, 804 were positive of screening results (22.9%). - Stage: Early-stage lung cancer detection is 94.1% in LDCT group versus 20% in control group (stage I: 48 vs 2; stage II-IV or limited stage: 3 vs 8). - Lung cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: Among 52 participants in the LDCT group confirmed with lung cancer, one of them was with negative screening result, based on which the LDCT screening sensitivity was 98.1% (51/52, 95%CI = 88.4-99.9), the specificity 78.2% (2707/3460, 95%CI = 76.8-79.6), PPV 6.3% (51/804, 95%CI = 4.8-8.3), and NPV 99.9% (2707/2708, 95%CI = 99.8-99.9). 	might be the cause of under-including candidates with high risks.
<p>DANTE (Hunger et al., 2021; Infante et al., 2017; Lopci et al., 2019)</p>	<p>Italy</p> <p>2001-2006</p> <p>1) Annual LDCT screening for 5 y (I)</p> <p>2) Unscreened control (C)</p> <p>Criteria: all solid, non-smooth</p>	<p>N = 2450 I = 1264 C = 1186 S = NR</p> <p>Mean age 65 y (60-74 y)</p> <p>100% Male</p> <p>Median follow-up 8.4 y</p> <p>Population: former or current smokers</p> <p>Baseline smoking status: 43% former</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: NR</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: The number of diagnosed lung cancers in screening and control arms were 104 (8.2%) and 72 (6.1%), respectively. - Detection rate: Among the 104 confirmed cases in the screening arm, 38 (37%) were not picked up via screening. Considering a total of 6482 LDCT scans performed, the recall rate across all screening rounds was 28.1% whereas the lung cancer detection rate was 5.3%. - Stage: NR - Lung cancer and all-cause mortality: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>The cost-effectiveness analysis was based on the costs of Italian National Health Service and showed in Euro.</p> <p>Errors in Table 2 and inconsistency in text from Lopci et al. made it difficult for judging the accurate information. Hence, cost-effectiveness data in Table 3 was extracted instead.</p>

		smoker ^d ; 57% current smoker ^b	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitivity/Specificity: Among patients with ≥ 1 indeterminate nodule detected through screenings (217 patients with 261 lung nodules), a retrospective analysis was carried out to evaluate the accuracy and cost-effectiveness of the 2 nodule workups: serial LDCT (n = 161, as standard protocol) and PET-CTB (n = 100). The diagnostic accuracy was 91% for LDCT arm with sensitivity 100%, specificity 91%, PPV 26% and NPV 100%. The accuracy was 90% for PET-CTB with sensitivity 98%, specificity 81%, PPV 85% and NPV 97%. - Cost effectiveness: The average inpatient's costs for both protocols were €12,121 while the average outpatient's costs were €694 and €1,462 for LDCT and PET-CTB, respectively. Hence, the general effective costs in the outpatient settings were 94 % for LDCT and 90% for PET-CTB. Considering diagnostics of nodules ≥ 9 mm, the effective costs in the outpatient settings would be 74 % for LDCT and 90% for PET-CTB ($P = 0.018$). Under inpatient conditions, the effective costs were 17% for LDCT and 84% for PET-CTB ($P < 0.001$). 	
Depiscan (Hunger et al., 2021)	France 2002-2004 1) Annual LDCT screening for 3 y (I)	N = 765 I = 385 C = 380 S = NR Mean age 56 (50-75 y) 71% Male	Uptake: NR Compliance: 144 subjects withdrew consent after enrolment. Baseline data available for 621 (81%) of 765 subjects enrolled Outcomes: - Lung cancer incidence: Baseline results were reported where 2.1% of LDCT screening participants were	Power calculation: NR Depiscan compared LDCT screening to screening with chest radiography (CXR) as control.

	<p>2) Annual CXR screening for 3 y (C)</p> <p>Criteria: D > 5 mm</p>	<p>Median follow-up NR</p> <p>Population: former^a or current^j smokers</p>	<p>diagnosed with lung cancer compared to 0.3% in the CXR screening arm.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: An independent meta-analysis showed that, considering a total of 336 LDCT scans performed with 81 (24.1%) positive or indetermined findings in Depiscan, the recall rate and lung cancer detection rate were 24% and 2.4%, respectively. - Stage: NR - Lung cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
<p>DLCST</p> <p>(Hunger et al., 2021; Jensen et al., 2020; Wille et al., 2016)</p>	<p>Denmark</p> <p>2004-2006</p> <p>1) Annual LDCT screening for 5 y (I)</p> <p>2) Unscreened control (C)</p> <p>Criteria: D ≥ 5 mm</p>	<p>N = 4104 I = 2052 C = 2052 S = 1960*</p> <p>Mean age 58 y (50-70 y)</p> <p>56% Male</p> <p>Median follow-up 9.8 y</p> <p>Population: former or current smokers</p> <p>Baseline smoking status: 24% former smoker^e; 76% current smoker^b</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: The mean annual participation rates were 95.5% and 93.0% in the screening group and control group, respectively.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: There were more lung cancer cases found in the screening arm (100 of 2052) compared to the control arm (53 of 2052, $P < 0.001$), especially the adenocarcinomas (58 vs 18, respectively, $P < 0.001$). - Detection rate: Meta-analysis of efficiency showed that, within 9800 LDCT scans performed, 512 (5.2%) were positive/indeterminate. The recall rate and lung cancer detection rate were 7.6% (baseline) and 0.7% (overall), respectively. - Stage: A trend of more early-stage cancers in the screening group than control group was observed (stage I 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p>

		*Interpreted from the given compliance rate	<p>and II, 54 vs 10, respectively; $P < 0.001$). More highest-stage disease (T4N3M1) were found in the control (21 of 53) than in screening arm (8 of 100, $P = 0.025$).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer & all-cause mortality: The overall mortality rate (HR 1.02; 95%CI 0.82-1.27; $P = 0.867$) and lung cancer mortality rate (HR 1.03; 95%CI 0.66-1.6; $P = 0.888$) were comparable in both arms. - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Cost effectiveness: A 60% increase of total annual healthcare cost was reported for LDCT screening, among which 12% could be attributed to more lung cancer cases detected. For the control arm, a 48% increase of costs was estimated as the lung function tests and smoking counselling were provided. - Risk of overdiagnosis: After ≥ 4 years of follow-up post-last screening, the overdiagnosis rate was 69.1% in DLCST. - Psychosocial harms: Participation in trial might have little negative psychosocial consequences for both screening and control arms. High motivation of smoking cessation and a positive baseline LDCT result might increase the quitting rate. 	
ITALUNG (Hunger et al., 2021; Jonas et al., 2021; Mascalchi et al., 2006; Paci et	Italy 2004-2006 1) Annual LDCT screening for 4 y (I)	N = 3206 I = 1613 C = 1593 S = NR Mean age 61 y (55-69 y) 65% Male	Uptake: 17,055 (24%) responses to questionnaire in 71,232 invitation letters. Compliance: 1,406 (87%) of 1,613 in I group performed the baseline scan Outcomes:	Power calculation: Y

<p><u>al., 2020; Paci et al., 2017)</u></p>	<p>2) Unscreened control (C) Criteria: D > 5 mm</p>	<p>Median follow-up 11.3 y Population: former or current smokers Baseline smoking status: 35% former smoker; 65% current smoker^f</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: The incidence rates of lung cancer were 52.8 and 59.4 (per 10,000 person-year) in the screening and control arms, respectively (RR 0.89; 95%CI 0.67-1.18). Among 91 confirmed cases in the screening group, 38 cases (42%) were screen-detected. - Detection rate: A total of 5333 LDCT scans were performed with 1044 (19.6%) positive/indeterminate findings. The recall rate and lung cancer detection rate throughout all screening rounds were estimated 52.7% and 0.5%, respectively. - Stage: The resected rate of screen-detected cases was 82% where 61% were stage I, compared to the control arm where 28% were resected with 12% stage I ($P < 0.001$). - Lung cancer & all-cause mortality: After a median of 9.3-year of follow-up, all-cause mortality was comparable between screening arm (105.1) and control arm (127 per 10,000 person-years, $P = 0.08$). - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Survival rate: The 3-year lung cancer survival rate was 44% for the screening arm and 25% for the control arm after a median of 9.3-year of follow-up ($P = 0.07$). After 11-year follow-up, with 38% “resected and early” cases in the screening arm compared to 19% in the control arm ($P = 0.003$), the 10-year survival rates were similar (64% vs 60%; $P = 0.689$). For “unresected and late” cases, the 5-year survival rates were 10% and 7% in the screening and control arms, respectively ($P = 0.679$). 	
---	---	--	---	--

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk of overdiagnosis: The risk of overdiagnosis was quantified as the excess of cumulative incidence of lung cancer in the careening arm, which was estimated 0.89 (RR; 95%CI 0.67-1.18). - Risk of radiation: Analysis evaluating the risk of X-ray exposure between multi-detector CT and single-detector CT scanners demonstrated the cumulative effective dose to the screening arm was 3.35 Sv per 1000 subjects over 4 years using the former setting and 5.87-7.12 Sv using the latter. The risk of lifetime fatal cancers associated with the screening intervention was 11.7 per 100,000 using the former and 20.5-24.9 per 100,000 using the latter settings. Assuming a 10% screening efficacy, the risk-benefit ratio was estimated between 0.32 and 0.02 depending different settings. - Adverse events: The death rates within 60 days post-surgery were 1.2 and 1.3 per 1000 in the screening and control arms, respectively ($P = 0.99$). The death rates within 60 days post-invasive diagnostic procedure were 3.7 for the former and 3.8 for the latter (per 1000, $P = 0.98$). 	
<p>LSS (Hunger et al., 2021; Jonas et al., 2021)</p>	<p>US 2000-2001 1) Annual LDCT screening for 2 y (I)</p>	<p>N = 3318 I = 1660 C = 1658 S = NR Mean age NR (55-74 y) 59% Male</p>	<p>Uptake: 12,270 responses (1.9%) to 653,417 information packages. 4,828 found to be eligible. (Gohagan 2004 https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.126.1.114)</p> <p>Compliance: NR</p> <p>Outcomes:</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>LSS is a feasibility pilot study comparing LDCT screening to screening with CXR.</p>

	<p>2) Annual CXR screening for 2 y (C)</p> <p>Criteria: D > 3 mm for baseline; D > 4 mm for others</p>	<p>Median follow-up 5.2 y</p> <p>Population: former or current smokers</p> <p>Baseline smoking status: 42% former smoker^d; 58% current smoker^g</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: The number of lung cancer detected were 40 (2.4%) in the LDCT group and 20 (1.2%) in the CXR group. - Detection rate: In total, 2984 LDCT scans were performed, among which 655 (22%) were positive/indeterminate findings. The overall recall rate was 34.5% whereas the lung cancer detection rate was 0.57%. Around 5% of lung cancer cases not picked up by screening. - Stage: NR - Lung cancer & all-cause mortality: The overall mortality rates were 1667 and 1384 per 100,000 in the LDCT arm and CXR arm, respectively (IRR 1.2; 95%CI 0.94-1.53) while the corresponding lung cancer mortality were 383 and 310 per 100,000 (IRR 1.24; 95%CI 0.74-2.07). - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
<p>LungSEARCH (Spiro et al., 2019)</p>	<p>UK</p> <p>2007-2011</p> <p>1) Annual sputum screening for 5 y (I)</p> <p>2) Unscreened control (C)</p> <p>Criteria of LDCT: D ≥ 9 mm</p>	<p>N = 1568 I = 785 C = 783 S = 669</p> <p>Mean age 63 y</p> <p>52% Male</p> <p>Median follow-up 5 y</p> <p>Population: former or current smokers with COPD</p>	<p>Uptake: From Centres collecting this data, 3,099 (39%) of 7,998 contacted by telephone accepted the invitation to attend pre-trial assessment; of which 42% (1313/3099) were randomised.</p> <p>Compliance: The baseline compliance with the sputum sampling with evaluable samples was 85.2%. The ratio of providing evaluable samples dropped to 53.9% by year 5. The overall compliance with AFB and LDCT was 72.0% and 91.6%, respectively.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>Participants were subjected to AFB and LDCT provided sputum cytology or cytometry showed abnormalities (sequential screening approach).</p>

		Baseline smoking status: 44% former smoker; 56% current smoker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: A total of 78 lung cancers were confirmed with 36 in the control arm and 42 in the screening arm. - Detection rate: Among participants provided adequate sputum samples, 19% were abnormal for cytology or cytometry. - Stage: The ratio of disease diagnosed at early stage was 45.2% and 54.8% in control and screening arm, respectively. - Lung cancer & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: Among the 42 confirmed cases in the screening group, 44.7% had an abnormal sputum sample, thereby led to the overall sensitivity of 40.5% and FPR of 32.8% for sputum. 	
<p>LUSI (Becker et al., 2020; Gonzalez-Maldonado et al., 2020; Hunger et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Germany 2007-2011</p> <p>1) Annual LDCT screening for 5 y (I) 2) Unscreened control I</p> <p>Criteria: $D \geq 5$ mm or VDT = 400-600 days and $D < 7.5$ mm</p>	<p>N = 4052 I = 2029 C = 2023 S = 2028*</p> <p>Mean age NR (50-69 y) 65% Male Median follow-up 9.8 y</p> <p>Population: former or current smokers</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: There was over 90% of attendance for each screening round. In total 84% of participants completed all 5 screenings.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: There were 4.2% (85 of 2029) and 3.3% (67/2023) lung cancer cases diagnosed in the screening and control arm, respectively. Around 7% (6 of 85) cases were not detected via screening. Within 5-year post-randomisation, an increased number of lung cancer diagnosis was observed in the screening arm compared to control arm (HR 1.76; 95%CI 1.17-2.66; $P < 0.01$). 	Power calculation: Y

		<p>Baseline smoking status: 38% former smoker^d; 62% current smoker^h</p> <p>*Baseline screening round; the number screened declined with each round: 2000, 1978, 1954, and 1925 for 2nd-5th rounds, respectively</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: In total, 9405 LDCT scans were performed with 816 (8.7%) positive/indeterminate findings. The overall recall rate was 22.2% while the lung cancer detection rate was 1.1%. - Stage: NR - Lung cancer & all-cause mortality: The overall mortality rates were similar between screening and control arm (HR 0.99; 95%CI 0.79-1.25; $P = 0.95$). The lung cancer mortality rates were reduced in screened women (HR 0.31; 95%CI 0.1-0.96; $P = 0.04$) but not in men (HR 0.99; 95%CI 0.79-1.25; $P = 0.95$) compared to control counterparts. - Sensitivity/Specificity: The LDCT sensitivity was estimated 83-91%. - Risk of overdiagnosis: The excess cumulative incidence was 25.4% (95%CI -11.3-64.3) in the screening arm (assessed 5.73 years since last screening). 	
<p>MILD</p> <p>(Hunger et al., 2021; Infante et al., 2017; Pastorino, Silva, et al., 2019; Pastorino, Sverzellati, et al., 2019; Sverzellati et al., 2016)</p>	<p>Italy</p> <p>2005-2011</p> <p>1) Annual LDCT screening for 7 rounds (I_1)</p> <p>2) Biennial LDCT screening for 4 rounds (I_2)</p> <p>3) Unscreened control</p>	<p>N = 4099</p> <p>$I_1 = 1190$</p> <p>$I_2 = 1186$</p> <p>C = 1723</p> <p>S = 2303</p> <p>Median age 58 y (49-75 y)</p> <p>68.4% Male</p> <p>Median follow-up 10 y</p> <p>Population:</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: The overall participation in screening was 96.9% (2303 of 2376).</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lang cancer incidence: Lung cancer cases confirmed was 98 (4.1%) in the screening arm (both annual and biennial) and 60 (3.5%) in the control arm. There were 27.6% lung cancer patients not detected via screening. - Detection rate: Both annual and biennial screening protocols conferred a lung cancer detection rate of 0.56%. 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p>

	<p>Criteria: $D \geq 5 \text{ mm}$ or $V \geq 60 \text{ mm}^3$</p>	<p>former^d or current^b smokers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage: Among lung cancer staged, half of cases in the screening arm were early stage while 21.7% were stage I in the control arm. In contrast, most cancer cases in control arm were stage IV (53.3%) whilst late-stage cases accounted for 29.6% in the screening arm ($P = 0.0004$). - Lung cancer & all-cause mortality: The overall mortality rates were 593.5 and 653.9 per 100,000 in screening arm and control arm, respectively. Mortality due to lung cancer were estimated 173.3 per 100,000 for the screening arm and 246.8 for the control arm. The landmark analysis beyond 5 years showed a reduced mortality risk in the screening arm compared to control arm (HR 0.68; 95%CI 0.49-0.94; $P = 0.01$). In terms of lung cancer mortality, screening group demonstrated 58% risk reduction than the control group (HR 0.42; 95%CI 0.22-0.79; $P = 0.0037$). The impact of screening intensity on the long-term mortality, which was assessed by comparing the biennial with the annual protocols, was reported to be mild as the overall mortality (HR 0.8; 95%CI 0.57-1.12) and lung cancer mortality (HR 1.10; 95%CI 0.59-2.05) were similar between two protocols. - Sensitivity/Specificity: Both screening protocols showed similar specificity (99.2% in both arms), sensitivity (73.5% in biennial arm vs 68.5% in annual arm, $P = 0.62$), PPV (42.4% in biennial arm vs 40.6% in annual arm, $P = 0.83$) and NPV (99.8% in biennial arm vs 99.7% in annual arm, $P = 0.71$). A total of 7369 LDCT scans were performed in the annual arm with 268 (3.6%) positive/indeterminate findings, resulting in a recall rate 5.81%. For the biennial 	
--	--	--	--	--

			arm, 5006 LDCT scans were performed with 217 (4.3%) positive/indeterminate findings, leading to a recall rate of 6.97%.	
NELSON (de Koning et al., 2020; Hunger et al., 2021; Jonas et al., 2021; Paci et al., 2020; Walter et al., 2018; Yousaf-Khan et al., 2017)	The Netherlands and Belgium 2003-2006 1) Four LDCT screenings in year 0, 1, 3 and 5.5 (I) 2) Unscreened control(C) Criteria: D > 5 mm or V > 50 mm ³ or VDT = 400-600 days	N = 15,792 I = 7915 C = 7877 S = 6309* Median age 58 y (50-74 y) 84% Male Median follow-up 10 y Population: former or current smokers Baseline smoking status: 45% former smoker ^d ; 55% current smoker ⁱ *Number of men screened at the baseline; number of women NR	Uptake: 150,920 (25%) of 606,409 responded to a questionnaire. 30,959 were eligible and 15,822 of these (51%) provided written informed consent. Compliance: The overall screening compliance was 90.0% (95%CI 76.9-95.8%) among male participants. Outcomes: - Lung cancer incidence: Around 4.3% (344 of 7915) and 3.8% (304 of 7877) participants were diagnosed with lung cancer in the screening arm and control arm, respectively. - Detection rate: Cases missed by the LDCT screening was 41%. Among the 22,600 LDCT scans performed, 2536 (11.3%) were positive or indeterminate. The baseline recall rate was 20.4% whilst the overall lung cancer detection rate was estimated 3.2%. - Stage: The rate of screening-detected lung cancer was 59% (203 of 344) in the screening arm, most of which were in stage IA or IB (58.6%). In contrast, only 14,2% and 13.5% of non-screening detected lung cancers were diagnosed in stage IA or IB in the screening arm and control arm, respectively. Only 9.4% of the screening-detected lung cancer were diagnosed stage IV whilst 51.8% and 45.7% of non-screening detected lung cancers	Power calculation: Y Volume-based nodule-management protocol

			<p>were stage IV in the screening arm and control arm, respectively.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer mortality: After 10-yr follow-up, the lung cancer mortality rate in men was 2.5 deaths versus 3.3 deaths per 1000 person-year in the screening arm compared to control arm (RR 0.76, 95%CI 0.61-0.94; $P = 0.01$). Analysis of women (much smaller sample size) revealed an RR of 0.67 (95%CI 0.38-1.14) at 10 years; RR 0.52 (95%CI 0.28-0.94) at 9 years; RR 0.42 (95%CI 0.19-0.84) at 8 years. - Sensitivity/Specificity: A final of 2.1% (467 of 22,600 scans) were test-positive after 10-yr follow-up and required further workup, which ended up with 203 screening-detected lung cancer cases. The overall PPV was 43.5% with the FPR 1.2%. - Risk of overdiagnosis: The risk of overdiagnosis was estimated 8.9% (95%CI -18.2-32.4) after 11-year follow-up of screen-detected cases. - Impact of various screening intervals: Longer screening and follow-up intervals (<10 m; 10-14 m; 15-21 m; 22-26 m and >26 m) helped discriminate between benign and malignant; however, the lung cancer proportion also increased with longer intervals (2%, 3%, 3%, 7%, 11%, respectively, $P = 0.001$). The analysis of the final screening round (with 2.5-year interval) showed similar lung cancer detection rate and PPV compared to former rounds. A higher proportion of later stage lung cancer was observed in the final round (17.3% compared to 6.8% in former rounds, $P = 0.02$) and more interval cancers found in the 	
--	--	--	---	--

			2.5-year interval than 1-year and 2-year intervals (28 vs 5 and 19, respectively).	
<p>NLST (Black 2014; Hunger et al., 2021; Jonas et al., 2021; Pinsky, 2014; Pinsky et al., 2018; Pinsky et al., 2015; Team, 2011, 2013, 2019)</p>	<p>US 2002-2004 1) Annual LDCT screening for 3 y (I) 2) Annual CXR screening for 3 y (C) Criteria: D > 4 mm</p>	<p>N = 53,452 I = 26,722 C = 26,730 S = 52,344* Mean age 61 y (55-74 y) 59% Male Median follow-up 11.3 y for incidence; 12.3 y for mortality Population: former^d or current^b smokers Baseline smoking status: 52% former smoker^a; 48% current smoker^e *Baseline screening round</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: The baseline compliance was 98.5% for LDCT and 97.4% for CXR, which decreased slightly at year 3 where the compliance rate was 90.2% for LDCT and 87.3% for CXR. Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: The confirmed number of lung cancer cases were comparable between LDCT arm (6.4%, 1701 of 26,722) and CXR arm (6.3%, 1681 of 26,730), giving an RR of 1.01 (95%CI 0.95-1.09). - Detection rate: Considering a total of 75,126 LDCT scans performed with 18,146 (24.2%) positive/indeterminate findings, the overall recall rate and lung cancer detection rate were 24.2% and 1.1%, respectively. - Stage: Compared to the CXR arm, there was a higher proportion of lung cancer cases diagnosed stage I in the LDCT arm (27.5% vs 39.6%; $P < 0.0001$). - Lung cancer mortality: The lung cancer mortality was 42.9 per 1000 subjects in the LDCT arm versus 46.2 per 1000 in the CXR arm with the RR estimated 0.92 (95%CI 0.85-1.00; $P = 0.05$). With adjusted analysis, the lung cancer mortality RR was 0.89 (95%CI 0.8-0.997). - Sensitivity/Specificity: The sensitivity and specificity for LDCT were 93.8% (95%CI 90.6-96.3) and 73.4% (95%CI 72.8-73.9) whilst 73.5% (95%CI 67.2-79.8) and 91.3% – 	<p>Power calculation: Y NLST compared LDCT screening to screening with CXR as control Diameter-based nodule-management protocol</p>

			<p>95%CI 91.0 - 91.6) for CXR. The overall PPV for LDCT arm was 3.8% (270 of 7181) and 5.7% (136 of 2379) for the CXR arm. The FPR was 23% in each of the three screening rounds, which led to costs for further workups including other diagnostic procedure (90.4%) and imaging (81%). Around 2.7% of false-positive cases were subjected to invasive diagnostic procedures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk of overdiagnosis: An analysis published after extended follow-up (11.3 years) revealed a minimal excess of cumulative incidence of lung cancer in the careening arm (RR 1.01; 95%CI 0.95-1.09) and estimated 3.1% risk of overdiagnosis. - Risk of radiation: Considering an average effective dose of 1.5mSv, the lung cancer excess risk due to LDCT was estimated 0.23% for men and 0.85% for women. Using a multiplicative model, the lung cancer excess risk due to LDCT was 0.07% for men and 0.14% for women. - Cost effectiveness: The average annual cost of LDCT screening would be \$241 per person. The cost of preventing one lung cancer death was estimated \$240,000. The cost per life-year saved would be below \$19,000. With QALYs being 0.0201 (95%CI 0.0088 to 0.0314), the mean ICER was \$81,000 per QALY gained (95%CI 52,000 to 186,000). 	
<p>PLCO (Paul Flores et al., 2018; Pinsky et al.,</p>	<p>US 1993-2001</p>	<p>N = 154,887 I = 77,443 C = 77,444 S = NR</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: NR</p>	<p>PLCO trial was designed to evaluate screening modalities for prostate, lung, colorectal and ovarian cancers.</p>

<p><u>2019; Prorok et al., 2018)</u></p>	<p>1) Annual CXR screenings for 3 y (never smoker) or 4 y (I) 2) Unscreened control (C) Criteria: one or more of the following: nodule, mass, hilar or mediastinal lymph node enlargement, infiltrate, consolidation, or alveolar opacity</p>	<p>Median age NR (55-74 y) Median follow-up 17 y 49.5% Male Population: general Current, former, never smokers or unknown</p>	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: After 13 years of follow-up, 1838 and 1737 lung cancer cases were confirmed in the screening and control arm, respectively (RR 1.06; 95%CI 0.99-1.13; <i>P</i> = 0.09). - Detection rate: Instead of lung cancer-specific analysis, only the overall PPV was reported as 4.2% with 96% FPR. The overall cancer detection rate was 3.38 per 1000 screened. - Stage: NR - Lung cancer & all-cause mortality: The overall mortality rate after 17-year follow-up was 0.966 for men (RR; 95%CI 0.943-0.989; <i>P</i> = 0.004) and 1.002 for women in the screening arm compared to control arm. The number of death due to lung cancer was comparable in both arms (16.2% for both; RR 1.008; 95%CI 0.947-1.07; <i>P</i> = 0.80). - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Power calculation: Y Lung cancer screening was evaluated by comparing CXR screening group with non-screening control.</p>
<p><u>UKLS (Balata et al., 2021; Field et al., 2016)</u></p>	<p>UK 2011-2013 1) Single LDCT screening (I) 2) Unscreened control (C) Criteria: $D \geq 3 \text{ mm}$ or $V \geq 15 \text{ mm}^3$</p>	<p>N = 4055 I = 2028 C = 2027 S = 1994 Mean age 67.1 y (50-75 y) 74.9% Male ≥ 10 y follow-up</p>	<p>Uptake: 75,958 (30.7%) of 247,354 contacted were positive responders. 4061 individuals (5.3% of all positive responders and 46.5% of all high-risk positive responders) consented and were recruited into the RCT. 4055 randomised.</p> <p>Compliance: Among the 2028 participants, 1994 individuals completed the baseline scan (98.3%).</p> <p>Outcomes:</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR Follow-up CT scans in suspicious cases; further referral to multidisciplinary team (MDT) clinics based on nodule size criteria</p>

		<p>Population: general</p> <p>Baseline smoking status (screening arm): 61.6% former smoker; 38.3% current smoker; 0.1% never smoker</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lung cancer incidence: Among 1994 individuals completing the baseline scan, 1015 (50.9%) individuals were recommended for repeat scans. A total of 114 individuals (5.7%) were referred to the MDT, among which 42 were diagnosed with lung cancer (2.1%). - Detection rate: NR - Stage: Most participants diagnosed with lung cancer underwent surgery (83.3%), reflecting the high proportion of disease detected at early stages (I and II). - Lung cancer & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: FPR was calculated as 3.6% (72/1994). - Cost effectiveness: Under the protocol of UKLS trial, a total of 3363 CT scans were required (single area, no contrast, mean unit cost £84). After the baseline scans, 114 individuals were referred to the MDT for further work-ups, where an additional 122 CT scans (≤ 3 area, with contrast, mean unit cost £135), 20 guided needle biopsies (mean unit cost £863), 50 PET scans (mean unit cost £425) and 4 endobronchial ultrasound biopsies (mean unit cost £1461) were requested. Regarding the treatment of 42 diagnosed lung cancer cases, 35 surgeries (mean unit cost £7502), 5 radiotherapies (mean unit cost £3039) and 11 chemotherapies (mean unit cost £3883) were undertaken. Furthermore, 4 patients received surgical biopsies/resection (mean unit cost £4295) for benign disease while 2 patients received palliative care (mean unit cost £340). Altogether, the mean gross current costs were £687,617, consisting of £282,490 for CT scans; 	
--	--	--	--	--

			<p>£72,592 for the MDT work-up and £332,534 for cancer treatments. Considering the cost range per procedure, an estimated cost would have a 95% CI between £479,173 and £899,794. An additional 10% of gross cost may incur for the screening invitation and selection, rendering the costs to £754,877 (95%CI £544,824 to £966,304). The gross cost avoided for cancer management when presented symptomatically was estimated £213,658 (28% of the management costs after screen detection). The ICER was estimated £8466 per QALY gained (95%CI £5516 to £12634) while the QALYs gained per person screened was 0.03.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Psychosocial harms: The trial allocation led to a short-term (2-4 weeks) distress of participants in the screening arm; yet the overall scores on measures of distress, anxiety and depression were within the normal range. Within the screening arm, the baseline screening results caused short-term cancer distress in participants required a repeat scan or referred to MDT (due to suspected lung abnormalities). The MDT group reported higher distress than other groups with levels close to clinical threshold. Anxiety levels, but not depression, were reported among participants in the screening arm with higher levels of short-term anxiety in the MDT group, yet scores within the normal range. Long-term adverse effects were not observed. 	
--	--	--	--	--

^a ≤ 15 y since quitting

^b ≥ 20 pack-y

^c > 2 h-day for at least 10 y

^d ≤ 10 y since quitting

^e quit after age 50 and < 10 y since quitting

^f ≥ 20 pack-y in the last 10 y or quit < 10 y

^g ≥ 30 pack-y

^h 15 cigarettes/d for ≥ 25 y or 10 cigarettes/d for ≥ 30 y

ⁱ 15 cigarettes/d for >25 y or 10 cigarettes/d for > 30 y

^j ≥ 15 cigarettes/d for ≥ 20 y

	<i>Uptake: Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial</i> <i>Compliance: Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening</i> N=Total number in trial; I=in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S=No. screened
AFB	Autofluorescence bronchoscopy
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
CXR	Chest radiography
D	Diameter
DANTE	Detection and Screening of Early Lung Cancer by Novel Imaging Technology and Molecular Essays
DLCST	Danish Lung Cancer Screening Trial
FPR	False-positive rate
HRQoL	Health-related quality of life
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IRR	Incidence rate ratio
ITALUNG	Italian Lung Cancer Screening Trial
LDCT	Low-dose computed tomography
LSS	Lung Screening Study
LUSI	The German Lung Cancer Screening Intervention Trial
MDT	Multidisciplinary team
NELSON	Nederlands-Leuvens Longkanker Screenings Onderzoek
NLST	National Lung Screening Trial
NPV	Negative predictive value

NR	Not reported
PET	Positron emission tomography
PET-CTB	Positron emission tomography-computed tomography-guided core biopsy
PLCO	The Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial
PPV	Positive predictive value
RCT	Randomised clinical trial
RR	Rate ratio
SD	Standard deviation
UKLS	The UK Lung Cancer Screening
QALY	Quality-adjusted life-years
V	Volume
VDT	Volume doubling time
Y	Year

Oesophageal cancer

Trial	Trial Details	Participants	Outcomes	Results	Notes
BEST3 Fitzgerald et al., 2020a; Fitzgerald et al., 2020b; Swart et al., 2021	RCT UK 2017–2019 Usual care of GP advised endoscopy vs usual care + offer of Cytosponge®-TFF3 procedure	Total number N = 13,514 (enrich) I = 6983 C = 6531 S = 1654 Mean FU 12 mo Population: ≥ 50yrs with > 6m treatment of gastro-	1. Diagnosis of BO at 12 mo in I vs C groups 2. Uptake of Cytosponge®-TFF3 procedure; Number of cases of BO with dysplasia and intestinal	Uptake: In I group, 39% (2679/6983) expressed interest in taking Cytosponge®-TFF3. Compliance 65% of I group (1750/2679) met eligibility criteria and received the procedure, 95% (1654/1750) of whom successfully swallowed the Cytosponge® for sample production: an overall uptake of 24%. Outcomes:	Power calculation: Y Subsequent upper endoscopy offered when TFF3-positive cells identified in I group

	<p>One off</p>	<p>oesophageal reflux. No endoscopy with 5 yrs</p>	<p>metaplasia-associated cancer, by stage at diagnosis; PPV of Cytosponge®-TFF3 test, in subset of patients with subsequent endoscopy after +ve TFF3; Acceptability and safety of Cytosponge®-TFF3 test.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer/BO incidence: 2% (140 /834) participants in I group vs <1% (13/6388) in C group were diagnosed with BO (RR 10.6, 95%CI 6.0–18.8; $P < 0.0001$). Nine cases with early-stage neoplasia were diagnosed in I group vs none in C group. - Detection rate: Among participants taking Cytosponge®-TFF3 procedure, 13% (221/1654) underwent endoscopy due to positive TFF3, 59% (131/221) of whom were diagnosed with BO or OAC. - Stage: Of the 9 neoplasia cases diagnosed in I group, 4 were dysplastic BO and 5 were stage I oesophago-gastric cancer. - Cancer-specific and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: Estimated specificity of the Cytosponge®-TFF3 procedure for detection of BO, dysplasia, or cancer was 94%. - Harms: One case required endoscopic removal of detached Cytosponge. 4% of participants reported a sore throat <p>Cost-effectiveness: An additional 0.015 QALYs per patients was generated with one-off Cytosponge®-TFF3 screening,</p>	
--	----------------	--	--	--	--

				<p>rendering an ICER of £5500 per QALY gained. The probabilistic sensitivity analysis revealed an incremental cost of £78 and 0.015 QALYs for Cytosponge®-TFF3 screening compared to usual care, giving an ICER of £5405 (95%CI -6791 to 17,600). Considering the willingness-to-pay threshold at £20,000 per QALY, there was a 97% probability of Cytosponge®-TFF3 being more cost-effective than usual care. The total budget impact, including screening plus incurred treatment and palliative care for identified BO/OAC was evaluated using the additional cost-per-patient of £82 for one round of Cytosponge®-TFF3 screening, which would cost a total of £21,636,235 spreading over 29 years at an annual cost of £746,077 in UK settings.</p>	
<p>Endoscopic Screening for OC in China Zeng et al. 2020</p>	<p>Cluster RCT China 2015-2017 All I group participants from high-risk areas screened by upper endoscopy. High-risk participants in non-high-risk areas advised for endoscopy</p>	<p>N = 149,956* I = 75,421 C = 74,535 S = 37,922 *from 3 high-risk areas and 4 non-high-risk areas (risk category based on crude mortality rate of OC during 1973–1975) 40–69 years plus</p>	<p>1. OC detection rate Early detection rate (proportion of stage 0/I among all positive cases). i.e. includes oesophageal squamous severe dysplasia, OCIS and stage I invasive OC 2. Screening compliance rate</p>	<p>Uptake: 152,172 (66%) attended the baseline survey from 230,583 invitations. Compliance: Overall compliance rate was 43.8% • <i>High-risk areas:</i> 27,111 in I group and 32,893 in C group. Compliance rate = 42.2% (26,633/63,123 eligible individuals invited had endoscopy). • <i>Non-high-risk areas:</i> 48,310 in I group and 41,642 in C group: 23,532/48,310 identified as high-risk for further endoscopy</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y Trial of upper endoscopic cancer screening of whole oesophagus and stomach cancer and gastric cancer High-risk participants in non-high-risk areas categorised based on bespoke questionnaire</p>

	<p>One-off</p>	<p>No history of cancer No endoscopy in previous 3 years</p> <p>Report after screening baseline complete</p>		<p>Compliance rate = 48.0% (11,289/23,532 invited had endoscopy)</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: Among 37,922 subjects undergoing endoscopy, oesophageal detection (rate) for combined pre- and malignant lesions was 254 (0.7%): 0.9% vs 0.1% in high- and non-high-risk areas, respectively. Older age group (OR = 25.6, 95%CI 13.5–48.4), male (1.6, 95%CI 1.3–2.1) and high-risk areas (8.2, 95%CI 4.9–13.9) were risk factors for positive detection. - Stage: 230 (90.6%) and 24 (9.4%) were early stage vs. advanced stage disease. In high risk areas, 92.9% of detection was early stage vs 53.3% in non-high-risk areas. 195 (0.5%) of cases were severe dysplasia/OCIS and 59 (0.2%) were OC. Additional cases detected were 1692 (4.5%) mild/moderate dysplasia and 4349 (11.5%) oesophagitis. - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
--	----------------	--	--	---	--

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harms: overall, 0.3 per 1000 screened had complications from endoscopy (8 cases with bleeding, 2 oesophageal perforation, 1 gastric perforation, 1 gastro-spasm). 	
<p>Upper GI screening in non-high risk areas</p> <p><u>Xiao et al. 2020</u></p>	<p>Cluster RCT</p> <p>China</p> <p>2015-2017</p> <p>Upper endoscopic screening with biopsy of suspicious lesions</p> <p>One-off</p>	<p>N =19,981*</p> <p>I = 10,416</p> <p>C = 9565</p> <p>S = 2388</p> <p>*across non-high incidence areas i.e. urban settings</p> <p>40–69 yrs</p> <p>Plus</p> <p>No personal history of cancer no endoscopy in previous 3 yrs</p> <p>Report after screening baseline</p>	<p>1. UGC mortality</p> <p>2. OC detection rate</p> <p>Incidence rate</p> <p>Survival rate</p> <p>Stage at diagnosis</p> <p>Feasibility</p>	<p>Uptake: 20,156 (74%) consented to participate of 27,116 individuals contacted.</p> <p>Compliance: 5242 (50.3%) of I group were estimated to be high-risk (based on bespoke questionnaire). 2388 (45.6%) underwent endoscopic screening. Older age and higher household income were positively associated with compliance.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/Detection rate: Three OC (0.13%) were detected (one stage Ib SCC and two severe hyperplasia). 1276/1488 pathologies detected were not cancerous or pre-cancerous. - Stage: 29 (1.21%) pre-cancerous oesophageal lesions were detected (two moderate and 27 mild dysplasia). 152 low-grade lesions were detected (141 mild oesophagitis, 8 acanthosis, 2 basal cell hyperplasia, 1 moderate oesophagitis.) Older age (OR= 1.07, 95% CI 1.02–1.13), male gender (OR = 2.42, 95% CI 1.11–5.27), and family cancer history (OR = 2.62, 95% CI 1.23– 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>Trial of endoscopic cancer screening of whole oesophagus and stomach cancer and gastric cancer</p> <p>Study conducted in one of non-high-risk centres in the National screening of upper gastrointestinal cancer in China study</p>

				<p>5.57 correlated with a higher risk of oesophageal precancerous lesions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
<p>Effect of screening on OC stage</p> <p><u>Chen-Tao Guan 2018</u></p>	<p>Population based cluster randomised control study</p> <p>2012-2016</p>	<p>N = 39,494 I = 18,316 C = 21,178 S ~ 6410 FU - NR</p>	<p>1. TNM disease stage 2. Mortality</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: Compliance rate was 35% in I group vs. 50% in C group</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/ OC detection rate: was 199 and 141 in I and C groups, respectively. - Stage: Proportion of cases with TNM stage from I to IV were 43.56%, 34.65%, 20.79%, and 0.99% in I group vs. 32.35%, 41.18%, 22.06%, and 4.41% in C group (P=.28). - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Underlying risk of OC in the two study areas is not clear.</p> <p>Only ~ 50% of cases had TNM data available</p>
<p>ESECC</p> <p><u>He et al. 2019</u></p> <p><u>Li et al. 2019</u></p>	<p>Cluster RCT</p> <p>China</p> <p>2012-2016</p> <p>Screening by endoscopy with biopsy of all lesions</p>	<p>N = 33,948 I = 17,151 C = 16,797 S = 15,299 45–69 years plus No history of cancer No endoscopy in previous 5 years</p>	<p>1. OC-specific mortality 2. All-cause mortality Incidence of advanced OC Cost per QALY - NR</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: 15,299/17,151 allocated to I group completed UCI endoscopy (89%)</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence: - Detection rate/Stage: High-grade lesions: 15,188 had at least one biopsy from which 113 (0.74%) high-grade 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p>

	One-off			<p>lesions were detected: 34 (0.22%) cases were OC. Pre-malignant lesions accounted for 79/113 (69.9%): 63 (0.41%) severe dysplasia, 16 (0.11%) OCIS. 24 high-grade lesions in other UGI sites were also found incidentally.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low-grade lesions: Mild and moderate dysplasia was detected in 473 (3.11%) and 87 (0.57%) of cases, respectively. Acanthosis, oesophagitis or basal cell hyperplasia was diagnosed in 14.0%, 14.97% and 18.93% of cases, respectively. Truncated prevalence (aged 45–69 years) of high-grade oesophageal lesions and overall UGI lesions was ~ 744.0/100,000 and 902.0/100,000, respectively. He et al. 2019 - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Cost-effectiveness: Cost per valid endoscopy was \$196. Costs for detecting one OC and one early-stage OC were \$26,347 and \$37,687, respectively (\$18,074, and \$25,853 after exclusion of protocol-driven costs.) In a simulated screening programme, annual costs decreased by 40%+ at 10-years. Li et al. 2019 	<p>Costs adjusted to US \$ rate for 2018</p>
--	---------	--	--	--	--

	<i>Uptake:</i> Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial <i>Compliance:</i> Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening N= Total number in trial; I= in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S= No. screened
BEST3	Barrett's OESophagus Trial 3
BO	Barrett's Oesophagus
C [group]	Control/unscreened group
ESECC	Endoscopic Screening for Oesophageal Cancer in China
FU	Follow up
I [group]	Intervention group(s)
NR	Not reported
OC	Oesophageal adenocarcinoma
OCIS	Oesophageal cancer in-situ
QALY	Quality adjusted life years
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
SCC	Squamous cell carcinoma
TFF3	Trefoil factor 3
UGI	Upper gastrointestinal
UGC	Upper gastrointestinal cancer

Ovarian Cancer

Trial	Trial details	Participants	Outcomes/Results	Notes
PLCO (Buhling et al., 2017; Buys et al., 2011; Doroudi et al., 2017;	US 1993-2001 1) Annual CA-125 blood test for 6 y	N = 78,216 I = 39,105 C = 39,111 S = 34,253	Uptake: NR Compliance: Compliance rate at baseline was 85% for CA-125 and 84% for TVS. These rates reduced to 79% and 78% by the 4 th screening.	PLCO trial was designed to evaluate screening modalities for prostate, lung, colorectal and ovarian cancers.

<p>Henderson et al., 2018; Lai et al., 2016; Pinsky et al., 2019; Prorok et al., 2018)</p>	<p>and annual TVS for 4 y (I) 2) Unscreened control (C) Criteria: CA-125 \geq 35 U/ml TVS results with (1) ovarian V \geq 10 cm³; (2) cyst V \geq 10 cm³; (3) any solid area or papillary projection extending into the cavity of a cystic ovarian tumor of any size; and (4) any mixed (solid and cystic) component within a cystic ovarian tumour.</p>	<p>Median age 62.8 y (55-74 y) Median follow-up 17 y Population: general</p>	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ovarian cancer incidence: A total of 239 and 213 ovarian cancer cases were confirmed in the screening group and control group, respectively. The incidence rate was 1.13 (RR; 95%CI 0.94-1.36). - Detection rate: Instead of ovarian cancer-specific analysis, only the overall PPV was reported as 4.2% with FPR 96%. The overall cancer detection rate was 3.38 per 1000 screened. - Stage: The patients diagnosed with stage I or II disease was 29% and 17% in the screening group and control group, respectively ($P = 0.085$). Patients with stage IIIC and IV disease was 52% in the screening group while 75% in the control group ($P = 0.031$). - Ovarian cancer & all-cause mortality: The number of ovarian cancer death was 250 (246 with ovaries) and 219 (209 with ovaries) in the screening and control group, respectively, leading to an ovarian cancer mortality of 1.10 (RR; 95%CI 0.86-1.40) or 1.18 in women with ovaries (RR; 95%CI 0.98-1.42). The number of all-cause deaths among the whole women participants was 8953 in the screening arm versus 8810 in the control arm, leading to the all-cause mortality of 1.002 in women (RR; 95%CI 0.973-1.031). The mortality analysis targeting the subgroup of participants with family histories of ovarian (22,355 participants; 28,6%) or breast cancer (2708 participants; 3.5%) was reported. The ovarian cancer and all-cause mortality 	<p>Power calculation: Y Bimanual examination of the ovaries was originally part of the screening procedures (first 4 years) but was discontinued in December 1998 because no cancers were detected solely by ovarian palpation and the sensitivity was 5.1% (2/39) with specificity of 99.0% (49,957/50,459); yet in the control group receiving usual care, a high proportion of women underwent bimanual examination with ovarian palpation. TVS was performed using a 5- to 7.5-MHz transvaginal probe.</p>
---	---	---	--	--

			<p>were 0.99 (RR; 95%CI 0.93-1.06) and 0.66 (RR; 95%CI 0.39-1.12), respectively.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Survival: There was an improved survival of patients diagnosed with ovarian cancer in the screening arm compared to the control arm. (RR 0.66; 95%CI 0.47-0.93). Yet such survival improvement did not translate to mortality reduction. - Risk of overdiagnosis: There was a possible risk of overdiagnosis. 	
<p>QUEST (Andersen et al., 2007; Henderson et al., 2018)</p>	<p>US</p> <p>NR</p> <p>1) Control with usually care (C)</p> <p>2) Risk education (I₁)</p> <p>3) Screening with CA-125 & TVS (I₂)</p> <p>4) Screening with CA-125 & TVS + risk education (I₃)</p> <p>Criteria: CA-125 ≥ 35 U/ml for pre-menopausal and</p>	<p>N = 592 I₁ = 150 I₂ = 140 I₃ = 152 C = 150 S = 236</p> <p>Median age 44.8-45.8 y (≥ 30 y)</p> <p>Median follow-up 2 y</p> <p>Population: general</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: The overall compliance rate of screening was 80.8% and 64.5% of women completed all 4 screenings. For women allocated to risk education groups (Group 2 and 4), 73% attended the full 4 workshops.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ovarian cancer incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Ovarian cancer & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Psychosocial harms: In general, no statistically significant differences were found among four groups in terms of mental and physical health as well as cancer worry scores. Compared to the non-screening control group, participants in the screening arms reported no 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>The screening protocol included: CA125 blood test at month 1 & 12; TVS at month 6 & 18</p> <p>Risk education was provided as four 2-h workshops.</p> <p>No detail of TVS was provided.</p>

	> 30 U/ml for post-menopausal women TVS results with (1) enlarged ovaries; (2) abnormal morphology		alterations in the level of cancer worry and QOL. Among women participating in the screening, those with abnormal results (32) reported increased levels of cancer worry compared to those receiving normal screening results (OR 2.8; 95%CI 1.1-7.2).	
SCSOCS (Buhling et al., 2017; Kobayashi et al., 2008)	Japan 1985-2002 1) Annual CA-125 blood test and pelvis ultrasound for 5 y (I) 2) Unscreened control (C) Criteria: CA125 \geq 35 U/ml Ultrasound results with (1) ovarian D \geq 4 cm; (2) complex cyst morphology	N = 82,487 I = 41,688 C = 40,799 S = 34,184 Median age NR (45-85 y) Median follow-up 9.2 y Population: post-menopausal women	Uptake: NR Compliance: The compliance rate of baseline screening was not reported. The compliance with subsequent screenings was 82% at the 2 nd round; 71% at the 3 rd round; 67% at the 4 th round and 56% at the 5 th round. Outcomes: - Ovarian cancer incidence: A total of 35 ovarian cancer cases were diagnosed in the screening group with 8 of them being interval cases. In the non-screening control, 32 participants were diagnosed with ovarian cancer. - Detection rate: The cancer detection rate was 0.31 per 1000 at baseline screening and ranged between 0.38 and 0.74 per 1000 in the following screening rounds. - Stage: The cases with stage I disease were 63% in the screening arm compared to 38% in the control arm ($P = 0.2285$). - Ovarian cancer & all-cause mortality: NR	Power calculation: NR In the first 5 years of the trial, ultrasound was performed mainly by the transabdominal method instead of transvaginal method. Yet no detail of the TVS was provided.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitivity/Specificity: The sensitivity, specificity and PPV of the pelvic ultrasound for ovarian cancer detection was estimated 74%, 99.9% and 23.3%, respectively. 	
<p>UKCTOCS (Barrett et al., 2014; Buhling et al., 2017; Fallowfield et al., 2017; Gentry-Maharaj et al., 2015; Henderson et al., 2018; Kalsi et al., 2021; Menon et al., 2021; Menon et al., 2017; Moss et al., 2018)</p>	<p>UK 2001-2014</p> <p>1) Multimodal screening group (MMS): Annual CA-125 blood test and annual TVS for 11 y (I₁)</p> <p>2) Ultrasound screening group (USS): Annual TVS for 11 y (I₂)</p> <p>3) Usual care control (101,359)</p> <p>Criteria: Intermediate risk (≥ 1/1818) or elevated risk (≥ 1/500) based on ROCA; one or</p>	<p>N = 202,638 I₁ = 50,640 I₂ = 50,639 C = 101,359 S = NR</p> <p>Median age 60 y (50-74 y)</p> <p>Median follow-up 16.3 y</p> <p>Population: post-menopausal women</p>	<p>Uptake: 288,955 (23%) of 1,243,282 women sent an invitation were positive responders.</p> <p>Compliance: NR</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ovarian cancer incidence: USS arm: 960 screen-positive women underwent surgery, and 113 cases were confirmed with ovarian/tubal cancer, in which 80 were invasive epithelial cancers. Among 2055 women diagnosed with ovarian/tubal cancers, 522 (1%) were in the MMS group; 517 (1%) were in the USS group and 1016 (1%) in the unscreened control group. - Detection rate: A total of 45 cancer cases (20 borderline) were detected in the USS group while 42 cancer cases (8 borderline) were detected in the MMS group. - Stage: Among the 80 invasive epithelial cancers detected in USS arm, 37.5% (95%CI 26.9-49.0) were stage I/II. There were 50 interval invasive epithelial cancer cases where 6% were stage I/II. Among cases detected in MMS arm, there were increased cases with 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>TVS was performed using Mainly Kretz SA9900.</p>

	<p>both ovaries with complex morphology, simple cysts > 60 cm³ or ascites</p>		<p>stage I disease (47.2%, 95%CI 19.7-81.1) and decreased cases with stage IV disease (24.5%, 95%CI -41.8 to -2.0) compared to the control arm.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ovarian cancer & all-cause mortality: A total of 1206 women died of ovarian cancer where 296 (0.6%) were in the MMS group; 291 (0.6%) were in the USS group; 619 (0.6%) were in the unscreened control group. The ovarian cancer mortality was comparable among three groups. - Sensitivity/Specificity: The sensitivity, specificity and PPV for detecting ovarian/tubal cancers in the USS arm was estimated 68.5% (95%CI 60.8-75.5), 99.7% (95%CI 99.7-99.7) and 11.8% (95%CI 9.8-14), respectively. The sensitivity, specificity and PPV for detecting invasive epithelial cancers was 61.5% (95%CI 52.6-69.9), 99.7% (95%CI 99.7-99.7) and 8.3% (95%CI 6.7-10.3), respectively. For the MMS arm, the sensitivity, specificity and PPV for detecting ovarian/tubal cancers was estimated 89.4%, 99.8% and 43.3%, respectively. The sensitivity, specificity and PPV for detecting invasive epithelial/tubal cancers was 89.5%, 99.8% and 35.1%, respectively. - Cost-effectiveness: An analysis constructed a Markov simulation model to compare MMS with non-screening in the US under the UKCTOCS protocols. Provided screening women starting at the age of 50 with MMS, the cost-effectiveness was estimated 70% under circumstances that decision makers were willing to pay \$150,000 per QALY. Screening led to 15% mortality 	
--	---	--	---	--

			<p>reduction and an ICER between \$106,187 (95%CI 97,496-127,793) and \$155,256 (95%CI 150,369-198,567).</p> <p>Another study used a Markov model and a predictive extrapolation based on the average life expectancy in the UK to evaluate the with-in trial cost-effectiveness. The USS vs non-screening ICER was estimated £625,801 per LYG (95%CI 620,451-631,245) while the MMS vs non-screening ICER was £91,452 per LYG (95%CI 90.909-92,001) with CA125-ROCA cost of £20. Provided CA125-ROCA cost of £15, the predictive extrapolation over the expected lifetime of women in UKCTOCS estimated an ICER of £ 30,033 per LYG whilst the Markov model estimated an extrapolated QALY of 0.0581 and the ICER of £46,922 per QALY.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk of overdiagnosis: There were more borderline epithelial ovarian cancers diagnosed in the screening group (97 of 101,279) than control group (62 of 101,359) ($P = 0.005$). Between the two screening arms, there were more screen-detected borderline cancers in the USS arm compared to the MMS arm (92.3% vs 55.6%; $P < 0.001$). - Psychosocial harms: The impact of ovarian cancer screening on sexual activity and functioning was evaluated and there was no difference found between screening group (both MMS and USS) and control group in general. Women in the USS group who required further repeated screening reported lower pleasure scores in the questionnaire (mean difference - 	
--	--	--	---	--

			<p>0.14, $P = 0.046$). Women in both MMS and USS group who had ≥ 2 repeat screens reported decreased pleasure scores compared to their annual scores (mean difference -0.16, $P = 0.005$). The mean pleasure score also decreased when more intensive screens were required (mean difference -0.09, $P = 0.046$). The potential effect of screening on patients' anxiety and psychological morbidity was evaluated in a 7-year follow-up and found that the mean differences of anxiety scores were small, though statistically significant due to large sample size, between all participants at the baseline and women required repeat screens. The overall psychological wellbeing, which was measured using GHQ-12, was not affected by the screening per se. The risk of psychological morbidity was found increased when women required higher level of repeat screens (OR 1.28; 95%CI 1.18-1.39).</p>	
<p>UK Pilot (Henderson et al., 2018)</p>	<p>UK 1989-1998</p> <p>1) Annual CA-125 blood test for 3 y (I)</p> <p>2) Unscreened control I</p> <p>Criteria:</p>	<p>N = 21,935 I = 10,958 C = 10,977 S = NR</p> <p>Median age NR (≥ 45 y)</p> <p>Median follow-up NR (0-8 y)</p>	<p>Uptake: By invitation to 22,000 women who had participated in a previous study [Jacobs et al., 1999 https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(98)10261-1]</p> <p>Compliance: In I group, 6792 (31%) underwent first, 6672 (31%) second and 6455 (30%) third screen. [Jacobs et al., 1999 https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(98)10261-1]</p> <p>Outcomes:</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>Women with elevated CA-125 levels were subjected to follow-up including TVS.</p>

	CA125 \geq 30 U/ml	Population: post-menopausal women	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ovarian cancer incidence: In total, 36 patients were diagnosed with ovarian cancers (0.2%). - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Ovarian cancer & all-cause mortality: There were 9 deaths due to ovarian cancer in the screening group (0.08%) while 18 deaths in the non-screening control group (0.16%), leading to a relative risk of 0.50 (95%CI 0.22-1.11). - Sensitivity/Specificity: There were 462 women receiving false-positive screening results (4.2%) among which 0.2% underwent surgery with no complications reported. 	
--	----------------------	--	---	--

	<p>Uptake: Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial</p> <p>Compliance: Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening</p> <p>N=Total number in trial; I=in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S=No. screened</p>
CA-125	Cancer antigen 125
D	Diameter
FPR	False-positive rate
GHQ-12	12-item General Health Questionnaire
HRQoL	Health-related quality of life
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IRR	Incidence rate ratio
LYG	Life-year gained
MMS	Multimodal screening group
NPV	Negative predictive value
NR	Not reported
OR	Odds ratio

PLCO	The Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial
PPV	Positive predictive value
RCT	Randomised clinical trial
ROCA	Risk of ovarian cancer algorithm
RR	Rate ratio
SCSOCS	Shizuoka Cohort Study of Ovarian Cancer Screening
SD	Standard deviation
TVS	Transvaginal ultrasound
UKCTOCS	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening
USS	Ultrasound screening group
QALY	Quality-adjusted life-years
QOL	Quality of life
QUEST	Quality of Life, Education, and Screening Trial
V	Volume
VDT	volume doubling time

Prostate cancer

Trial	Study Details	Participants	Outcomes	Results	Notes
CAP trial <u>Martin et al.</u> <u>2018</u>	Cluster RCT UK 2001–2009 PSA. Biopsy if ≥3ng/mL One-time screening	N = 419,582 I = 189,386* C = 219,439* S = 67,313 *available for analyses Men aged 50- 69 yr Median FU 10yr	1. PCa-specific mortality 2. Disease incidence All-cause mortality Stage Grade (Gleason) HRQoL - NR Cost effectiveness - NR	Uptake: Randomisation by GP practice; 73% of the 573 eligible practices agreed to participate. 75,707 (40% of I group) attended for PSA testing. Compliance: 67,313 of I group (36%) underwent PSA testing. Outcomes: 64,436 had a valid PSA result, of whom 6857 (11%) had a PSA level 3–19.9 ng/mL: 5850/6857 (85%) had a prostate biopsy.	Power calculation: Y However, a (low) compliance with screening rate (~35%) and a lower than expected number of control arm PCa deaths has raised questions whether the trial was under-powered

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/ Detection rate: Diagnosis of PCa was n = 8054 (4.3%) in I group vs n = 7853 (3.6%) in C group; RR = 1.19 (95% CI, 1.14–1.25). - Stage/Grade: More low-risk tumors identified in I group (n = 3263/189,386 [1.7%]) vs C group (n = 2440/219,439 [1.1%]); difference per 1000 men = 6.11 (95% CI, 5.38–6.84), P <.001. - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: 25,459 deaths in I group vs 28,306 in C group; RR = 0.99 (95% CI, 0.94–1.03); P = .49. PCa-specific mortality was 549 (0.30 per 1000 person-years) in I group vs 647 (0.31 per 1000 person-years) in C group (rate difference, –0.013 per 1000 person-years (95% CI, -0.047–0.022); RR = 0.96 (95% CI, 0.85–1.08, P = .50 - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Trial adopts a less intensive screen frequency to minimize over-diagnosis, however note increased detection rate for low-risk cases, without mortality benefit.</p> <p>The ProtecT trial of treatments for localized PCa was embedded within CAP trial</p>
<p>ERSPC <u>Ilic et al. 2018</u> <u>Hugosson et al. 2019</u> <u>Osses et al. 2018</u> <u>Saarimaki et al. 2017</u></p>	<p>RCT 8 European countries 1993–2003 21 year follow-up PSA ± DRE. Biopsy if ≥3ng/mL</p>	<p>N = 162,389* I = 112,553 C = 128,681 S = 72,525 (screened at least once) *‘core’ age group - Men aged 55-69 yr- is focus of data analysis (some</p>	<p>1. PCa-specific mortality 2. All-cause mortality PCa incidence Stage HRQoL – only Finnish centre, based on a random sample of participants (n=1088) from both</p>	<p>Uptake: Recruitment processes differed across participating countries; some from population registries while others required consent. Of 112,553 allocated to I group, 72,525 (64%) were screened at least once.</p> <p>Compliance: Mean (SD) screens-per-man was 2.1 (1.1).</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/Detection rate: RR for PCa incidence between I and C groups = 1.91 (95% CI, 1.83–1.99) at 9 years (1.64 [1.58–1.69] including 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>Minor protocol variations across 8 European centres</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Belgium • Netherlands • Finland • Italy • Spain • Sweden • Switzerland • France*

<p><u>Schroder et al. 2012</u></p> <p><u>Schroder et al. 2014</u></p> <p><u>Talala et al. 2020</u></p> <p><u>van Leeuwen et al. 2013</u></p> <p><u>Kilpelainen et al. 2013</u></p> <p><u>Walter et al. 2021</u></p> <p><u>Karlsson et al 2021</u></p> <p><u>Booth et al 2018</u></p> <p><u>Heijnsdijk et al 2021</u></p>	<p>Screening every 2-7 yr*</p> <p>*Most centres 4yr with variation eg France 2 yr, Belgium 7yr</p>	<p>centres included men 50-74)</p> <p>15.5 yr median FU</p> <p>16 yr maximum FU</p>	<p>trial groups excluding men with a subsequent diagnosis of prostate cancer.</p> <p>Harms from PCa screening</p>	<p>France data), 1.66 (1.60–1.73) at 11 years, and 1.57 (1.51–1.62) at 13 years. <u>Schroder et al. 2012</u>; <u>Schroder et al. 2014</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage: NR - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: Absolute RR in excess mortality = 0.08 per 1000 person-years. Overall <i>all-cause mortality</i> not significantly different between I and C groups: RR 0.99 (95% CI 0.96–1.01). <u>van Leeuwen et al. 2013</u>. Pooled data from four largest ESPRC centres (N = 141,578) at median FU 9 yr reported excess mortality among men with PCa = 0.29 per 1000 person-years in I group vs 0.37 per 1000 person-years in C group; RR = 0.77 (95% CI, 0.55–1.08). Data from FinRSPC, the largest ERSPC centre (31,866 and 48,278 men in I and C groups, respectively) reported 6618 deaths in the I group (cumulative mortality = 20.8%) vs 10,079 deaths (20.9%), in C group at median 12 yr FU. HR for all-cause mortality = 0.99 (95% CI, 0.96–1.02); P = .69). <u>Kilpelainen et al. 2013</u> <p>21% reduction in <i>PCa specific mortality</i> at 16 yr FU; RR between I and C groups = 0.80 (95% CI, 0.72–0.89, P <0.001. No significant change in RR from 9,11 & 13 yr FU. Absolute group difference in PCa mortality increased from 0.14% at 13 yr to 0.18% at 16 yr. Equates to</p>	<p>*French data excluded from some analyses as failed to comply with screening criterion</p>
---	--	---	---	--	--

				<p>NNI of 742 vs 570 and NND of 26 vs 18, at respective time points.</p> <p>PCa-specific survival for cases detected at screening round 1 significantly worse compared with diagnosis at subsequent screening rounds (HR = 1.86, p<0.001). The pattern of PCa mortality reduction variation across centres, RR range = 0.91–0.63, suggests increased screening intensity may correlate positively to mortality reduction. Hugosson et al. 2019 In FinRSPC (N = 31,866) the largest mortality reduction was in men screened three times (HR 0.17; 95% CI, 0.09–0.33). Pakarainen et al 2019. However, differences in FinRSPC (screening interval of 2 yr; PSA cut-off of 3.0 ng/ml) and Swedish (N = 5901: screening interval 4 yr; PSA cut-off 4.0 ng/ml) protocols ‘unlikely to explain the differences in mortality’ at 13 yr and 16 yr FU. Saarimaki et al. 2017</p> <p>Rotterdam pilot 1 study cohort (N = 1134) reported RR of metastatic (M+) disease and of PCa mortality were 0.46 (95% CI, 0.19–1.11) and 0.48 (95% CI, 0.17–1.36), respectively, in favour of screening at 19 yr FU. Osses et al. 2018</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitivity/Specificity: >20,000 biopsies were performed to detect ~ 5000 cancers, corresponding to PPV of 24%. A quarter of 	
--	--	--	--	--	--

				<p>participants were biopsied at least once, demonstrating low specificity of PSA (with cut-off values of 3–10 ng/mL) as a screening test. Hugosson et al. 2019</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overdiagnosis: The excess PCa incidence in I group was 41% at 16 yr FU) and NND was 18. Hugosson et al. 2019. FinRSPC data (N = 80,149) estimated overdiagnosis in I group as 30%. Kilpelainen et al. 2013. This compares to ~ 60% in overall ERSPC analysis Schroder et al. 2012. A later FinRSPC analysis estimates an overdiagnosis rate between 2.3% and 15.4%, with equivalent results for T1c tumours as a proxy of early-stage screen-detected disease. Walter et al. 2021 - HRQoL: 15 yr FU of FinRSPC (N = 80,458) revealed generic HRQOL measures were comparable between I and C groups. PCa specific HRQOL measures were ‘slightly higher’ in I group vs C group. The only statistically significant difference was for ‘urinary bother’: (UCLA-PCI score 77.9; 95% CI 75.2–80.5 vs 70.9; 95% 66.8–74.9, P=.005). Talala et al. 2020 - Cost-effectiveness: 71 fewer deaths per 10,000 men corresponds with an increase of 652 life-years and 366 QALYs per 10,000 men. PSA screening associated with increased costs for screening (€214/man), diagnostics (€290/man), treatment for localised prostate cancer 	<p>Cost-effectiveness analysis across ERSPC dataset, uses a microsimulation model, from a lifetime societal perspective Discounted costs, quality-adjusted life-years (QALYs) and incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICERs) were calculated</p> <p>Findings are of low certainty due to low statistical power and</p>
--	--	--	--	---	---

				<p>(€294/man) and productivity losses (€77/man), with lower costs for treatment for advanced prostate cancer (-€306/man). Discounting at 3% per annum, the ICER from a societal perspective was €54,918/ per QALY gained. <u>Karlsson et al 2021</u></p> <p>Modelling the effect of screening interval and upper age on mortality (Heijnsdijk et al 2021), predicted a 33% overdiagnosis rate of screen-detected cancers and ICER of \$73,000 per QALY gained, with a simulated two-year interval with an age range of 55–59.</p> <p>20 year FinRSPC data showed cumulative all-cause cost estimates for all men in the trial were equivalent across groups (p =0.64). Mean all-cause costs and PCa-related costs for <i>diagnosed men</i> were respectively ~1% (€700) and ~10% <i>lower</i> (€1100) in I group. Mean all-cause costs and PCa-related costs for <i>men dying from PCa</i> were ~10% (€5100) and ~1% <i>higher</i> (€1700) in I group. <u>Booth et al 2018</u></p>	substantial contamination in C group
<p>Göteborg-1 PCa screening trial</p> <p><u>Arnsrud Godtman et al 2015</u></p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>1995–2014</p> <p>Biennial PSA testing</p> <p>± DRE</p>	<p>N = 20,000</p> <p>I = 9950</p> <p>C = 9949</p> <p>S = 7647</p> <p>Men aged 50-69 yr</p>	<p>1. Absolute and relative risk reduction in PC mortality</p> <p>2. Attendance</p>	<p>Uptake: All 20,000 men in a population registry were randomised into the trial. In I group, n = 5855/9950 (59%) attended the first screening round.</p> <p>Compliance: Of 5855 attending the first screening round, 661 (11%) had a PSA ≥ 3 ng/mL threshold for biopsy.</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>The Goteborg Randomized Population-Based Prostate Cancer Screening Trial started in 1995. Since 1996, the trial has</p>

<p><u>Franlund et al 2018</u> <u>Hugosson et al 2017</u> <u>Carlsson et al 2017b</u></p>		<p>20yr FU</p>	<p>PCa incidence PCa mortality rate and RR in sociodemographic subgroups</p>	<p>77% (7647/9950) attended screening at least once; 74% of study population attended all study invitations.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/Detection rate: IRR for PCa incidence at 18 years = 9.7% [95% CI 9.2–10.2] per 1000 person-years in I group vs 6.5% (95% CI 6.1–6.9) per 1000 person-years in C group. The HR for PCa incidence in I vs C group was 5.2, 1.9 & 1.1 at 1, 5 and 15 yrs. <u>Hugosson et al 2017</u> - 754/ 5174 (14.6%) men with PSA level <3 ng/mL at initial screen were diagnosed with PCa during a median FU of 18.9 years. Cumulative PCa incidence was 17.2%: 7.9% for PSA levels <0.99ng/mL; 26.0% for 1–1.99 ng/mL; 40.3% for 2–2.99 ng/mL (p<0.001). <u>Franlund et al 2018</u> - Stage/Grade: Of 1396 (14%) PCa cases in I group, 7.0%, 4.7%, 1.4% and 0.7% were low risk, intermediate risk, high risk and advanced, respectively. - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: 2844/9950 (28.6%) died of all causes in I group vs 2857/9,949 (28.7%) in C group, at 18 yr. <u>Hugosson et al 2017</u> <p>At 18 yr, cumulative PCa-specific mortality was 0.98% (95% CI 0.78–1.22%) in I group vs 1.50%</p>	<p>constituted the Swedish arm of the ERSPC.</p>
--	--	----------------	---	---	--

				<p>(95% CI 1.26–1.79%) in C group: an absolute reduction of 0.52% (95% CI 0.17–0.87%). RR for PCa death was 0.65 (95% CI 0.49–0.87). NNI = 231 and NND = 10 to prevent one PCa death.</p> <p>Absolute risk reduction for PCa mortality was improved at 20-yr FU compared to 14-yr FU (0.52 vs 0.40), NNI (231 vs 293) and NND (10 vs 12). However, relative risk reduction decreased (RR 0.56 vs 0.65) <u>Arnsrud Godtman et al 2015</u></p> <p>Greater benefit for PCa mortality was demonstrated for all men starting screening at 55–59 years (RR = 0.47, 95% CI 0.29–0.78) and for men with low education (RR = 0.49, 95% CI 0.31–0.78) <u>Hugosson et al 2017</u></p> <p>A nested cohort study (to evaluate effect of age at start screening on PCa-specific mortality) compared 3479 men aged 50–54 yr in I group vs 4060 aged 51–55 yr in C group. At 17 yr FU, PCa death (IRR = 0.29, 95% CI 0.11–0.67) and the risk of metastases (IRR = 0.43, 95% CI 0.22–0.79) were lower in I group: 57 fewer PCa deaths per 10 000 men (95% CI 22–92); NNI = 176 and NND =16, respectively. <u>Carlsson et al 2017b,</u></p> <p>- Sensitivity/Specificity: NR</p>	
Norrköping PCa screening trial	Quasi-randomised CT (random	N = 9026 I = 1494 C = 7532	1. PCa-specific mortality	<p>Uptake: Identification of sample via National Population Register. Attendance was 1161/1492 (78%) at round one.</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>Due to change of protocol, many men did not receive</p>

<p><u>Sandblom et al 2011</u></p> <p><u>van Leeuwen et al 2012</u></p>	<p>allocation of every 6th man).</p> <p>Sweden</p> <p>1987–1996</p> <p>Every third year</p> <p>Screening DRE only for first 2 rounds. From 1993, +PSA with 4 µg/L cut-off.</p>	<p>S = 1161</p> <p>50-69 yr</p> <p>20 yr FU</p>	<p>2. PCa incidence</p> <p>Tumour stage</p> <p>Tumour grade</p> <p>Treatments</p>	<p>Compliance: Attendance was 957/1363 (70%), 895/1210 (74%), and 446/606 (74%), at rounds two to four respectively.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/Detection rate: PCa incidence was = 85/1494 (5.7%) and 292/7532 (3.9%) in I and C groups, respectively. <u>Sandblom et al 2011</u> - Stage: Percentage of localised tumours (T1-2,N0,M0) was significantly higher in I group (56.5%) vs C group (26.7%, P<0.001): Non-localised tumour incidence was 2.5% in I group vs 2.8% in C group (P=0.44). <u>Sandblom et al 2011</u> - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: RR for PCa mortality in I group = 1.16 (95% CI 0.78–1.73). PCa-specific survival favoured the C group, HR = 1.23 (95% CI 0.94–1.62) P=0.13. PCa specific survival adjusted for age-at-study-entry = HR 1.58 (95% CI 1.06–2.36), P=0.024. In a survival analysis adjusted for age comparing PCa-specific survival in C group with I group, the age adjusted HR = 1.23 (0.94–1.62; P=0.13). <u>van Leeuwen et al 2012</u> - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>PSA test, some men only received one PSA test and none received more than two PSA tests.</p>
<p><u>PLCO trial Ilic et al 2018</u></p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>US</p> <p>1993–2001</p>	<p>N = 76,685</p> <p>I = 38,340</p> <p>C = 38,343</p> <p>S = ?</p>	<p>1. PCa-specific mortality</p> <p>2. All-cause mortality</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: Approximately 92% of the study participants were followed to 10 years and 57% to 13 years. At transition to centralised FU</p>	<p>PLCO trial evaluates screening modalities for prostate, lung, colorectal and ovarian cancers.</p>

<p><u>Andriole et al 2012</u> <u>Pierre-Victor et al 2021</u> <u>Pinsky et al 2017</u> <u>Pinsky et al 2019a</u> <u>Pinsky et al 2019b</u> <u>Prorok et al 2021</u> <u>Tsodikov et al 2017</u></p>	<p>Annual screening with PSA for 6 yrs, + DRE for 4 years</p>	<p>Men aged 55–74 yr Median 16.9 yr FU for I group</p>	<p>PCa incidence Tumour stage Tumour grade (by Gleason category) Harms of screening</p>	<p>(end of 2011), 11.2% of patients in I group vs 15.2% in C group refused further FU. Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/Detection rate: PCa incidence: Overall 20-yr cumulative PCa incidence was 26.4% (95% CI, 24.8–28.1); RR = 1.05 (95% CI, 1.01–1.09). RRs by Gleason category were 1.17 (95% CI, 1.11–1.23) for Gleason 2–6 disease, 1.00 (95% CI, 0.93–1.07) for Gleason 7 and 0.89 (95% CI 0.80–0.99) for Gleason 8–10. During screening phase (i.e. first 6 years), 13% of I group PCa cases vs 27% of C group cases were symptomatic; post-screening, percentages were 18% in each group. <u>Pinsky et al 2019a</u> - Stage: Of 4250 I group prostate cancers diagnosed through 13 years, 15.8%, 54.7%, 8.6%, and 1.0% were stage I to IV respectively at diagnosis. <u>Andriole et al 2012</u> - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: Overall cumulative mortality rates were 1.2% (95% CI, 0.9–1.7). RR for <i>all-cause mortality</i> was 0.977 (95% CI, 0.950–1.004) in PCa cases. In men overall (i.e. Prostate Lung Colorectal screening combined) there was a significant reduction in overall mortality in the I versus C group: (RR = 0.966; 95% CI, 0.943–0.989; p = 0.004) <u>Pinsky et al 2019b</u>. 	<p>Power calculation: Y A critique of the PLCO prostate trial has been that the original (and a revised) power estimate was too high because it was based on both higher levels of contamination and lower numbers of events than predicted. With extended follow-up and approximately 65% more prostate cancer deaths in the current analysis, the second factor has been mitigated to some extent.</p>
--	---	--	---	---	--

				<p>Data from a cohort of men (N = 2855) with a positive PSA (> 4 ng/mL) or DRE screen followed by a negative biopsy within one year. showed HRs for PCa mortality increased significantly with increasing PSA. Pierre-Victor et al 2021.</p> <p>PCa-specific mortality at 16.9 yrs was 333 (5.5 per 10,000 person-years) in I group vs 352 (5.9 per 10,000 person-years) in C group; RR = 0.93 (95% CI, 0.81–1.08), P= .38. <u>Pinsky et al 2019a</u> HR = 0.93 (95% CI, 0.80–1.08) <u>Pinsky et al 2019b</u> At 15 yrs, approximately 60% of PCa deaths in each group still occurred in cases diagnosed during the first 6 years of the trial. <u>Pinsky et al 2017</u></p> <p>No significant interaction was found between comorbidity status and PCa mortality (RR = 0.99 and RR = 1.06 in ‘no comorbidity’ and ‘comorbidity’ groups, respectively) <u>Andriole et al 2012</u></p> <p>Analyses to reconcile contradictory PCa-mortality results from EESPC and PLCO trials modelled effects of screening on PCa mortality controlling for differences in screening intensity in S and C groups of ERSPC and PLCO trials. Mean lead time (MLT) analysis showed no significant differences in ERSPC and PLCO I groups, but longer MLT in the PLCO vs ERSPC C</p>	
--	--	--	--	---	--

				<p>groups. Screening benefit increased with MLT (P=0.0027–0.0032). Screening confers an estimated 7–9% reduction in PC death per year of MLT. This translates into an estimated 25–31% and 27–32% lower risk of PC death under screening as performed in the ERSPC and PLCO I groups, respectively, relative to C groups. <u>Tsodikov et al 2017</u></p> <p>- Sensitivity/Specificity: 14,662 +ve PSA results from 177,275 screens, gives an overall +ve rate of 8.27%. 4707 (32.1%) of the 14,662 +ve screens prompted a biopsy and 1793 cancers were detected. (For positive screens, where the cancer was not identified, a repeat test was used about 60–70% of the time across screening rounds.) The overall PPV was 12.23% and the cancer detection rate was 10.11 per 1000 screens. The PCa false +ve rate was over 80% across study waves. <u>Prorok et al 2021</u></p>	
<p>STHLM3-MRI trial</p> <p>Eklund et al 2021</p> <p>Nordström et al 2021</p>	<p>Non-inferiority RCT</p> <p>Sweden</p> <p>2018–2020</p> <p>MRI + targeted biopsy vs</p>	<p>N = 2293</p> <p>I = 1372</p> <p>C = 921</p> <p>S = 1184</p> <p>Men aged 50–74 yr</p> <p>Higher risk participants</p>	<p>1. Probability of detection of clinically significant PCa</p> <p>2. proportions of benign biopsies and clinically insignificant cancer</p>	<p>Uptake: 12,750 (26%) of 49,118 invited consented to screening and provided blood samples for PSA testing.</p> <p>Compliance: 1372 high risk men were allocated to I group. 1184 had the assigned intervention.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <p>- Incidence/Detection rate: 233 vs 179 PCa cases were detected in I vs C groups. biopsy group, as compared with 106 men (18%) in the standard biopsy</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>In experimental group, MRI was followed by standard biopsy where MRI indicated presence of PCa</p> <p>* Stockholm3 test is a risk prediction</p>

	standard biopsy	based on PSA (≥ 3 ng OR Stockholm3 test ($\geq 11\%$)* FU after screening complete	Serious adverse events 30 days after biopsy	<p>The percentage of clinically insignificant cancers was lower in the experimental biopsy group than in the standard biopsy group (4% [41 participants] vs. 12% [73 participants]; difference, -8 percentage points; 95% CI,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage/Grade: Clinically-significant cancer was diagnosed in 192/929 (21%) vs 106/603 (18%) in I and C groups respectively (3% difference; 95%CI -1 to 7). Clinically-insignificant cancer was diagnosed in 4% vs 12% in I and C groups respectively (8% difference; 95%CI -11 to -5) - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Harms/benefits: I group had a lower incidence of prescription of antibiotics for infection (1.8% vs 4.4%) and admission to hospital (1.2% vs 3.4%) than C group. 	model based on clinical variables (age, first-degree family history of prostate cancer, and previous biopsy), blood biomarkers (total PSA, free PSA, ratio of free PSA to total PSA, human kallikrein 2, macrophage inhibitory cytokine-1, and MSMB), and a polygenic risk score for predicting the risk of prostate cancer with a Gleason score of 7 or higher.
Stockholm trial <u>Lundgren et al 2018</u>	RCT Screening v background population Sweden 1988–2003 PSA, DRE, TRUS. Biopsy on PSA	N = 27,464 (source population) I = 2400 C1 = 621 invited but declined C2 = 25,685 not invited S = 1779	1. PCa-specific mortality 2. All-cause mortality PCa incidence	<p>Uptake/Compliance: Random selection of 2,400 from a population of 27,464 men. 1779/2400 (74%) accepted screening.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incidence/Detection rate: Cumulative PCa incidence at 20 yr was 13.3% (RR = 1.22 [95% CI 1.08–1.38]), 9.0% (RR = 0.83 [95% CI 0.64–1.07]), and 10.9% (RR = 1) in I vs C1 and source populations, respectively. PCa incidence remained higher in I population throughout FU. - Stage: 	Power calculation: Y Statistical power was limited in retrospective calculation

	>10ng/mL and DRE & TRUS One-time screening	Men aged 55-70 years 20 yr FU		<p>- Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: All-cause mortality at 20 years was 972 (54.6%) for I group (IRR = 0.92 [95% CI, 0.86-0.98]) vs 448 (72.1%) in C1 group (IRR = 1.25 [95% CI, 1.14-1.37]), and 14,703 (58.6%) in source population. I group participants had decreased overall mortality rate compared to source population (IRR = 0.93, [95% CI, 0.86-0.98]) vs CI (IRR = 1.25, [95% CI 1.14-1.37]). PCa incidence in screening arm represents an overdiagnosis rate of 16.5–32.3%.</p> <p><i>PCa mortality</i> in I group was 59 (3.3%) (IRR 95% CI = 0.97 [0.71-1.23]) vs 27 (4.4%) (IRR = 1.24 [0.86-1.63] in C1 group and 857 (3.4%) in source population.</p> <p>- Sensitivity/Specificity: NR</p>	
<p>'US clinical trial'</p> <p><u>Catalona et al 2017</u></p>	<p>Multicentre CT US</p> <p>≥ 50 yrs</p> <p>PSA and DRE</p> <p>Biosy if PSA > 4/g/L and/or suspicious DRE</p>	<p>N = 6630</p> <p>I = 6630</p> <p>S = 6630</p> <p>Comparison groups based on screen method -PSA ± DRE</p> <p>1991–1992</p> <p>20 y FU</p>	<p>Comparison of efficacy of PSA and DRE to detect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PCa • Localised disease 	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: All participants underwent PSA and DRE. 15% had PSA >4 µg/l and 1167 had a biopsy.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <p>- Incidence: Of 160 patients who underwent radical prostatectomy and pathological staging 114 (71%) had organ confined cancer: PSA detected 85 (75%) of this localised disease vs DRE detected 64 (56%), p = 0.003.</p> <p>- Detection rate: PCa detection rate was 3.2% for DRE, 4.6% for PSA and 5.8% for the methods combined. PSA detected 216/ 264</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p>

				<p>cancers (82%,) vs DRE 146/ 264 (55%) , p = 0.001. PPV was 32% for PSA and 21% for DRE .</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage: 261/264 men had organ localised cancer and the remaining 3 (1%) had advanced disease. - Cancer-specific & all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
--	--	--	--	--	--

	<p><i>Uptake:</i> Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial <i>Compliance:</i> Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening N=Total number in trial; I=in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S=No. screened</p>
C [group]	Control/non-screened group
CAP	Cluster Randomised Trial of PSA Testing for Prostate Cancer
DRE	Digital rectal examination
ERSPC	European Randomized Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer
FinRSPC	Finnish Randomized Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer
FPR	False-positive rate
FU	Follow up
HR	Hazard ratio
HRQOL	Health-related quality of life
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IRR	Incidence rate ratio
MLT	Mean lead time [the average time by which diagnosis is advanced by screening relative to the date of diagnosis without screening]
NND	Number needed to invite to diagnose to prevent one prostate cancer death
NNI	Number needed to invite to screening to prevent one prostate cancer death
NPV	Negative predictive value
NR	Not reported
PCa	Prostate cancer

PLCO	Prostate, Lung, Colorectal & Ovarian Cancer Screening trial
PPV	Positive predictive value
PSA	Prostate-specific antigen
QALY	Quality-adjusted life-years
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
RR	Rate ratio
TRUS	Transrectal ultrasound

2.2 Bottom line results

Based on data from the 84 controlled trials included in the rapid review (many of which were randomised controlled trials) the evidence on efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness may be summarised as follows.

Gastric cancer:

Two trials were identified looking at endoscopic screening for gastric cancer (Zeng et al. 2020; Xiao et al. 2020). Both found that detection rates for gastric cancers were low (0.04% and 0.4%) but precursor lesions were also detected. Compliance rates were approximately 45%. No trial-based mortality or cost-effectiveness data were identified.

Screening via gastric juice MicroRNAs biomarkers is being explored (Virgilio et al. 2018) but has not yet been assessed in controlled trials so was outside the scope of the review.

Limited data from two trials, not identified within this rapid review but included in an identified systematic review (Haddad et al. 2020), suggest a 79-80% sensitivity and specificity for cancer detection by breath analysis.

The eradication of *Helicobacter pylori* as an alternative 'screen and treat' strategy for prevention of gastric cancer was outside the scope of this review of cancer screening methods but the authors are aware of ongoing trials (see discussion).

Lung cancer:

Data from 13 published trials found higher lung cancer incidence as well as early-stage disease in the screening arm, compared to control. A review pooling data from 9 randomised controlled trials (RCTs) found that the overall lung cancer incidence was higher in the low-dose CT scan (LDCT) screening group compared to the control group (RR 1.26; 95%CI 1.10-1.45) (Hunger et al. 2021).

Reduced lung cancer mortality but not overall mortality was observed in the screening arm, compared to control with mild gender variation: 29% reduction in women and 13% reduction in men. A meta-analysis pooling data from 8 RCTs calculated a relative risk of 0.88 (95%CI 0.79-0.97), suggesting a 12% reduction of lung cancer mortality in the screening versus control arm (Hunger et al, 2021).

The harms due to false-positive screening results may be minimal with some invasive investigations for benign disease but low complication rates (Balata et al. 2021; Hunger et al. 2020).

There are short-term psychosocial harms observed, due to involvement or suspicious results of screening, but these may resolve in the long run (Field et al. 2016; Hunger et al. 2020; Jonas et al. 2021; Pinsky 2014).

Four trials provided data on healthcare costs and estimates vary widely. Two trial-data based studies estimated costs per quality adjusted life year as £8,466 (95%CI £5516 to £12634) (Field et al. 2016) and \$81,000 (95%CI \$52,000 to \$186,000) (Black et al. 2014).

Oesophageal cancer:

Four controlled trials based in China, found that endoscopic screening can improve the detection rate of oesophageal cancer, compared to the control group. Based on three study findings (He et al. 2019; Xiao et al. 2020; Zeng et al. 2020), the detection rate of high-grade lesions is in the range 0.7–0.3%. No data on mortality were identified.

Compliance rates were less than 50% across the four trials (Chen-Tao Guan 2018; He et al. 2019; Xiao et al. 2020; Zeng et al. 2020)

A single trial estimated the healthcare costs to detect one cancer/one early-stage cancer at \$26,347 and \$37,687 respectively (Li et al. 2019).

A single trial of biomarker-based screening in higher risk individuals in the United Kingdom has shown a promising effect on early diagnosis of Barrett’s Oesophagus and subsequent cancer development (Fitzgerald et al., 2020a; Fitzgerald et al., 2020b; Swart et al., 2021).

Ovarian cancer:

No improvement of cancer mortality is observed in the screening arm compared to the control arm of trials overall. One study reported an improved survival of patients diagnosed with ovarian cancer in the screening arm compared to the control arm of the PLCO trial (RR 0.66; 95% CI 0.47-0.93) (Lai et al., 2016). However, no improvement in terms of ovarian cancer or all-cause mortality was observed across all RCTs examined, regardless of the screening protocols (Henderson et al., 2018). The false positive rate ranges from psychosocial harms are minor for screening *per se*, unless high-level repeat screenings are required (Andersen et al. 2007; Barrett et al. 2014; Fallowfield et al. 2017).

A single trial provided data on healthcare costs with an estimate of £46,922 per QALY (Menon et al. 2017).

Prostate cancer:

Screening via low threshold prostate specific antigen (PSA) results in a small reduction in prostate cancer/all-cause mortality. A meta-analysis of five RCTs estimated an incidence rate ratio of 0.96 (95% CI 0.85–1.08) at 10 years (Ilic et al. 2018). This equates to one prostate cancer death fewer per 1000 men screened over 10 years.

Any mortality benefit tends to be balanced against overdiagnosis and overtreatment of low-risk disease. One study estimated that for every prostate cancer death saved by screening 1000 men over 10 years, approximately 1, 3, and 25 more men would experience biopsy- and treatment-related sepsis, urinary incontinence, and erectile dysfunction, respectively (Ilic et al. 2018).

Longer follow-up is required to fully evaluate real-world costs. Two trial-based studies modelled costs of €54,918 (Karlsson et al. 2021) and \$73,000 (Heijnsdijk et al. 2021) per QALY gained.

One trial suggests that using MRI scanning to indicate biopsy may reduce the risk of overdiagnosis in men with abnormal PSA (Nordström et al. 2021) and the authors are aware that trials are ongoing to look at risk adapted screening with MRI.⁴

3. Discussion

3.1 Summary

This rapid review provides evidence for the efficacy of a number of screening regimens, based on the findings of controlled trials (Section 2.2).

Although not within the remit of this review, since no controlled trial evidence was identified, we are aware that a number of related strategies are being considered within the research community. Firstly, the eradication of *Helicobacter pylori* as an alternative ‘screen and treat’ strategy for prevention of gastric cancer. This is currently the subject of at least two randomised controlled trials (see Annex A). Secondly, the use of risk stratification algorithms as a way of refining prostate cancer PSA screening to reduce potential harms. These are both discussed in the workshop report (available on SAPEA website).

It is of interest to note the recommendations of guidance documents published this year on lung and prostate cancer screening:

The US Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommendation statement for 2021 states that *“The USPSTF recommends annual screening for lung cancer with LDCT in adults aged 50 to 80 years who have a 20 pack-year smoking history and currently smoke or have quit within the past 15 years. Screening should be discontinued once a person has not smoked for 15 years”*.⁵

Authors of this review are aware of a number of trials in Europe, the USA, UK, China and Iraq are ongoing to explore a more personalised approach to lung cancer screening⁶.

The European Association of Urology (EAU) position and recommendations for 2021 states that *“The EAU has developed a risk-adapted early prostate cancer detection strategy for well-informed men*

⁴ These include: Tampere et al (2022) <https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03423303>; UROONCO [web page 2022] <https://prostate.uroonco.uroweb.org/video/barentsz-trial-bi-parametric-mri-versus-multi-parametric-mri-2/>

⁵ Force, U.P.S.T., *Screening for Lung Cancer. US Preventive Services Task Force Recommendation Statement*. JAMA, 2021. **325**: p. 962-970 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.1117>

⁶ These include: Crosbie et al (2020) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-037075>; Hannover et al. (2022) June <https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT04913155>; National Jewish Health (2020) <https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT01700257>; Oncology Teaching Hospital (2021) <https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT04366661>; Changzheng (2021) <https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT03988322>; Arnold et al (2016) <https://ClinicalTrials.gov/show/NCT00596310>; van der Aalst et al (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.congress-2020.4171>

*based on PSA testing, risk calculators, and multiparametric magnetic resonance imaging, which can differentiate significant from insignificant prostate cancer. This approach largely avoids the overdiagnosis/overtreatment of men unlikely to experience disease-related symptoms during their lifetime and facilitates an early diagnosis of men with significant cancer to receive active treatment”.*⁷

A key issue in relation to the overall reach and impact of screening programmes in the general population is the overall measure of those willing to participate based on the screening offer. Within this rapid review, data giving the reported uptake (the % of the invited population agreeing to participate in the trial) and compliance rates (the % of the trial population screened and/or adherence to multiple screening rounds) are provided within the Evidence Tables (Section 2.1). Information on compliance only may over-estimate the true proportion likely to take up the screening offer in a real-life situation. This appears to be particularly true for lung cancer screening where, in the UKLS and Nelson lung cancer trials, only around 30% of potentially eligible subjects responded to the initial approach from the trial organisers and only around half of those volunteers found to be eligible for the trial agreed to be recruited⁸. Issues relating to screening uptake are discussed in detail in the workshop report (available on the SAPEA website).

3.2 Strengths and limitations of this Rapid Review

3.2.1 Strengths

This review summarises a valuable sub-set of the evidence base. It emphasises the findings from recent randomised and other controlled clinical trials, providing the evidence with the least potential for bias. Despite the very short time-period available for the review, a large number of trial reports have been included.

3.2.2 Limitations

In order to complete the review in a timely fashion a pragmatic and precise search strategy was employed. It is possible that further controlled trials would have been identified should there have been time for a detailed and sensitive systematic search. It is acknowledged that other types of non-trial evidence are relevant to the topic, notably ‘real life’ screening populations and modelling studies derived from trials and other screening cohorts.

The timeline also precluded any statistical or meta-analysis of findings unless these were available from published systematic reviews. Barriers and facilitators to screening uptake relating to socio-economic factors were not explored. No formal critical appraisal was carried out although information is provided on whether the trial included a power calculation. Data extraction and summary were undertaken by different reviewers and, although reviewed by another author, these have not been independently checked for accuracy and consistency.

⁷ Van Poppel, H., et al., *Prostate-specific Antigen Testing as Part of a Risk-Adapted Early Detection Strategy for Prostate Cancer: European Association of Urology Position and Recommendations for 2021*. *European Urology*, 2021. **15**: p. 15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2021.07.024>

⁸ Baldwin DR et al. Participation in lung cancer screening. *Translational Lung Cancer Research* 2021; 10(2): 1091-1098 <http://dx.doi.org/10.21037/tlcr-20-917>

4. References

1. Andersen, M.R., et al., *Changes in cancer worry associated with participation in ovarian cancer screening*. *Psycho-Oncology*, 2007. **16**(9): p. 814-20 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/pon.1151>
2. Andriole, G.L., et al., *Prostate cancer screening in the randomized Prostate, Lung, Colorectal, and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial: mortality results after 13 years of follow-up*. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 2012. **104**(2): p. 125-32 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djr500>
3. Arnsrud Godtman, R., et al., *Opportunistic testing versus organized prostate-specific antigen screening: outcome after 18 years in the Göteborg randomized population-based prostate cancer screening trial*. *European urology*, 2015. **68**(3): p. 354-360 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2014.12.006>
4. Balata, H., et al., *MA05.06 Lung Cancer Screening - Cumulative Results from Five UK-Based Programmes*. *Journal of Thoracic Oncology*, 2021. **16** (3 Supplement): p. S149 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jtho.2021.01.169>
5. Barrett, J., et al., *Psychological morbidity associated with ovarian cancer screening: results from more than 23,000 women in the randomised trial of ovarian cancer screening (UKCTOCS)*. *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 2014. **121**(9): p. 1071-9 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1471-0528.12870>
6. Becker, N., et al., *Lung cancer mortality reduction by LDCT screening-Results from the randomized German LUSI trial*. *International journal of cancer*, 2020. **146**(6): p. 1503-1513 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijc.32486>
7. Black, W.C., et al., *Cost-Effectiveness of CT Screening in the National Lung Screening Trial*. *New England journal of medicine*, 2014. **371**: p. 1793-1802 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1312547>
8. Booth, N.et al., *Costs of screening for prostate cancer: evidence from the Finnish Randomised Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer after 20-year follow-up using register data*. *European journal of cancer*, 2018. **93**(pp 108-118) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2018.01.111>
9. Buys, S.S., et al., *Effect of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal, and Ovarian (PLCO) cancer randomized screening trial*. *Journal of clinical oncology*, 2011. **29**(15) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2011.766>
10. Carlsson, S., et al., *At what age should a PSA-based screening program start? 20-year results from the Göteborg randomized population-based prostate cancer screening study*. *European urology, supplements*, 2017. **16**(3): p. e406-e408 DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1569-9056\(17\)30300-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1569-9056(17)30300-7)
11. Carlsson, S., et al., *Screening for Prostate Cancer Starting at Age 50-54 Years. A Population-based Cohort Study*. *European urology*, 2017. **71**(1): p. 46-52 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2016.03.026>
12. Catalona, W.J., et al., *Comparison of Digital Rectal Examination and Serum Prostate Specific Antigen in the Early Detection of Prostate Cancer: results of a Multicenter Clinical Trial of 6,630 Men*. *Journal of urology*, 2017. **197**(2 Supplement): p. S200-S207 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.juro.2016.10.073>
13. de Koning, H.J., et al., *The efficacy of PSA screening: impact of key*

- components in the ERSPC and PLCO trial. *Cancer*, 2018. **124**(6): p. 1197-1206 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/cncr.31178>
14. de Koning, H.J., et al., *Reduced Lung-Cancer Mortality with Volume CT Screening in a Randomized Trial*. *New England journal of medicine*, 2020. **382**(6): p. 503-513 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1911793>
 15. Doroudi, M., B.S. Kramer, and P.F. Pinsky, *The bimanual ovarian palpation examination in the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian cancer screening trial: performance and complications*. *Journal of medical screening*, 2017. **24**(4): p. 220-222 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0969141316680381>
 16. Eklund, M., et al., *MRI-targeted or standard biopsy in prostate cancer screening*. *New England journal of medicine*, 2021. **385**: p. 908-920 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2100852>
 17. Fallowfield, L., et al., *The effect of ovarian cancer screening on sexual activity and functioning: results from the UK collaborative trial of ovarian cancer screening RCT*. *British journal of cancer*, 2017. **116**(8): p. 1111-1117 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/bjc.2017.72>
 18. Field, J.K., et al., *The UK Lung Cancer Screening Trial: a pilot randomised controlled trial of low-dose computed tomography screening for the early detection of lung cancer*. 2016, NIHR Health Technology Assessment programme: England. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3310/hta20400>
 19. Fitzgerald, R.C., et al., *Cytosponge-trefoil factor 3 versus usual care to identify Barrett's oesophagus in a primary care setting: a multicentre, pragmatic, randomised controlled trial*. *Lancet*, 2020a. **396**(10247): p. 333-344 DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)31099-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)31099-0)
 20. Fitzgerald, R.C., et al., *634 results from the Barrett's Oesophagus Trial 3 (BEST3): A randomised controlled trial comparing the Cytosponge™-TFF3 Test with usual care to identify oesophageal precancer in primary care patients with chronic gastroesophageal reflux*. *Gastroenterology*, 2020b. **158**(6): p. S-136- DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0016-5085\(20\)31020-9](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0016-5085(20)31020-9)
 21. Franlund, M., et al., *Prostate cancer risk assessment in men with an initial P.S.A. below 3 ng/mL: results from the Goteborg randomized population-based prostate cancer screening trial*. *Scandinavian journal of urology*, 2018. **(no pagination)** DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/21681805.2018.1508166>
 22. Gentry-Maharaj, A., et al., *Overdiagnosis of borderline ovarian cancer in ovarian cancer screening: the UK collaborative trial of ovarian cancer screening (UKCTOCS) experience*. *International journal of gynecological cancer. (var.pagings)*, 2015. **25**(9 SUPPL. 1): p. 22-23 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/01.IGC.0000473498.85773.6e>
 23. Gonzalez-Maldonado, S., et al., *Overdiagnosis in lung cancer screening: estimates from the German Lung Cancer Screening Intervention Trial [Journal: Article in Press]*. *International Journal of Cancer*, 2020 DOI: <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijc.33295>
 24. Haddad, G., et al., *Using breath analysis as a screening tool to detect gastric cancer: A systematic review*. *Journal of Breath Research*, 2020. **26**: p. 26 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1752-7163/abc4d5>
 25. Heijnsdijk, E.A.M., et al., *Cost-effectiveness of Prostate Cancer*

- Screening: A Simulation Study Based on ERSPC Data* JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute, 2015. **107**(1) DOI: [https://doi-org.abc.cardiff.ac.uk/10.1093/jnci/dju366](https://doi.org.abc.cardiff.ac.uk/10.1093/jnci/dju366)
26. Hugosson, J., et al., *Eighteen-year follow-up of the Goteborg Randomized Population-based Prostate Cancer Screening Trial: effect of sociodemographic variables on participation, prostate cancer incidence and mortality*. Scandinavian journal of urology, 2017: p. 1-11 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/21681805.2017.1411392>
27. Hugosson, J., et al., *A 16-yr Follow-up of the European Randomized study of Screening for Prostate Cancer*. European urology, 2019. **76**(1): p. 43-51 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2019.02.009>
28. Hunger, T., et al., *Lung Cancer Screening with Low-Dose CT in Smokers: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis*. Diagnostics, 2021. **11**(6): p. 05 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics11061040>
29. Ilic, D., et al., *Prostate cancer screening with prostate-specific antigen (PSA) test: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. BMJ, 2018. **362**: p. k3519 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k3519>
30. Infante, M., et al., *Lung cancer screening with low-dose spiral computed tomography: evidence from a pooled analysis of two Italian randomized trials*. European journal of cancer prevention, 2017. **26**(4): p. 324-329 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/CEJ.000000000000264>
31. Jensen, D.M., et al., *Direct and indirect healthcare costs of lung cancer CT screening in Denmark: a registry study*. BMJ Open, 2020. **10**(1) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-031768>
32. Jonas, D.E., et al., *Screening for Lung Cancer With Low-Dose Computed Tomography: Updated Evidence Report and Systematic Review for the US Preventive Services Task Force*. JAMA, 2021. **325**(10): p. 971-987 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.0377>
33. Kalsi, J., et al., *Performance characteristics of the ultrasound strategy during incidence screening in the UK collaborative trial of ovarian cancer screening (UKCTOCS)*. Cancers, 2021. **13**(4): p. 1-13 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/cancers13040858>
34. Karlsson, A., et al, *The cost-effectiveness of prostate cancer screening using the Stockholm3 test*. PloS one, 2021. **16**(2): p. e0246674- DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0246674>
35. Kilpelainen, T.P., et al., *Prostate cancer mortality in the Finnish randomized screening trial*. Journal of the National Cancer Institute, 2013. **105**(10): p. 719-25 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djt038>
36. Kobayashi, H., et al., *A randomized study of screening for ovarian cancer: a multicenter study in Japan*. Obstetrical & gynecological survey, 2008. **63**(10): p. 635-636 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/01.ogx.00000333238.05419.56>
37. Lai, T., et al., *Ovarian cancer screening in menopausal females with a family history of breast or ovarian cancer*. Journal of gynecologic oncology, 2016. **27**(4): p. e41 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3802/jgo.2016.27.e41>
38. Lopci, E., et al., *Cost-effectiveness of second-line diagnostic investigations in patients included in the DANTE trial: a randomized controlled trial of lung cancer screening with low-dose computed tomography*. Nuclear

- medicine communications, 2019. **40**(5): p. 508-516 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/MNM.0000000000000993>
39. Lundgren, P.O., et al., *Long-Term Outcome of a Single Intervention Population Based Prostate Cancer Screening Study*. Journal of urology, 2018. **200**(1): p. 82-88 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.juro.2018.01.080>
40. Martin, R.M., et al., *Effect of a Low-Intensity PSA-Based Screening Intervention on Prostate Cancer Mortality: the CAP Randomized Clinical Trial*. JAMA, 2018. **319**(9): p. 883-895 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2018.0154>
41. Mascalchi, M., et al., *Risk-benefit analysis of X-ray exposure associated with lung cancer screening in the Italung-CT trial*. AJR. American Journal of Roentgenology, 2006. **187**(2): p. 421-9 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2214/AJR.05.0088>
42. Menon, U., et al., *Ovarian cancer population screening and mortality after long-term follow-up in the UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS): a randomised controlled trial*. Lancet (london, england), 2021. **397**(10290): p. 2182-2193 DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)00731-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00731-5)
43. Menon, U., et al., *The cost-effectiveness of screening for ovarian cancer: results from the UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS)*. British journal of cancer, 2017. **117**(5): p. 619-627 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/bjc.2017.222>
44. Moss, S.A., A. Berchuck, and M.L. Neely, *Estimating cost-effectiveness of a multimodal ovarian cancer screening program in the United States: secondary analysis of the UK collaborative trial of ovarian cancer screening (UKCTOCS)*. JAMA oncology, 2018. **4**(2): p. 190-195 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamaoncol.2017.4211>
45. National Lung Screening Trial Research, T., et al., *Reduced lung-cancer mortality with low-dose computed tomographic screening*. New England Journal of Medicine, 2011. **365**(5): p. 395-409 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1102873>
46. National Lung Screening Trial Research, T., et al., *Results of initial low-dose computed tomographic screening for lung cancer*. New England Journal of Medicine, 2013. **368**(21): p. 1980-91 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1209120>
47. Nordström, T., et al., *Prostate cancer screening using a combination of risk-prediction, MRI, and targeted prostate biopsies (STHLM3-MRI): a prospective, population-based, randomised, open-label, non-inferiority trial* The Lancet Oncology, 2021. **22**(9): p. 1240-1249 DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(21\)00348-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(21)00348-X)
48. Osses, D.F., et al., *Results of Prostate Cancer Screening in a Unique Cohort at 19 yr of Follow-up*. European urology, 2018. **(no pagination)** DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2018.10.053>
49. Paci, E., et al., *Prognostic selection and long-term survival analysis to assess overdiagnosis risk in lung cancer screening randomized trials*. Journal of medical screening, 2020: p. 969141320923030 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0969141320923030>
50. Paci, E., et al., *Mortality, survival and incidence rates in the ITALUNG randomised lung cancer screening trial*. Thorax, 2017. **72**(9): p. 825-831 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/thoraxjnl-2016-209825>

51. Pakarainen T., et al., *The number of screening cycles needed to reduce prostate cancer mortality in the Finnish section of the European Randomized Study of Prostate Cancer (ERSPC)*. *Clinical cancer research*, 2019. **25**(2): p. 839-843 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-18-1807>
52. Pastorino, U., et al., *Prolonged lung cancer screening reduced 10-year mortality in the MILD trial: new confirmation of lung cancer screening efficacy*. *Annals of oncology*, 2019. **30**(7): p. 1162-1169 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mdz117>
53. Pastorino, U., et al., *Ten-year results of the Multicentric Italian Lung Detection trial demonstrate the safety and efficacy of biennial lung cancer screening*. *European journal of cancer*, 2019. **118**: p. 142-148 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2019.06.009>
54. Pierre-Victor, D., et al., *Prostate Cancer Incidence and Mortality Following a Negative Biopsy in a Population Undergoing PSA Screening*. *Urology.*, 2021 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.urology.2021.05.060>
55. Pinsky, P.F., *Assessing the benefits and harms of low-dose computed tomography screening for lung cancer*. *Lung cancer management*, 2014. **3**(6): p. 491-498 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2217/LMT.14.41>
56. Pinsky, P.F., C.R. Bellinger, and D.P. Miller, *False-positive screens and lung cancer risk in the National Lung Screening Trial: implications for shared decision-making*. *Journal of medical screening*, 2018. **25**(2): p. 110-112 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0969141317727771>
57. Pinsky, P.F., et al., *Performance of Lung-RADS in the National Lung Screening Trial: a retrospective assessment*. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 2015. **162**(7): p. 485-91 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7326/M14-2086>
58. Pinsky, P.F., et al., *Extended follow-up for prostate cancer incidence and mortality among participants in the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian randomized cancer screening trial*. *BJU international*, 2019. **123**(5): p. 854-860 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/bju.14580>
59. Pinsky, P.F., et al., *Overall mortality in men and women in the randomized Prostate, Lung, Colorectal, and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial*. *Journal of medical screening*, 2019. **26**(3): p. 127-134 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0969141319839097>
60. Pinsky, P.F., et al., *Extended mortality results for prostate cancer screening in the PLCO trial with median follow-up of 15 years*. *Cancer*, 2017. **123**(4): p. 592-599 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/cncr.30474>
61. Prorok, P.C., et al., *Overall and Multiphasic Findings of the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian (PLCO) Randomized Cancer Screening Trial*. *Reviews on recent clinical trials*, 2018. **13**(4): p. 257-273 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2174/1574887113666180409153059>
62. Qian, F., et al., *Community-based lung cancer screening of high-risk population with low-dose computed tomography in China*. *Annals of oncology*, 2017. **28**: p. v502- DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mdx383.001>
63. Rampinelli, C., et al., *Exposure to low dose computed tomography for lung cancer screening and risk of cancer: secondary analysis of trial data and risk-benefit analysis*. *BMJ (online)*, 2017. **356**(no pagination) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i347>
64. Saarimäki, L., et al., *Impact of Prostatic-specific Antigen Threshold and Screening Interval in Prostate Cancer Screening Outcomes:*

- comparing the Swedish and Finnish European Randomised Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer Centres. *European urology focus*, 2019. **5**(2): p. 186-191 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.euf.2017.07.007>
65. Sandblom, G., et al., *Randomised prostate cancer screening trial: 20 year follow-up*. *BMJ: british medical journal (overseas & retired doctors edition)*, 2011. **342**(7803): p. 908-908 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d1539>
66. Schroder, F.H., et al., *Screening for prostate cancer decreases the risk of developing metastatic disease: findings from the European Randomized Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer (ERSPC)*. *European Urology*, 2012. **62**(5): p. 745-52 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eururo.2012.05.068>
67. Schroder, F.H., et al., *Screening and prostate cancer mortality: results of the European Randomised Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer (ERSPC) at 13 years of follow-up*. *Lancet*, 2014. **384**(9959): p. 2027-35 DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(14\)60525-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(14)60525-0)
68. Spiro, S.G., et al., *Sequential screening for lung cancer in a high-risk group: randomised controlled trial: lungSEARCH: a randomised controlled trial of Surveillance using sputum and imaging for the EARly detection of lung Cancer in a High-risk group*. *The european respiratory journal*, 2019. **54**(4) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1183/13993003.00581-2019>
69. Sverzellati, N., et al., *Low-dose computed tomography for lung cancer screening: comparison of performance between annual and biennial screen*. *European radiology*, 2016. **26**(11): p. 3821-3829 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00330-016-4228-3>
70. Swart, N., et al., *Economic evaluation of Cytosponge R-trefoil factor 3 for Barrett esophagus: A cost-utility analysis of randomised controlled trial data*. *EClinicalMedicine*, 2021. **37**: p. 100969 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2021.100969>
71. Talala, K., et al., *Long-term health-related quality of life among men with prostate cancer in the Finnish randomized study of screening for prostate cancer*. *Cancer medicine*, 2020. **9**(15): p. 5643-5654 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/cam4.3181>
72. Tsodikov, A., et al., *Reconciling the effects of screening on prostate cancer mortality in the ERSPC and PLCO trials*. *Annals of internal medicine*, 2017. **167**(7): p. 449-455 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7326/M16-2586>
73. van Leeuwen, P.J., *Prostate cancer screening has no effect on prostate cancer specific mortality over 20 years of follow-up of Swedish men*. *Evidence based medicine*, 2012. **17**(1): p. 25-26 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/ebm-2011-100070>
74. van Leeuwen, P.J., et al., *Impacts of a population-based prostate cancer screening programme on excess total mortality rates in men with prostate cancer: a randomized controlled trial*. *Journal of medical screening*, 2013. **20**(1): p. 33-38 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0969141313476632>
75. Veronesi, G., et al., *Lung cancer screening with low-dose computed tomography: A non-invasive diagnostic protocol for baseline lung nodules*. *Lung Cancer*, 2008. **61**(3): p. 340-349 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lungcan.2008.01.001>
76. Virgilio, E., et al., *Gastric juice MicroRNAs as potential biomarkers for screening gastric cancer: A systematic review*. *Anticancer Research*, 2018. **38**(2): p. 613-616

- DOI:
<http://dx.doi.org/10.21873/anticancerres.12265>
77. Walter, J., et al., *Impact of Screening Interval Length on New Nodules Detected in Incidence Rounds of CT Lung Cancer Screening: the NELSON Trial*. *Journal of thoracic oncology*, 2018. **13**(10): p. S788- DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jtho.2018.08.1371>
78. Walter, S.D., et al., *Estimating the rate of overdiagnosis with prostate cancer screening: evidence from the Finnish component of the European Randomized Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer*. *Cancer Causes and Control.*, 2021 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10552-021-01480-8>
79. Wang, H., et al., *Lung cancer screening with low-dose CT in China: study design and baseline results from the first round screening arm*. *Journal of thoracic oncology*, 2017. **12**(1): p. S581-S582 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jtho.2016.11.734>
80. Wille, M.M., et al., *Results of the Randomized Danish Lung Cancer Screening Trial with Focus on High-Risk Profiling*. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*, 2016. **193**(5): p. 542-551 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201505-1040OC>
81. Xiao, H.F., et al., *Community-Based Upper Gastrointestinal Cancer Screening in a Randomized Controlled Trial: baseline Results in a Non-high-incidence Area*. *Cancer prevention research (Philadelphia, Pa.)*, 2020. **13**(3): p. 317-328 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1940-6207.CAPR-19-0422>
82. Yang, W., et al., *Community-based lung cancer screening with low-dose CT in China: results of the baseline screening*. *Lung cancer (amsterdam, netherlands)*, 2018. **117**: p. 20-26 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lungcan.2018.01.003>
83. Yousaf-Khan, U., et al., *Final screening round of the NELSON lung cancer screening trial: the effect of a 2.5-year screening interval*. *Thorax*, 2017. **72**(1): p. 48-56 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/thoraxjnl-2016-208655>
84. Zeng, H., et al., *Initial results from a multi-center population-based cluster randomized trial of esophageal and gastric cancer screening in China*. *BMC gastroenterology*, 2020. **20**(1): p. 398 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12876-020-01517-3>

5. Rapid review method

5.1 Eligibility criteria

- Randomised controlled trial (RCT) or controlled clinical trial⁹
- Published during or after 2007
- Screening for first diagnosis of lung, gastric, prostate, ovarian or (o)esophageal cancers
- Inclusion of data on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost-effectiveness
- All locations, all languages

5.2 Literature search strategy

Searches were carried out for publications from 2016 onwards using title and Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) searches of the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CCTR). This includes trial data from Medline, Embase and the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP). Supplementary searching of Medline, Embase and the ICTRP was carried out for publications in 2021 that may not yet have been included in the CCTR.

To ensure coverage of trial reports back to 2007, Cochrane Reviews, Health Technology Assessment and the US Preventive Services Taskforce (USPSTF) was searched for systematic reviews on the topics. These were then examined for relevant trial reports.

Text word terms: [lung OR pulmonary OR stomach OR gastric OR prostat* OR ovar* OR esophag* OR oesophag*] *in Record Title* AND [cancer* OR neoplasm*] *in Record Title* AND screen* *in Record Title*

MeSH terms: (exp¹⁰ lung neoplasms OR stomach neoplasms OR exp prostatic neoplasms OR exp ovarian neoplasms OR exp esophageal neoplasms) AND (early detection of cancer)

Additional search methods: The screened results were provided to the co-chairs of the Expert Workshop who were asked to liaise with workshop attendees and the workshop on the topic was attended by one of the review authors to note any additional studies meeting the inclusion criteria.

5.3 Resources list

Clinical trials.gov
Cochrane Library [Cochrane Reviews/Cochrane Central Register of Controlled trials]
Health Technology Assessment
Embase
International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)
Medline
US Preventive Services Taskforce (USPSTF)

⁹ Quasi-randomised and other controlled trials where randomisation is not explicit, but cannot be ruled out

¹⁰ The exp (explode) function directs the selection of all papers tagged with this heading and any more specific sub-headings.

5.4 Study selection process

Results from the literature searches were imported into EndNote 20, where duplicates were removed. Titles and abstracts were screened for inclusion followed by full text screening. Both screening stages were undertaken by a team of reviewers according to the eligibility criteria in Section 5.1. Identified systematic reviews were examined for trials dating back to 2007.

5.5 Study selection flow chart

5.6 Data extraction

Data from main trial report(s) on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost effectiveness were extracted into a summary table for each cancer by a single reviewer with checking by a second reviewer (Section 2.1).

5.7 Quality appraisal

Each included study was identified as RCT or controlled clinical trial (CCT) according to the study design as provided in the database(s) within the evidence table (Section 2.1) along with a note as to whether a power calculation was included as part of the trial. No other formal critical appraisal was carried out.

5.8 Synthesis

The findings are summarised in a narrative report, drawing from the summary tables with brief findings based on the consensus from the included studies.

6. Additional information

6.1 Conflicts of interest

None

6.2 Acknowledgements

This template is based, with permission, on the rapid review template used within the Palliative Care Evidence Review Service ([PaCERS](#)) and the [Welsh Covid 19 Evidence Centre](#).

7. About the review team

The [Specialist Unit for Review Evidence \(SURE\)](#) is a team of experienced systematic reviewers and information specialists at Cardiff University who conduct all forms of systematic and other evidence reviews, and teach evidence review methods. The team work across all topic areas and also specialise in health and social care. Staff have carried out a number of reviews for SAPEA, working closely with Academia Europaea and experienced reviewers within the University's Library Service. Reviews are carried out in close collaboration with subject specialists for each review topic. For these rapid reviews the subject specialists are Dr Hui-Ling Ou (Cambridge University) and Dr Nicholas Courtier (Cardiff University).

8. Brief reference lists on topics related to the rapid review

As agreed within the protocol for Rapid Review 1, some references identified during searching for the review were provided to workshop attendees where they related to additional questions of potential interest to the working group.

A specific search was not undertaken for each of these questions.

An EndNote file with full details of each publication is available from the authors of this rapid review.

A. Ongoing/unpublished clinical trials
B. Trials exploring smoking cessation as part of lung cancer screening programmes
C. Trials exploring decision making tools to assist patients with screening decisions
D. Cost-effectiveness or harm-benefit studies that are not explicitly linked to an included trial
E. Evidence-based screening guidelines published since 2016
F. Systematic reviews published since 2016 on implementation issues such as barriers to screening uptake

SAPEA is part of the European Commission's Scientific Advice Mechanism, which provides independent, interdisciplinary, and evidence-based scientific advice on policy issues to the European Commission.

SAPEA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 737432.

www.sapea.info
@SAPEAnews

Cancer screening in Europe

Rapid review 2

To what extent do more risk-stratified approaches to screening programmes for breast, cervical and colorectal cancers impact on uptake, efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness?

To download the latest version of this document, together with the full Evidence Review Report that it informed, please visit:

www.sapea.info/cancerscreening

SAPEA

Science Advice for Policy by European Academies

The text of this work is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution licence which permits unrestricted use, provided the original author and source are credited. The licence is available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>. Images reproduced from other publications are not covered by this licence and remain the property of their respective owners, whose licence terms may be different. Every effort has been made to secure permission for reproduction of copyright material. The usage of images reproduced from other publications has not been reviewed by the copyright owners prior to release, and therefore those owners are not responsible for any errors, omissions or inaccuracies, or for any consequences arising from the use or misuse of this document.

This document has been produced by the SAPEA consortium. The information, facts and opinions set out in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The SAPEA Consortium is not responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained in this report by anyone, including the European Union institutions and bodies or any person acting on their behalf.

- DOI: -forthcoming
- Downloadable from <https://www.sapea.info/cancer-screening/>

Version history

Version	Date	Summary of changes
1.0	2 March 2022	First published version

Publisher

SAPEA
c/o acatech
Pariser Platz 4a
10117 Berlin, Germany

Contact

SAPEA Communications Office
Rue d'Egmont 13
1000 Brussels, Belgium
contact@sapea.info

Rapid Review 2

To what extent do more risk-stratified approaches to screening programmes for breast, cervical and colorectal cancers impact on uptake, efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness?

Rapid Review Details

Review conducted by:

A team led by the Specialist Unit for Review Evidence (SURE) for SAPEA (Science Advice for Policy by European Academies)

Review Team:

- Dr Hui-Ling Ou, Research Associate, Cambridge Centre Lung Cancer Early Detection Group, Cambridge University UK
- Dr Nicholas Courtier, Senior Lecturer Radiography, School of Healthcare Sciences, Cardiff University UK
- Dr Alison Weightman, Director Specialist Unit for Review Evidence, Cardiff University UK
- Louise Edwards, Hub Manager, Academia Europaea, Cardiff University UK

Acknowledgements:

The advisory group for the review team, comprising the Chairs of the Expert Workshop, Professor Ole Petersen (Academia Europaea), members of SAPEA, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (Advisors) and the SAM Unit. Dr Sunil Dolwani (Cancer Theme Lead, School of Medicine, Cardiff University) and Professor Jacek Jassem (Head, Department of Oncology & Radiotherapy, Medical University of Gdańsk) for reviewing and commenting on the draft pre-publication.

Method:

This is one of three rapid reviews - a lighter form of a full systematic review that takes account of time constraints. The top-line results are included in the main SAPEA Evidence Review Report, with cross-referencing between the documents.

The review summarises a valuable subset of the evidence base, emphasising the findings from recent randomised and other controlled clinical trials, and modelling studies based on trial data. To meet deadlines, a pragmatic and precise search strategy was employed; it is possible that further controlled trials would have been identified if there had been time for a detailed and sensitive systematic search. The timeline also precluded any statistical or meta-analysis of findings unless these were available from published systematic reviews. No formal critical appraisal was carried out although information is provided on whether the trial included a power calculation. Data extraction and summary were undertaken by different reviewers and, although reviewed by another author, these have not been independently checked for accuracy and consistency.

Disclaimer: The authors of this work declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

To what extent do more risk-stratified approaches to screening programmes for breast, cervical and colorectal cancers impact on uptake, efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness?

TOPLINE SUMMARY

Who is this summary for?

To support the work of SAPEA in providing evidence to the European Commission's Group of Chief Scientific Advisers on cancer screening in Europe.

Background

This review is one of three rapid reviews conducted on the topic of cancer screening in Europe. It was produced specifically for the expert workshop convened to discuss how cancer screening programmes targeting breast, cervical and colorectal cancers can be improved throughout the EU. This final version has been revised to address feedback received on earlier drafts and supplements the workshop report (available on the SAPEA website).

Aim

To examine the published evidence base for the question: *'To what extent do more risk-stratified approaches to screening programmes for breast, cervical and colorectal cancers impact on uptake, efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness?'*

Rapid review method

A literature search was conducted in September 2021 for controlled trials published since 2007, supplemented with studies from published systematic reviews and modelling studies based on trial data. Trials were included if they examined screening for first diagnosis of breast, cervical or colorectal cancer and included data on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost-effectiveness in relation to targeting screening uptake and screening methods.

Key findings

Breast cancer [16 trials]:

- Modelling data suggest risk-stratified and adapted strategies can improve benefit-harm ratio with reasonable cost-effectiveness in the European setting
- Annual mammography ± ultrasound ± digital breast tomosynthesis ± MRI is likely to be feasible, acceptable and effective in higher risk 40–49 year-old European women. Supplemental MRI screening increases sensitivity for younger women with dense breasts
- Overdiagnosis is unlikely to be a significant problem where screening is targeted at younger European women

Cervical cancer [11 trials]:

- Screening with HPV self-sampling increases the screening uptake, especially for under-screened women, and is most cost-effective compared to standard cytology testing
- Screening intervals may be extended for women with negative HPV results and older age

- Increased sensitivity of HPV testing may reflect early detection of lesions rather than overdiagnosis

Colorectal cancer [13 trials]:

- The majority of the population prefers FIT to colonoscopy in terms of CRC screening uptake although the latter has a higher sensitivity and specificity in detecting advanced neoplasms
- The uptake and compliance with screening can be promoted via pro-active interventions
- Risk-stratification by age or family history remain the most used inclusion criteria

Strength of evidence

No formal critical appraisal was carried out within this rapid review but the included evidence is from randomised and other controlled clinical trials, with the least theoretical potential for bias.

Full report

Table of Contents

1.	Background.....	5
1.1	Purpose of this review	5
1.2	Research question	5
2.	Results	6
2.1	Summary of the evidence base.....	6
	Breast cancer	6
	Cervical cancer.....	8
	Colorectal cancer	9
2.1	Summary of the evidence base [table].....	12
2.2	Bottom line results	47
3.	Discussion.....	49
3.1	Summary.....	49
3.2	Strengths and limitations of this Rapid Review.....	49
3.2.1	Strengths	49
3.2.2	Limitations.....	49
4.	References: Breast cancer	50
5.	References: Cervical cancer.....	52
6.	References: Colorectal cancer	53
7.	Rapid review method.....	56
7.1	Eligibility criteria.....	56
7.2	Literature search strategy.....	56
7.3	Resources list	57
7.4	Study selection process	58
7.5	Study selection flow chart.....	58
7.6	Data extraction.....	59
7.7	Quality appraisal.....	59
7.8	Synthesis	59
8.	Additional information	59
8.1	Conflicts of interest	59
8.2	Acknowledgements	59
9.	About the review team	59

1. Background

This Rapid Review is one of three reviews conducted to support the work of Expert Groups convened to assist the European Commission Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM) in developing policy guidance in relation to cancer screening. As described in the Scoping Paper¹, this review supported the second of the Expert Group workshops being convened to discuss the question **“How can cancer screening programmes targeting breast, cervical and colorectal cancers, be improved throughout the EU?”**

An advisory group was formed to provide guidance to the review team, comprising the Chairs, Professor Ole Petersen (Academia Europaea), members of SAPEA, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors and the SAM Unit.

1.1 Purpose of this review

Following detailed discussions with the co-chairs, the question for the rapid review to inform the second workshop was:

“To what extent do more stratified approaches to screening programmes for breast, cervical and colorectal cancers impact on uptake, efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness?”

Post-review this was clarified to:

“To what extent do more risk-stratified approaches to screening programmes for breast, cervical and colorectal cancers impact on uptake, efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness?”

1.2 Research question

Rapid Review Question
Based on findings from controlled trials on efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness, and modelling studies based on those controlled trials, what is the current evidence related to the risk-stratification of screening programmes for breast, cervical and colorectal cancers?

As defined in ‘Cancer Screening in the EU’ SAPEA Evidence Review Report, **Risk-stratified screening** relates to the delivery of screening within an established screening programme, where the type of screening, the intensity or the modality can be varied according to the level of individual risk in order to achieve a more favourable balance of benefits and harms at the individual as well as population level.

It was agreed at review protocol stage that a broad approach to risk-stratification would be adopted to include targeting specific populations by risk factors (including age, gender, ethnicity/race, other socio-demographic differences), interval and interval by age comparisons, and stratified screening method comparisons (see Section 7.1).

¹ Scientific Advice Mechanism. European Commission’s Group of Chief Scientific Advisors. [Scoping Paper: Cancer Screening](#). 22 April 2021

2. Results

2.1 Summary of the evidence base

In all, 67 reports have been summarised. We provide a narrative overview of the identified evidence below. A summary of each included trial is provided in Section 2.2.

Breast cancer

16 trials (in 24 reports), two systematic reviews and seven simulation modelling papers were identified.

Modelling data included three systematic reviews of risk-based screening simulations (Canelo et al. 2018; Khan et al. 2021; Mühlberger et al. 2021) and one analysis of modelling techniques (Arnold 2017). Review data are neither based on, nor confirmed by controlled trials; a summary of harm-benefit balance has been included because of limitations in RCTs of complex stratified screening. Five European risk-adapted screening studies predict superior efficacy (BCa specific mortality, increased life expectancy, reduced overdiagnosis) and cost-effectiveness (increased QALYs and/or incremental cost-utility/cost-effectiveness) compared to conventional age-based/non-risk adapted screening (Mühlberger et al. 2021).

Modelling studies of risk-based screening (Canelo et al. 2018; Khan et al. 2021) from Europe, US and China indicate annual mammography in high-risk women and the age group 40-49 years was cost-effective compared to no screening or non-risk adapted screening, and compared with a longer screen interval – yielding higher mortality rate reduction and QALYs at expense of higher absolute cost and false positives. However, the modelling studies generated inconsistent results regarding the cost effectiveness of supplementary MRI use to minimise false positives and overdiagnosis in dense-breasted women.

Modelling of UK RCT data favoured annual over biennial or triennial screening when targeted at women aged 40 to 49 (Gunsoy et al. 2012). Overdiagnosis, based on invasive and in-situ disease, was predicted to be approximately 0.8% (range 0.5-2.9) due to ‘short cancer sojourn times’. Quality of modelling studies was difficult to establish, with heterogeneous methods, approaches to risk stratification and underlying assumptions.

RCT data was extracted from 16 trials; eight including European data. The primary rationales were to test screen method, invitation age or frequency. Four tested risk-adapted screening in a higher risk population e.g. supplemental screening for dense breast parenchyma and four tested risk-stratified screening in the general population (by an individualised risk model encompassing previous biopsies, family history, breast density and genetic markers.)

Cost-effectiveness

Trial data were limited. Modelling data (above) indicate that risk-stratified screening is likely to be reasonably cost-effective. Microsimulations of the Dense Tissue and Early Breast Neoplasm Screening (DENSE) trial data suggests that additional MRI at a four-year interval was most cost effective (€15,620 per QALY) for women with extremely dense breasts (Geuzinge et al. 2021).

Supplemental annual MRI screening may reduce cost-effectiveness in risk-stratified populations: for example, a Netherlands cohort study found annual mammography plus MRI to be expensive for women with an estimated cumulative lifetime breast cancer risk of 15–50% (Saadatmand et al. 2012). More recent preliminary US trial data indicated biennial, supplemental MRI and personalised risk-based screening could be delivered at lower cost versus annual screening; (14.1 v 22.1 million US\$ per 100,000 women) (Shieh 2019). Individualisation of a US intervention to increase screening compliance was more costly and less effective than a generic version (Lairson et al. 2011).

Compliance and uptake

Consistent evidence across stratification and screen methods showed uptake of risk-based screening was typically between 50 and 70%. Relative uptake of and compliance with ultrasound or MRI (Bakker et al. 2019; Berg et al. 2012; Constock et al. 2020; Huang et al. 2010; Veenhuizen et al. 2021) suggest that they are broadly acceptable breast screening modalities. When given a choice, individualised risk-based screening was preferred by over 80%, with no discernible elevation of anxiety levels (Naeim 2018). The compliance rate for 47–49 years group was only slightly lower than for 71–73 years (24% v 29%) with a significantly greater proportion of older women requesting screening after allocation to no screening (Moser et al. 2011). Almost 90% of women below 50 years with a false positive attended their next routine screening (Duffy et al B, 2020).

Mortality

RCT data is limited to the effect of targeting annual mammographic screening in women 40–49 years. A large UK trial demonstrated a relative reduction in breast cancer mortality of 25% at 10 years follow up, which was attenuated thereafter (Duffy et al. a 2020). An older Canadian trial found only a 1% (-12 to 12) relative risk reduction in BCa mortality at 22 years (Miller et al. 2014)² and a slight increase in risk of BCa-specific death for women 40–49 years (Narod et al. 2014). Results are methodologically controversial and unlikely to reflect developments in adjuvant therapies. However, a Swedish trial reported a 40% reduction in breast mortality after 25 years (Bjurstam et al. 2016). Modelling based on almost 50,000 screened, estimated a relative risk of BCa mortality of 0.83 for annual versus triennial mammography in UK (Van Ravesteyn et al. 2011).

Cancer incidence and detection efficacy

Target Screening population level data is largely from North America: A simulated target screening population of 100,000 US women predicted no significant difference in proportion of \geq stage IIB BCa for personalised risk-based screening (Shieh et al. 2019).

For younger women 40–49 years: Incidence was approximately 6–7x more in the 50–59 years group versus 40–49 years across 25 years follow up (Shieh 2019). BCa incidence in UK was 0.5% versus 1.1% in a 71–73 age group (Moser et al. 2011). Incidence was slightly higher in screened versus unscreened women aged 40–49 years in Canada (Miller et al. 2014) and equivalent after 23 years follow up in the UK (Duffy et al. b 2020). The addition of ultrasound demonstrated a 3–4 x increased detection rate versus mammography alone in Taiwanese women aged 40–49 years (Huang et al. 2010).

Dense breast tissue: The supplemental yield of BCa events from MRI screening was between 7 and 16.5 per 1000 women with dense breasts. (Bakker et al. 2019, Berg et al. 2014, Comstock et al.

² The methodology employed by this study was criticised post-publication. See commentary associated with the publication at <http://dx.doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-160-10-201405200-02007>

2020). MRI was associated with 'significantly fewer interval cancers' than mammography alone (Bakker et al. 2019). As expected, the MRI cancer detection rate decreases significantly at subsequent MRI screening rounds (Veenhuizen et al. 2021). Digital breast tomosynthesis plus synthetic mammography demonstrated a significant positive association between relative risk of BCa and stratified breast density in a Norwegian trial (Moshina et al. 2020).

Harm-benefit

Evidence of high rates of overdiagnosis from North American trials e.g. 22% of all screen-detected cancer (excluding DCIS) with no overall survival benefit (Miller et al. 2014) is not borne out by 20 years follow up for younger women in the UK setting (Duffy et al. a 2020; Gunsoy et al. 2012). Furthermore, rates of false-positive recall were comparable with routine screening (Johns et al. 2010). The recall rate from digital breast tomosynthesis + synthetic mammography appeared to be sensitive to breast density, with fewer recalls for lower density and higher rates for higher density (Moshina et al. 2020). Concerns that digital breast tomosynthesis may increase overdiagnosis were not born out from a repeated round of screening (Hofvind 2021). A false-positive rate for women with dense breasts was almost 80 per 1000 at the first round of MRI screening, but this reduced to 26.3 per 1000 at a second round (Veenhuizen et al. 2021).

Cervical cancer

11 trials and 4 systematic reviews were included and the information across the 11 RCTs was extracted and summarised in the Table. The sample size per RCT ranged from 975 to 94,370 participants. Most trials took place in Europe (9 RCTs), one in the US and one in Australia. Across RCTs with various trial designs, HPV self-sampling and Pap-smear (by midwife or clinician) were used as screening methods.

Compliance and uptake

The screening uptake was higher when HPV self-sampling was offered as a screening option than Pap-smear among women due or overdue for CC screening. The compliance rate was generally high irrespective of the testing type, although slightly descended over rounds of screening. Consistent with other RCTs reviewed (Elfström et al., 2019; Gök et al., 2012; Sancho-Garnier et al., 2013; Tranberg et al., 2018), a meta-analysis pooling data across 33 studies (29 RCTs and 4 observational studies) reported that HPV self-sampling promoted the screening uptake substantially (RR 2.13; 95% CI 1.89-2.40) compared to the standard care control. Among different dissemination methods studied, directly mailing the HPV self-sampling kit (RR 2.27; 95% CI 1.89-2.71) as well as door-to-door offering (RR 2.37; 95% CI 1.12-5.03) increased the participation rate of cervical cancer screening, but not the opt-in intervention (requested on demand; RR 1.28; 95% CI 0.90-1.82) (Yeh et al. 2019).

Cancer incidence and detection efficiency

In general, incidence of CC or CIN2+ was higher in women screened with HPV self-sampling than cytology, probably owing to the higher sensitivity of HPV testing. Among women with HPV positive results, the CC incidence was much higher than those with HPV negative results (Dijkstra et al., 2016), suggesting that HPV testing may be a potential risk-stratification tool for targeting women of higher cancer risk. A meta-analysis pooling data across 4 RCTs (176,464 women in total) also suggested that HPV-based screening may provide better protection against cervical cancer compared to conventional cytology testing (Ronco et al. 2014). The incidence of high-grade lesions (CIN3) did not vary with the screening frequency (Louvanto et al., 2020) and thereby some studies

(including the largest RCT in Netherlands) suggested that an extended screening interval (> 5 years) may be implemented, especially for women with HPV-negative results in former screening rounds for optimised harm/benefit balance (Dijkstra et al., 2016; Gilham et al., 2019).

The detection rate of CIN2+ varied among RCTs as a result of different screening methods and triages. The Compass trial (Canfell et al., 2017), for instance, reported CIN2+ detection rates ranging from 0.1% to 1.2% when liquid-based cytology (LBC) was utilised alone or when HPV screening was first used to identify those with higher risk (positive for HPV16/18) before referring to colposcopy and LBC (Canfell et al., 2017). One study reported a CIN2+ detection rate of 18.2% among HPV-positive responders while the other reported a detection rate of 9.5% (Elfström et al., 2019; Gök et al., 2012; Sancho-Garnier et al., 2013).

Altogether the evidence of CC/CIN2+ incidence and detection efficiency is inconsistent because of variations across RCTs providing relevant data.

Survival, cancer and all-cause mortality

There were no studies reporting data in terms of CC survival and mortality.

Cost-effectiveness

Among RCTs reviewed, no study provided a cost-effectiveness analysis. However, comprehensive data on cost-effectiveness were reported in two systematic reviews pooling data across different continents from modelling studies (Malone et al., 2020; Sroczynski et al., 2018).

Most (14 of 16) studies in Malone et al. (2020) reported that HPV-based self-sampling screening was more effective than a cytology-based screening strategy in terms of patient-relevant outcomes. The lifetime cost-effectiveness outcomes were mostly provided in forms of willingness to pay threshold for cost-effectiveness, ranging from \$756 USD/LYG in Uganda to \$103,531 USD/QALY in Norway (Malone et al., 2020). Another systematic review looked at 14 modelling studies comparing HPV with cytology screening (Sroczynski et al., 2018). In scenarios where women were screened with at least a 3-year (non-vaccinated) or 5-year (vaccinated) interval, HPV-based screening versus cytology alone would be considered cost-effective at a willingness-to-pay threshold of €50,000/LYG (Sroczynski et al., 2018).

Colorectal cancer

13 RCTs and two systematic reviews were included and the information across 13 trials was extracted and summarised in the Table. The size of RCTs ranged from 230 to 37,311 participants with most trials taking place in the US (8 RCTs), one in China, one in Australia, two in Europe and one unspecified. Whilst different types of screening methods were used across all RCTs, FIT and colonoscopy were the most dominant among RCTs examined.

Risk-prediction Models for CRC

Across RCTs reviewed, many used age and family histories for evaluating the CRC risk and thereby the eligibility for CRC screening (Kinney et al., 2014; Lowery et al., 2014; Carey et al., 2016; Ingrand et al., 2016; Ingrand et al., 2019; Reeves et al., 2019; Paskett et al., 2020). One systematic review analysed data across 29 risk models that incorporate common genetic variants for estimating future

incidence of CRC in the general population. Results showed that involvement of genetic variants, e.g., single-nucleotide polymorphisms, alongside other factors, e.g., age and family histories, increased the discrimination power, which would substantially change the risk stratification in the population, leading to an earlier (up to 23 years) screening invitation to whom of the top 20% for risk (McGeoch et al., 2019).

Compliance and uptake

The uptake of CRC screening test varied across different RCTs with types of screening offered, with or without active intervention, ranging from 7.6% to 83.5%. The compliance/adherence rate in general was between 50-60%, which can be improved by several pro-active interventions (Carey et al., 2016; Ingrand et al., 2016; Ingrand et al., 2019; Kinney et al., 2014; Lairson et al., 2008; Liang et al., 2021; Lowery et al., 2014; Paskett et al., 2020; Percac-Lima et al., 2016; Reeves et al., 2019; Skinner et al., 2015; Yen et al., 2021).

The largest RCT in Europe showed that general population with average risk were more prone to accept biennial FIT than one-time colonoscopy in terms of CRC screening (34.25% vs 25.38%; $P < 0.001$) (Salas et al., 2014; Urturi et al., 2012).

Risk-stratification using GERA did not improve the uptake of CRC screening; however, the GERA feedback might improve screening adherence (Myers et al., 2011; Myers et al., 2015; Weinberg et al., 2014). Another study used a blood test of methylated SEPT9 DNA for risk evaluation and found an increased uptake as well as compliance rates of CRC screening (Liang et al., 2021).

Cancer incidence and detection efficiency

Among RCTs reviewed in this report, few studies provided data on cancer incidence and detection efficiency. The incidence of CRC and AA was 0.23-0.6% and 2.4-6.9%, respectively, using colonoscopy as the screening approach for high-risk populations, either with family history or evaluated via a scoring system (Chen et al., 2019; H. Chen et al., 2020; H. D. Chen et al., 2020; Ingrand et al., 2016; Ingrand et al., 2019), which demonstrated the highest sensitivity across different approaches.

As FIT may be more preferred among populations due for CRC screening, and could be an option for risk-stratification prior to colonoscopy, the COLONPREV trial in Spain (the largest RCT included) provided analysis on how different positivity cutoffs of FIT may affect the detection efficiency in men: the sensitivity of advanced adenoma and neoplasm detection declined 7-11% when the positivity cutoffs were increased from 75 ng/ml to 125 ng/ml (Urturi et al., 2012).

A meta-analysis pooling 46 studies revealed that the specificity of FIT for CRC detection could increase from 69% to 80% when lowering the positivity threshold from $>10-20 \mu\text{g/g}$ to $\leq 10 \mu\text{g/g}$ at the expense of slightly decreased specificity (-3%). Likewise, the FIT sensitivity for detecting advanced adenoma may increase from 21% to 31% when lowering the threshold. The authors performed modelling for accessing the changes of FIT sensitivity and specificity on a theoretical cohort of 100,000 participants and found the number of CRC and advanced adenoma detected increased by 16% and 43%, respectively, when lowering the positivity threshold from $>10-20 \mu\text{g/g}$ to $\leq 10 \mu\text{g/g}$ (Selby et al., 2019).

In general, the CRC detection rate was higher by means of colonoscopy compared to other screening types (Chen et al., 2019; H. Chen et al., 2020; H. D. Chen et al., 2020; Liang et al., 2021; Salas et al., 2014; Urturi et al., 2012). The largest RCT in Europe showed that the detection rate of any

neoplasms using colonoscopy was much higher compared to FIT (OR 12.06; 95%CI 10.73-13.55) (Salas et al., 2014; Urturi et al., 2012). Similar results were reported in the largest RCT in Asia where detection rate of CRC or advanced neoplasms was better utilising colonoscopy than FIT. Yet using FIT or risk-adapted screening strategy as primary care options could reduce the number of colonoscopies thus the resource load required for detecting one advanced colorectal neoplasm (Chen et al., 2019; H. Chen et al., 2020; H. D. Chen et al., 2020).

Survival, cancer and all-cause mortality

No study provided data on CRC survival or mortality.

Cost-effectiveness

The cost-effectiveness analysis was only reported in two RCTs. One study reported comparable QALYs between subjects receiving risk-level tailored advice and general information for CRC screening uptake were found comparable. The ICER amounted to 258 AUD per person properly screened from the health care perspective whilst 275 AUD from the societal perspective (Reeves et al., 2019). The other study compared the promoting efficiency of CRC screening uptake among three groups: SI, TI, TIP and a control group with usual care. The ICER was estimated at 319 USD in SI compared to usual care and was more effective and dominated TI (Lairson et al., 2008).

2.1 Summary of the evidence base [table]

Breast cancer

Citation	Study Details	Participants	Outcomes	Results	Notes
MyPeBS MyPeBS 2017	RCT Belgium, France, Israel, Italy, United Kingdom and Spain 2018-present Standard M vs. M ± US ± MRI stratified by 4 risk groups*	Total # screened: Target N ~ 85,000 Population: Target screening population, women 40–70 yrs	1. Proportion of > stage IIB tumours 2. Reduction in recall rate Number of biopsies	Protocol: No results available	Power calculation: Y *5-yr risk of BCa defined by Breast Cancer Surveillance Consortium individualised breast cancer risk prediction model: <i>Low risk</i> (<1%): M every 4 years. <i>Medium risk</i> (1–1.66%): biennial M (if high density, US every 2 years) <i>High risk</i> (1.67–6%): annual M (if high density US every year) <i>Very high risk</i> (> = 6%): annual M + MRI
EA1141 Comstock 2020	Study with randomised screening modality order US & Germany 2006-2007	Total # screened: N = 1444* Population: Women 40–75 yrs with dense or extremely dense breast tissue 12 yrs FU	1. Invasive BCa detection rate 2. Sensitivity Specificity Additional imaging recommendation rate (callback plus recommendation for short-term follow-up)	Uptake: NR Compliance: *all 1444 women received both imaging modalities with randomised temporal order Outcomes Incidence/stage: At ~12 years, MRI detected 17/17 invasive BCa and 5/6 DCIS vs 7/17 and 2/6 women for DBT BCa detection rate was 11.8 (95%CI 7.4–18.8) per 1000 women for MRI vs 4.8 (95%CI 2.4-10.0) per 1000 women for DBT; a difference of 7 (95%CI 2.2-11.6) per 1000 women (P = .002)	Power calculation: Y

	One time screening with abbreviated MRI vs DBT		PPV of biopsy for invasive BCa & DCIS	<p>Harms-benefits: For detection of BCa and DCIS: <i>sensitivity</i> = 95.7% (95%CI 79.0–99.2) for MRI vs. 39.1% (95%CI 22.2-59.2) for DBT (P = .001); <i>specificity</i> = 86.7% (95% CI, 84.8%-88.4%) vs. 97.4% (95% CI, 96.5%-98.1%), respectively (P < .001). The additional imaging recommendation rate was 7.5% (95%CI 6.2%–9.0%) for MRI vs 10.1% (95%CI 8.7%–11.8%) with DBT (P = .02); PPV = 19.6% (95%CI 13.2%–28.2%) vs. 31.0% (95%CI 17.0%-49.7%), respectively (P = .15)</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p>	
<p>WISDOM</p> <p>Naeim et al. 2018</p> <p>Shieh et al. 2019</p> <p>Acerbi et al. 2021</p>	<p>Pragmatic preference-tolerant RCT</p> <p>US</p> <p>2016 - present</p> <p>Annual M vs RBS of M ± MRI stratified by 4 risk groups* [validation of risk thresholds in Shieh 2017)</p>	<p>N~ 100,000 target</p> <p>28706 consented as of July 2020 (<i>Acerbi 2021</i>)</p> <p>Total # screened: NR</p> <p>Population: Target screening population Women 40–74 yrs</p>	<p>1. Rate of ≥ stage IIB tumours Reduced rate of recall and breast biopsy between arms</p> <p>2. Rate of stage IIB and interval cancers Rate of DCIS Recall rates and follow-up procedures Proportion of women enrolling in randomised vs. self-assigned cohort Within self-assigned cohort, % choosing risk-based screening vs. standard annual screening</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: Interim analysis of N = 1643/1817 (90.4%) completing baseline questionnaires. 1071/1643 (65.1%) willing to be randomised to a study arm. Risk perception not significantly different between random vs observational arms. 474/572 (82.9%) of those who joined the observational cohort selected the personalised risk arm. Anxiety levels low and similar across arms. Mean (SD) <i>anxiety</i> scores at baseline = 14.0 (4.6). Mean (SD) Breast Cancer Risk Worry scores = 5.7 (1.05). (Naeim et al 2018)</p> <p>Outcomes</p> <p>Incidence: A study population simulated cohort of 100,000 women modelled no statistically significant difference in % of ≥ stage IIB BCa between personalised vs standard screening, RR = 1.01 (95%CI 0.89-1.12). The average 5-year BCa risk of annual screening under the personalised strategy was higher than the</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>Both a randomised cohort and observational cohort - intervention assignment self-selected - integrated into WISDOM. High-risk of bias in the observational cohort.</p> <p>*5-yr risk of BCa defined by Breast Cancer Surveillance Consortium individualised breast cancer risk prediction model: <i>Low risk</i> (40–49 years and <1.3%): start M at age 50 years. <i>Medium risk</i> (50–74 years, or 40-49 years with risk ≥ 1.3%): biennial M.</p>

			<p>PROMIS anxiety score Breast cancer risk worry</p>	<p>hybrid strategy (M+MRI), 1.7% vs. 1.2%. The average 5-year risk of biennial screening was lower under the personalised strategy, 1.1% vs. 1.9%.</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: Biennial, hybrid (M+MRI), and personalised strategies resulted in fewer FP, RR = 0.55 (95%CI 0.46-0.65) and biopsies RR = 0.56 (0.47-0.65) compared to annual screening. (Shieh et al 2019)</p> <p>Cost effectiveness: Modelling indicated biennial, hybrid and personalised strategies delivered at lower cost vs annual screening; 14.1 v 22.1 million US\$ per 100,000 women. (Shieh et al 2019)</p>	<p><i>High risk</i> (extremely dense breasts, risk $\geq 0.75\%$ of ER-tumour): annual M. <i>Very high-risk</i> (genetic mutations): annual M + MRI</p>
<p>ACRIN 6666 Berg et al. 2012</p>	<p>RCT sub study USA 2004-2006 3 annual rounds of M+US \pm one-time MRI after 24-month M</p>	<p>Total # screened: N = 2809 underwent 7473 M and US</p> <p>Population: Women with ≥ 1 other BCa risk factor* AND heterogeneously dense or extremely dense breast tissue</p>	<p>1. Supplemental cancer detection rate with 1 MRI</p> <p>2. Sensitivity Specificity PPV of biopsies performed and interval cancer rate</p>	<p>Uptake: Of a total 7473 M and US screenings: 2659 completed the first annual M + US (35.6%)</p> <p>Compliance: 2493/2659 completed the second (93.8%); 2321 the third (87.3%). 703 chose to undergo MRI (612 with complete data)</p> <p>Outcomes Incidence/stage: 111 BCa events detected: 89 invasive BCa and 22 DCIS. 33 detected by M only, 32 by US only, 26 by both, and 9 by MRI (after M + US); 11 not detected by any modality.</p> <p>For M alone: <i>sensitivity</i> was 0.52 (95%CI, 0.40-0.64); <i>specificity</i>, 0.91 (95%CI, 0.90-0.92); PPV, 0.38 (95%CI, 0.28-0.49; P.001 all comparisons. <i>Supplemental yield of US screening</i> was 3.7 cancers per 1000 screens (95%CI, 2.1-5.8). <i>Sensitivity</i> for M + US was 0.76 (95%CI, 0.65-0.85); <i>specificity</i>, 0.84 (95%CI, 0.83-0.85); PPV, 0.16 (95%CI, 0.12-0.21). 16 of 612 MRI participants (2.6%) had breast cancer diagnosed.</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>*Risk factors Mutation in BRCA1 or BRCA2 History of prior chest, mediastinal, or axillary irradiation Personal history of breast cancer Lifetime risk, Gail/Claus model $\geq 25\%$ -Year risk, Gail model $\geq 2.5\%$ 5-Year risk, Gail model $\geq 1.7\%$ and extremely dense breasts ADH/ALH/LCIS or atypical papilloma ADH, atypical ductal hyperplasia; ALH, atypical lobular hyperplasia; LCIS, lobular carcinoma in situ</p>

				<p><i>Supplemental yield of MRI</i> was 14.7 per 1000 (95%CI, 3.5-25.9). <i>Sensitivity</i> for MRI +M + US was 1.00 (95%CI, 0.79-1.00); <i>Specificity</i>, 0.65 (95% CI, 0.61-0.69); <i>PPV</i>, 0.19 (95% CI, 0.11-0.29).</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: NND 1 cancer was 127 (95%CI, 99-167) for M; 234 (95%CI, 173-345) for supplemental US; and 68 (95% CI, 39-286) for MRI after -ve MRI + US.</p>	
<p>DENSE</p> <p>Bakker et al. 2019</p> <p>Geuzinge et al 2021</p> <p>Veenhuizen et al. 2021</p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>Netherlands</p> <p>2011-2015</p> <p>3 rounds of biennial screening with M + MRI vs M alone</p>	<p>N = 40,373 I = 8061 Total # screened = 4783 C = 32,312</p> <p>Population: Women 50–75 yrs with extremely dense breast tissue*</p> <p>2-year FU</p>	<p>1. Incidence of interval cancer (proxy for reduction in morbidity and mortality)</p> <p>2. Recall rate MRI screening Detected cancer FP rate PPV Tumour characteristics QoL Cost effectiveness</p>	<p>Uptake: 4783/8061 accepted MRI invite (59%).</p> <p>Compliance: 3436/4783 (72%) underwent a second MRI round</p> <p>Incidence/stage: Interval-cancer rate/1000 screenings = 2.5 in I group vs 5.0 in C group [difference of 2.5 per 1000 screenings (95%CI 1.0-3.7; P<0.001). Of 20 interval cancers detected in I group, 4 cases underwent MRI (0.8/1000 screenings) and 16 did not accept the invitation (4.9/1000 screenings). MRI cancer-detection rate = 16.5/1000 screenings (95%CI, 13.3-20.5). PPV = 17.4% (95%CI, 3.8-9.0) for recall for additional testing and 26.3% (95%CI, 21.7-31.6) for biopsy.</p> <p>At screening round 2, MRI cancer-detection rate = 5.8/1000 screenings (95%CI, 13.3-20.5). PPV = 18% (95%CI, 12.1.2-26.4) for recall for additional testing and 24.0% (95%CI, 16.0-33.9) for biopsy.</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: FP rate was 79.8 /1000 screenings at round 1 and 26.3/1000 at round 2 screenings. 0.1%</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>*grade 4 as measured on Volpara imaging software</p>

				<p>who underwent MRI had an adverse/serious adverse event during or immediately after screening.</p> <p>Cost effectiveness: MRI alone very 4 years dominated both trial arms at €15,620/QALY. A 3-year interval resulted in an ICER of €15,620/QALY. Geuzinge et al 2021</p>	
<p>UK Age trial</p> <p>Duffy et al. a 2020</p> <p>Duffy et al. b 2020</p> <p>Johns et al. 2010</p> <p>Gunsoy et al. 2012</p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>UK</p> <p>1990-1997</p> <p>Annual M till 48 yrs vs usual care of no screening via UK NHSBSP</p>	<p>N = 160,921 I = 53,883</p> <p>Total # screened ~37,179 C = 106,953</p> <p>Population: Women 39-41 yrs i.e. below eligible age for screening via UK NHSBSP</p> <p>23 yr FU</p>	<p>1. Mortality from BCa diagnosed in intervention period</p> <p>2. Mortality from BCa diagnosed after randomisation</p> <p>All-cause mortality</p> <p>Mortality from causes other than breast cancer (in the entire trial population and in the subgroup of women with breast cancer), incidence of breast cancer</p>	<p>Uptake: Uptake was 36,622/53,801 invitations (68·1%) at round 1 and 176,746/255,618 (69·1%) across subsequent rounds ~ 31% average non-compliance rate (Johns 2010.)</p> <p>Compliance: 89% of women who had a FP recall at their previous screen attended their next invitation to routine screening. (Duffy et al. b 2020)</p> <p>Incidence/stage: RR of BCa incidence just before the first NHSBSP screen = 1.09 (95%CI 1.00-1.19; p = 0.03). RR up to and including first NHSBSP screen = 0.99 (95%CI 0.92-1.07; p = 0.7). At the end of 23 yr FU, RR = 0.99 (95%CI 0.94-1.04; p = 0.6). i.e. no excess in I group in addition to cancers diagnosed in the NHSBSP from the age of 50 years onwards.</p> <p>BCa mortality: 83 BCa deaths in I group vs. 219 in C group (RR = 0.75 (95%CI 0.58–0.97; p=0.029) represents ~ 25% reduction in BCa mortality at 10 years FU. No significant reduction was observed thereafter: 126 deaths in I group vs 255 deaths in C group after more than 10 years FU (RR=0.98 [0.79–1.22]; p=0.86). (Duffy et al. b 2020)</p> <p>Absolute benefit of screening ~ 1 death prevented per 1000 women screened (Duffy et al. a 2020)</p> <p>All-cause mortality: No significant difference in all-cause mortality: 3507 deaths in I group vs 6932 in C group (RR = 1.01, 95%CI 0.96–1.05; p=0.66), or</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p>

				<p>mortality from causes other than BCa (RR = 1.02 (0.97–1.07; p=0.43). (Duffy et al. b 2020)</p> <p>Harms-benefits: 14.6% (7,893) of I group experienced ≥ 1 FP. Rates of FP rate at first and subsequent routine screens were 4.9% and 3.2%, respectively. Cumulative FP rate over 7 screens = 20.5%.</p> <p>PPV of recall was 2% at first screen and 3%–5% at subsequent screens, increasing with age.</p> <p>[comparison NHSBSP PPV of 8% at first screens and 16% at subsequent screens] (Johns 2010)</p> <p>Total # of expected screen-detected cancers was 164 vs 244 observed. This suggests 80 (8.5%) of screen-detected cancers diagnosed in the intervention phase were <i>overdiagnosis</i>. This equates to 32.8% of screen-detected cancers, and an absolute rate of 0.2% over 8 years of screening in women 40-49.</p> <p>Markov modelling estimate overdiagnosis as 0.7% of screen-detected cancers (range 0.5% to 2.9%).</p> <p>Simulated screen-detectable mean duration of pre-clinical cancer states (mean sojourn time) of non-progressive and progressive in situ cancers was 1.3 (95%CI 0.4-3.4) and 0.11 (95%CI 0.05-0.19) years, respectively, and 0.8 years (95%CI 0.6-1.2) for preclinical invasive breast cancer.</p> <p>The sensitivity of M for invasive and in situ breast cancers was 90% (95%CI 72-99) and 82% (43-99), respectively. (Gunsoy et al. 2012)</p>	
UK Breast Screening	RCT UK	N = 99 389 Total # screened: I = 49 173 C = 50 216	Predicted BCa mortality	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: The attendance rate in the control group among women who had attended the prevalence screen was 85%. In the study group,</p>	Power calculation: Y

Frequency Trial Van Ravesteyn et al. 2011	1989-1996 Standard triennial M vs. 3 annual M screens	Population: Target screening population, women aged 50–62 yrs		attendance rates at the three yearly screens were 78%, 78% and 81% respectively. BCa mortality: MISCAN modelling estimated RR = 0.83 for BCa mortality in I group vs C group (point statistic within reported trial 95%CI). Increasing the simulated FU to lifetime had no effect on predicted RR. A simulated increase of screening sensitivity and attendance rate both reduced predicted RR to 0.81	
Breast Cancer Screening with Alternate Mammography and Ultrasound Huang et al. 2010	RCT Taiwan 2003–2008 Cross-over design with M and US on alternate years until 2008	N = 79,691 Total # screened I _M = 20,040 first assigned to M I _{US} = 20,088 first assigned to US* C = 39,563 Population: Women aged 40–49 yrs	Detection rate and annual incidence rate of interval cancer as a percentage of the control group (I/E ratio) compared between M vs US.	Uptake: Attendance rate at round 1 was 11921/20040 (59%) for M and 11249/20088 (56%) for US. Compliance: Attendance rates of both groups was 85% and 91% in rounds 2 and 3, respectively. Incidence: At round 1, the BCa detection rates were 0.34% for I _M group and 0.22% for I _{US} group. The additional detection rate was 0.16% from a subsequent US screen and 0.36% from a subsequent M. M + US was 3-4x more likely to detect BCa compared with C group (annual incidence rate was 0.17%). The detection rate of interval cancer as a % of the C group was lower after M vs. after US screening.	Power calculation: Y *Cross-over design with mammography and US on alternate years until 2008 Limited data reporting from conference abstract
J-START Ishida et al. 2014	RCT Japan 2006-2012 M + US v M alone 2 rounds biennially	N = 76,196 Total # screened I = 38,313 C = 37,883 Population: Women aged 40–49 yrs	1. sensitivity, specificity and the rate of detection of cancer 2. cumulative rate of advanced breast cancer	Uptake: NR Compliance: 74.1% of participants at round 1 were screened at round 2 Outcomes - Only preliminary data reported after round 2 of screening complete Incidence/stage/mortality: NR	Power calculation: Y
Project HOME	RCT	N = 5500 Total # screened =3660	Prevalence of at least 1 self-reported post-	Uptake: 44.7%, 46.9% and 46% in C group, I1 group and I2 group reported undergoing at least one M	Power calculation: NR

<p>Lairson et al. 2011</p>	<p>US</p> <p>Dates NR</p> <p>Interventions to increase compliance with BCa screening (i) generic messages (ii) tailored to individual responses to questionnaire</p>	<p>I1 = 1857 generic intervention I2 = 1803 tailored intervention C = 1840 control (survey only)</p> <p>Population: Female, veterans, 52 years of age or older</p>	<p>intervention M and 2 post-intervention Ms 6-15 months apart.</p> <p>ICERs per additional person screened</p>	<p>Compliance: Not applicable Incidence/stage/mortality: NR Cost effectiveness: At 2008 US\$ values, the societal costs for generic intervention were \$25 per person vs. \$52 per person for tailored intervention. ~ 27% of total costs were identifying and recruiting eligible population. Eligibility costs were a higher proportion of total cost (40%) for I1 vs. I2 (20%). The ICER was \$1,116 comparing I1 vs. C groups (95%CI = \$493 to dominated). The I2 (tailored) intervention was dominated by the I1 (generic) intervention, i.e., I2 more costly and less effective than I1.</p>	
<p>Canadian NBSS National Breast Screening Study</p> <p>Miller et al. 2014</p> <p>Narod et al. 2014</p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>Canada</p> <p>1980-1985</p> <p>4 to 5 annual M + breast exam for I group till age 60</p>	<p>N = 89,835 Total # screened I = 44,925 C = 44,910</p> <p>Population: Women 40 to 49 yrs, no history of breast cancer, no M in past 12 months</p> <p>Mean 22 yr, max 25 yrs FU</p>	<p>1. BCa mortality 2. BCa incidence overdiagnosis</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: NR Outcomes Incidence/ mortality: BCa detected in 1.5% (40-49 yrs) and 7.2% (50-59) of I group vs. 1.2% and 7.0% of the C group across the 25-yr FU period. At a mean 22 yrs FU, BCa mortality rate / 10,000 women was 108 vs 100 in I and C groups RRR = 1% (95%CI -12 to 12). (Miller et al. 2014)</p> <p>A cohort of n = 50,436 age 40–49 years were FU until age 60. (Narod et al. 2014) Of 256 deaths from BCa recorded in the study cohort, 134 occurred in I group, and 122 in C group. The cumulative risk of death from BCa to age 60 was 0.53% and 0.48% for I and C groups, respectively The hazard ratio for BCa-specific death associated with 1 or more screening mammograms before age 50 was 1.10 (95%CI 0.86-1.40).</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>DCIS excluded from analysis would likely increase overdiagnosis estimate</p>

				<p>Harms-benefits: For the whole study population at 22 years, 22% of screen-detected invasive Bca cases and 50% of nonpalpable cancer were overdiagnosis (Miller et al. 2014)</p>	
<p>Extension of the invited age range in NHSBSP</p> <p>Moser et al. 2011</p>	<p>Cluster RCT</p> <p>UK</p> <p>2009–2010</p> <p>Invitation v no invitation for standard NHSBSP triennial M screening</p>	<p>N = 60,708</p> <p>Total # screened = 31,069</p> <p>[47–49 yrs I = 20,596 C = 19,409; 71 – 73yrs I = 10,473 C = 10,230]</p> <p>Population: Women aged 47– 49 & 71–73 yrs</p>	<p>Workload from randomisation screening uptake among women invited</p> <p>self-referrals among women not invited</p> <p>and screening outcomes among women invited</p>	<p>Uptake: 63% accepted screening (63% aged 47–49, 62% aged 71–73). A higher proportion of the younger group DNA (29% vs. 24%).</p> <p>Compliance: Over the 12 month study, 31 women (0.2%) aged 47–49 who had been randomised to C group requested M screening. For women aged 71–73 697 (6.8%) requested M screening.</p> <p>Outcomes</p> <p>Incidence: BCa incidence rate was 0.5% and 1.1% in the 47–49 vs 71–73 age groups.</p> <p>Harms-benefits:</p> <p>Recall rate was 7.5% and 3.0% in the 47–49 vs 71–73 age group.</p> <p>Among the women recalled for assessment 7% (65/966) of those recalled aged 47–49 were found to have BCa vs 36% (70/192) of recalled women aged 71–73. The percentage of women 2.8% vs. 1.8% of those screened had a needle biopsy in the 47–49 vs 71–73 age group.</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p>
<p>To-Be 1 Trial Moshina et al. 2020</p> <p>To-Be 2 Trial Hofvind et al. 2021</p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>Norway</p> <p>2016-2017</p> <p>SM + DBT vs. DM</p>	<p>N = 28,749</p> <p>Total # screened I = 14,380 (DBT+ SM) C = 14,369 (DM)</p> <p>Population: Target screening population</p>	<p>To-Be 1</p> <p>Rates of recall</p> <p>FP rate</p> <p>Biopsy</p> <p>cancer detection rate, PPV of recalls & biopsies</p> <p>Tumour histopathology</p>	<p>Uptake: Of 44,266 women invited for screening, 32,976 (74.5%) attended screening and 29,453 (66.5%) consented to participate in the trial.</p> <p>Compliance: Of the 28,749 women screened in To-Be1 22,306 (77.6%) returned for a second screening round in to-BE2 (11,105 from C group and 11,201 from I group)</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>*Volpara Density Grade (VDG) 1–4</p> <p>To-BE 1 participants were screened and followed for 2</p>

		stratified by breast tissue density*	<p>To-Be 2</p> <p>Cancer detection rates and tumor characteristics of interval cancers</p>	<p>Outcomes</p> <p>Incidence: For DBT+SM, RR of screen-detected breast cancer (VDG 2: 2.4; $P = .004$; VDG 3: 2.8; $P = .01$; VDG 4: 2.8; $P = .05$) increased with VDG, whereas no differences in RR were observed for DM (VDG 2: 1.7; $P = .13$; VDG 3: 2.1; $P = .06$; VDG 4: 2.2; $P = .15$).</p> <p>At round 2 (To-Be 2 trial), 20 interval cancers were detected (rate of 1.4 per 1000 screens) in I group vs 29 (2.0 per 1000 screens) in C group.</p> <p>Tumor characteristics were similar between groups</p> <p>The RR of interval cancer was 0.69 (95%CI: 0.39–1.22; $P = .20$) for DBT versus DM,</p> <p>Harms-benefits: The recall rate for I group vs. C group for VDG:</p> <p>1 = (2.1% [81 of 3929] vs 3.3% [106 of 3212]; $P = .001$)</p> <p>2 = (3.2% [200 of 6216] vs 4.3% [267 of 6280]; $P = .002$).</p> <p>For DBT+SM, RR of recall (VDG 2: 1.8; $P < .001$; VDG 3: 2.4; $P < .001$; VDG 4: 1.8; $P = .02$) increased with VDG, whereas no differences were observed for DM (relative risk of recall for VDG 2: 1.3; $P = .06$; VDG 3: 1.1; $P = .41$; VDG 4: 1.1; $P = .71$)</p>	years, then invited to To-BE 2 (if met eligibility)
<p>Patient Navigation for Comprehensive Cancer Screening</p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>US</p> <p>2014</p> <p>IT-enabled patient navigation for</p>	<p>Among 1612 patients (673 men and 975 women)</p> <p>N = 1612*</p> <p>I = 7927</p> <p>C = 829</p> <p>Population:</p>	<p>1. Mean cancer screening test completion rate over 8-month trial</p> <p>2. proportion of patients completing overdue cancer screening test(s)</p>	<p>Uptake: Not applicable.</p> <p>Compliance: Of patients at high risk for non-compliance 605/797 (75.9%) allocated to intervention received the intervention and 764/829 (92.1%) of patients allocated to control. For the I group, patient navigators were unable to reach 151 (19%), deferred 246 (38%) (patient declined,</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>*Study of combined breast, cervical and colorectal cancers.</p>

Percac-Lima et al. 2016	routine cancer screening	Target screening population* -women 50-74 yrs for BCa in in low income & ethnic/racial minority populations.		<p>competing comorbidity), and navigated to 202 (32%).</p> <p>Outcomes The mean proportion up to date with screening among all overdue screening examinations for I group vs C group was 14.7% vs 11.0% (95%CI 0.2%-7.3%; P = .04) for breast cancer screening. The proportion of I group vs C group completing breast screening was 23.4% vs 16.6% (95%CI 1.8%-12.0%; P = .009).</p> <p>Incidence/stage/mortality: NR</p>	
Pasynkov et al. 2021	<p>RCT</p> <p>Russia</p> <p>Dates NR</p> <p>US ± Computer aided detection (CAD) system during screening</p>	<p>Total # screened N = 2078</p> <p>Random allocation NR I = UX + CAD C = US alone</p> <p>Population: Women 40-72 yrs with dense breast tissue after negative M</p> <p>3 yr FU</p>	Number and size of lesions detected with and without the CAD results	<p>Uptake: All 2078 women meeting criteria were screened with randomly allocated modality</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable.</p> <p>Incidence/stage: 16 vs 22 BCa detected in the C I group (US +CAD). 3 /16 BCs (18.8%) in C group vs 11 /22 (50.0%) BCa in I group were <1cm dia (p< 0.05). During 3-year FU, 9 more BCa in C group and 2 more BCa in I group were detected</p> <p>Harm-benefit: The rate of benign lesions requiring biopsy was 76 /1039 (7.31%) in C group and 68 /1039 (6.54%) in I group.</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>Superficial reporting of trial methods and results</p>
Göteborg Trial Bjurstam et al. 2016	<p>RCT</p> <p>Sweden</p> <p>Dates 1982-2007</p>	<p>Total # screened N = 21,904</p> <p>Age 39-49 11,792 Age 50-50 10,112</p>	Cumulative mortality	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: NR</p> <p>Incidence/stage: The reduction in the incidence rate of node-positive cancers was significant in the 39- to 49-year age group (RR, 0.65; 95% CI, 0.43-0.97; P = .03) but not in the 50- to 59-year group (RR, 0.98; 95% CI, 0.67-1.43; P = .9).</p>	Power calculation: NR

	Mammographic screening vs usual care for women 39-49 vs 50-59	I = Offer of mammography every 18 months (N= 21,904) C = Usual care (N= 30,318) 25 yr FU		<p>Harm-benefit: NR</p> <p>Mortality: In women aged 39 to 49 years, there was a significant 40% reduction in breast cancer mortality (RR, 0.60; 95% CI, 0.43-0.85; $P = .003$). In the 50- to 59-year age group, there was a nonsignificant 18% breast cancer mortality reduction (RR, 0.82; 95% CI, 0.54-1.26; $P = .4$).</p>	
--	---	--	--	--	--

Abbreviations and Acronyms	
	<p>N=Total number in trial; I=in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S=No. screened</p> <p><i>Uptake:</i> Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial</p> <p><i>Compliance:</i> Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening</p>
BCa	Breast cancer
BMI	body mass index
C [group]	Control/non-screened group
CI	confidence interval
DBT	Digital breast tomosynthesis
DCIS	Ductal carcinoma in situ
DENSE	Dense Tissue and Early Breast Neoplasm Screening Trial
DM	Digital mammography
DNA	Did not attend
FP(R)	False positive (rate)
FU	Follow up
HR	Hazard ratio
HRQOL	Health-related quality of life
I [group]	Intervention/screened group
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IRR	Incidence rate ratio
J-START	Japan Strategic Anti-cancer Randomised Trial

M	Mammography/mammographic screening
MISCAN	Microsimulation of Screening Analysis
MLT	Mean lead time [average time by which diagnosis is advanced by screening relative to without screening]
MyPeBS	My Personal Breast Screening
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
NBSS	National Breast Screening Study
NHSBSP	National Health Service Breast Screening Programme
NND	Number needed to invite to diagnose to prevent one cancer death
NNI	Number needed to invite to screening to prevent one cancer death
NPV	Negative predictive value
NR	Not reported
PPV	Positive predictive value
ProjectHOME	Project Healthy Outlook on the Mammography Experience
QALY	Quality-adjusted life-years
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
REToMo	Reggio Emilia Tomosynthesis trial
RBS	Risk-based screening
RR	Relative risk
SM	Synthetic mammography
I [group]	Intervention group
VDG	Volpara Density Grade
WISDOM	Women Informed to Screen Depending On Measures of Risk Study

Cervical cancer

Trial	Trial Details	Participants	Outcomes/Results	Notes
ARTISTIC	UK	N = 24,510 I = NR C = NR	Uptake: NR	Power calculation: Y

(Gilham et al., 2019)	2001-2003 NA	S = 23,888 Mean age NR (20-69 y) 12 y follow-up post randomisation Population: general population eligible for routine cervical cytology screening	<p>Compliance: Among 24,510 women, 24,496 (ca 100%) participated at round 1 and 13,591 (55%) women remained for analysis at round 2.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: In total, 505 CIN3+ cases were identified with 22 being invasive cancers. - Detection rate: Among 331 women with double positive of high-risk HPV tests, 115 (35%) were positive with a new HPV type at round 2 and 216 (65%) showed persistent infection of specific genotype. - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - CC Risk: The 10-year cumulative CIN3+ risk in women with HC2-negative at entry was higher in those aged 25-39 years (0.40%; 95%CI 0.28-0.56%) compared to those aged > 40 years (0.11%; 95%CI 0.06-0.20%) ($P < 0.001$). Higher cumulative CIN3+ risk was observed in women with HPV 16 infection than those with infections of any other genotype. HPV16 infection also showed the highest 10-year cumulative CIN3+ risk following a new infection at round 2. Persistent infection of any genotype was associated with higher risk (20.4%; 95%CI 15.6-26.4%). 	<p>This trial was aimed to compare the HPV testing with routine cytology regarding the risk and corresponding screening intervals of women.</p> <p>Cytology was performed using LBC technology at the trial entry (baseline), 3 and 6 years after entry, which were subjected to HPV test. After trial ended in 2009, women returned to routine cytological screening with recall every 3 years (aged < 50 years) or 5 years (aged 50-64 years).</p>
CHOICE (Tranberg et al., 2018)	Denmark 2016-2017 1) A self-sampling kit	N = 9791 I ₁ = 3265 I ₂ = 3264 C = 3262 S = NR	<p>Uptake: The trial examined differential uptake amongst all women (34-64) due to receive a second reminder from the Central Denmark region.</p> <p>Compliance/Uptake: Higher participation rate was observed in the directly mailed group compared to the control for women of Western immigrants (PD 18.1%; 95%CI 10.2-26.0%) and</p>	<p><i>Power calculation: Y</i></p> <p><i>This trial was designed to compare the invitation strategy, kit directly mailed versus invitation for opt-in, for screening</i></p>

	<p>directly mailed to home (directly mailed group; I₁)</p> <p>2) An invitation sent for ordering kit (opt-in group; I₂)</p> <p>3) A standard 2nd reminder mailed for regular cytology screening (control group; C)</p>	<p>Mean age NR (30-64 y)</p> <p>1 y follow-up</p> <p>Population: general population due for the 2nd reminder of routine cervical cytology screening</p>	<p>social welfare recipients (PD 15.2%; 95%CI 9.7-20.6%). Compared to the control group, the largest effects of opt-in strategy were found for women receiving social welfare (PD 7.8%; 95%CI 2.6-13.1%) and women with middle level of education (PD 7.3%; 95%CI 4.5-10.1%). In general, mailing the kit directly led to higher participation than the opt-in strategy, particularly in Western immigrants, which resulted in two times higher participation rate (34.3% vs 16.0%; RR 2.14; 95%CI 1.51-3.04).</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: NR. - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p><i>uptake by women across various socioeconomic groups.</i></p>
<p>Compass (Canfell et al., 2017)</p>	<p>Australia</p> <p>2013-2014</p> <p>1) LBC with HPV triage of low-grade cytology (LBC screening group; I₁)</p> <p>2) HPV screening with those positive for</p>	<p>N = 5006</p> <p>I₁ = 998</p> <p>I₂ = 1996</p> <p>I₃ = 2012</p> <p>C = NA</p> <p>S = 4995</p> <p>Mean age NR (25-64 y)</p> <p>18 m follow-up</p> <p>Population: general population</p>	<p>Uptake: 5,303 participants were recruited from 8,595 eligible women approached (62%).</p> <p>Compliance: The compliance rate was 99.8% across all groups.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: The overall CIN2+ incidence rates were 0.1%, 1.0% and 1.2% in the LBC screening, HPV+LBC triage and HPV+DS triage groups, respectively, whilst the corresponding CIN3+ rates were 0.1%, 0.7% and 0.8%. - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>This trial was designed to evaluate the influence of implementation of HPV vaccination on the CC screening and detection efficiency.</p> <p>All women aged ≤ 33 years at the time of trial enrolment (2014)</p>

	<p>HPV16/18 referred to colposcopy and with LBC triage for OHR (HPV+LBC triage group; I₂)</p> <p>3) HPV screening with those positive for HPV16/18 referred to colposcopy and with dual-stained cytology triage for OHR (HPV+DS triage; I₃)</p>		<p>- Sensitivity/Specificity: The overall PPVs for CIN2+ and CIN3+ were 3.7% and 3.7% for the LBC screening; 26.7% and 17.3% for HPV+LBC triage; 30.4% and 21.5% for HPV+DS triage, provided primary and triage referral mechanisms and 12-m follow-up were considered.</p>	<p>were offered HPV vaccination (22% of participants).</p>
<p>HPV self-sampling vs Pap-smear</p> <p>(Sancho-Garnier et al., 2013)</p>	<p>France</p> <p>2011</p> <p>1) HPV self-sampling (I₁)</p> <p>2) Pap-smear (I₂)</p>	<p>N = 18,730</p> <p>I₁ = 8829</p> <p>I₂ = 9901</p> <p>C = NA</p> <p>S = 1811</p> <p>Mean age NR (35-69 y)</p> <p>Time follow-up NR</p> <p>Population: nonattenders of CC screening from lower socioeconomic groups</p>	<p>Uptake: Trial examined differential uptake from all non responders to invitation for a Pap-smear who had not had a Pap-smear in ≥ 2 years.</p> <p>The uptake rate was 0.2% in the Pap-smear group compared to 18.3% in the HPV self-sampling group ($P \leq 0.001$). The completion rate of Pap-smear increased with age ($P < 0.001$) while no age-associated trend was observed in the HPV self-sampling group.</p> <p>Compliance:</p> <p>The compliance of follow-up recommendations was around 55% in the Pap-smear group and 41% in the HPV self-sampling group.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>Sample quality was generally good with only 0.5% of Pap-smear classified as unsatisfactory and 0.56% of HPV self-sampling unanalysed due to technical issues.</p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: Two CIN3 were diagnosed in the Pap-smear group while 6 CIN2, 3 CIN3 and 2 invasive cancers were diagnosed in the HPV self-sampling group, rendering the prevalence of CIN2+ lesions 9.5% in the latter. - Detection rate: Around 4.5% (9 of 198) women of Pap-smear group had abnormal results whilst the positive rate of HPV was 17.6% (283 of 1604). The prevalence of HPV type was 3.24% HPV16, 1.4% HPV18 and 13% non-HPV16/18. The detection rate of CIN2+ was 0.2 per 1000 for the Pap-smear group compared to 1.25 per 1000 for the HPV self-sampling group ($P = 0.01$). - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
HPV vaccines vs screening frequency (Louvanto et al., 2020)	Finland 2014-2017 1) Frequent screening at age of 22/25/28 (Arm 1; I ₁) 2) Infrequent screening at the age of 28 (Arm 2; I ₂) 3) Safety control who had	N = 4273 I ₁ = 2073 I ₂ = 2200 C = 1329* S = NR Mean age 22 y > 4 y follow-up Population: females who received HPV16/18 vaccination in 2007-2009 at age of 13-15 *Safety control for risk assessment	Uptake: Of 13,354 eligible 22 year olds 4,273 (32%) were randomised to infrequent vs frequent screening. Compliance: The compliance rate of the 1 st screening visit was 97% across three arms. Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: The incidence rates of CIN3 were comparable between infrequently screened, cross-vaccinated Arm 3 and frequently screened Arm 1 (0.4% for both). - Detection rate: The positive rates of HPV16/18 and other high-risk genotype were 0.5% and 25% in Arm 1; 0.2% and 24% in Arm 2; 3.1% and 23% in Arm 3. - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR 	Power calculation: NR For all consented participants, Pap-smear and a cervicovaginal self-sample for HPV and Chlamydia trachomatis DNA-testing were obtained at the 1 st and 2 nd screening visits at ages of 22 and 25.

	HPV16/18 vaccination at age 18 (Arm 3; C)		- Sensitivity/Specificity: NR	
NCT02553538 (Percac-Lima et al., 2016)	US 2014 1) PN intervention (I) 2) Usual care (UC; C)	N = 975 I = 479 C = 496 S = NR Mean age NR (21-64 y) 8 m follow-up Population: general population due or overdue for CC screening	Uptake: The trial examined differential uptake amongst all patients overdue for at least one cancer screening The mean cervical cancer screening completion rate was 11.1% in the PN arm compared to 5.7% in the UC arm ($P = 0.002$) in the intention-to-treat analysis. In as-treated analysis, the completion rate was 14.1% in the PN arm compared to 6.2% in the UC arm ($P < 0.001$). Among participants overdue for cervical screening during follow up, the completion rate was higher in the PN group than UC group in both intent-to-treat analysis (14.4% vs 8.6%; 95%CI 1.6-10.5%; $P = 0.007$) and as-treated analysis (18.0% vs 9.3%; 95%CI 3.3-13.7%; $P = 0.001$). Compliance: Not applicable Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- CC/CIN incidence: NR- Detection rate: NR- Stage: NR- CC and all-cause mortality: NR- Sensitivity/Specificity: NR	Power calculation: Y Participants randomized to the PN intervention group were referred to navigators via IT system to track, contact and provide help for screening completion. The type of cervical screening was Papanicolaou and HPV testing.
NTCC (Ronco et al., 2010)	Italy 2002-2004 1) HPV testing with or without	N = 94,370 I = 47,369 (22,708 in Phase 1 and 24,661 in Phase 2) C = 47,001 (22,466 in Phase 1 and 24,535 in Phase 2) S = 92,829* Mean age NR (25-60 y)	Uptake: 94,370 (74%) of 128,026 eligible women were randomised. Compliance: At the baseline, 46,680 women in the intervention arm (99%) and 46,149 women in the control arm (98%) completed the test. The compliance rate between 2-5 years after recruitment was comparable between intervention and control arms (73% vs 70%).	Power calculation: NR The screening was composed of 2 phases: the intervention group received thin-layer cytology and HPV test in Phase 1 whereas the same group received HPV test alone in Phase 2. The control

	<p>thin-layer cytology (I)</p> <p>2) Conventional cytology (C)</p>	<p>Median follow-up 5.1 y</p> <p>Population: eneral population</p> <p>*Baseline testing</p>	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: After 2 rounds of screening, eighteen invasive cancer cases were detected in the conventional cytology group compared to 7 cases in the HPV group ($P = 0.028$). At the end of follow-up, a total of 24 and 7 invasive cell carcinomas were confirmed in the control group and intervention group, respectively. - Detection rate: The relative detection rate of invasive cervical carcinoma was RR 0.37 (95%CI 0.17-0.80) in the intervention group compared to control group. - Stage: Among 24 cases confirmed in the conventional cytology, 11 were > Stage 1A whereas only 1 in 9 cases in the HPV testing was > Stage 1A. - CC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>group received conventional cytology in both Phases.</p> <p>Women with positive HPV results were referred to colposcopy or cytological triage (women aged 25-34 years in Phase 1).</p>
<p>POBASCAM</p> <p>(Dijkstra et al., 2016)</p>	<p>Netherland</p> <p>1999-2002</p> <p>1) HPV+cytology co-testing (I)</p> <p>2) Cytology testing only (C)</p>	<p>N = 44,938</p> <p>I = 22,420</p> <p>C = 22,518</p> <p>S = 43,339</p> <p>Mean age 42.8 y (29-61 y)</p> <p>14 y follow-up</p> <p>Population: general population eligible for 5-yearly screening</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: During the 14-y follow-up, the compliance rate of women who were eligible for both 2nd and 3rd screening rounds was 90.7% in the intervention arm and 90.3% in the control arm. The compliance rate for the 3rd screening round was 84.3% and 84.5% in the intervention and control group, respectively.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: Among women with positive HPV and negative cytology results, the CC incidence was lower in the intervention arm compared to control arm (RR 0.29; 95%CI 0.10-0.87; $P = 0.02$). The CC incidence after 2nd and 3rd screening round was 0.01% and 0.07% among double-negative women in the intervention arm whilst 0.09% and 0.19% among cytology-negative 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>Women in the intervention arm were informed of their HPV and cytology results while women in the control arm only received the cytology result.</p>

			<p>women in the control arm. The CIN3+ incidence after 2nd and 3rd screening round was 0.27% and 0.52% among double-negative women in the intervention arm whilst 0.69% and 1.20% among cytology-negative women in the control arm. The CC incidence after the 3rd screening round was similar among HPV negative and double-negative women in the intervention arm compared with cytology-negative women from the control arm (RR 0.97; 95%CI 0.41-2.31; $P = 0.95$; RR 0.83; 95%CI 0.32-2.15; $P = 0.69$). Higher CC (64.2% higher; $P = 0.32$) yet lower CIN3+ (72.1% lower; $P < 0.001$) incidence was observed among double-negative women aged ≥ 40 years than younger women. Likewise, higher CC (62.0% higher; $P = 0.29$) yet lower CIN3+ (72.2% lower; $P < 0.001$) incidence was observed among HPV negative women aged ≥ 40 years than younger women. There was 11.9 times higher CC incidence among HPV positive women with negative cytology triage compared to HPV negative women (95%CI 3.7-38.1; $P < 0.001$).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
PROTECT-2 (Gök et al., 2012)	Netherland 2007-2008 1) HPV self-sampling group (I)	N = 26,409 I = 26,145 C = 264 S = 7887 Mean age NR (29-63 y) 18 m follow-up	<p>Uptake: Not applicable. All non-attendees to the regular screening programme were included.</p> <p>Compliance: Among participants of HPV self-sampling group, 30.8% returned a self-sampled specimen while only 6.5% of control group responded for the recall of cervical cytology test (chi-square = 71.77; $P < 0.01$). Most women (99.7%) returned</p>	Power calculation: Y

	2) Control group re-invited for regular cytology-based screening (C)	<p>Population: general population eligible but not attending the CC screening programme</p>	<p>specimen valid for HPV test. Around 90% of women with HPV positive results adhered to further workups.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: Among HPV-positive responders, the incidence of CC, CIN3 and CIN2 was 3.6%, 35.4% and 18.2%, respectively, at baseline. Among women underwent colposcopy after 1 year, the incidence of CC, CIN3 and CIN2 was 3.8%, 18.5% and 11.1%, respectively. The cumulative incidence of CIN3+ and CIN2+ within 18-m follow-up of HPV-positive women were 1.0% and 1.5%, respectively. Among the same population, higher incidence of CIN2+/CIN3+ was observed in younger women compared to older women (CIN2+: 2.9% vs 0.8%; $P < 0.01$; CIN3+: 2.0% vs 0.8%; $P < 0.01$). - Detection rate: Among women returned a valid sample for HPV test, the positive rate of high-risk HPV was 8.3%. The positive rate decreased with age: 15.6% in women aged 29-33 years whilst 4.6% in women aged 59-63 years (chi-square for linear trend = 113.14; $P < 0.01$). - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Concordance of physician-taken cervical scrapes vs self-sampling: The concordance between two samplings was high (68.8%; 95%CI 64.7-73.0%). In women diagnosed with CIN2+/CIN3+, the concordance was over 90%. 	
--	--	--	---	--

<p>Swedescreen (Elfström et al., 2014)</p>	<p>Sweden 1997-2000</p> <p>1) HPV & cytology double testing (I)</p> <p>2) Cytology only, with samples frozen for future HPV testing (C)</p>	<p>N = 12,527 I = 6257 C = 6270 S = 12,091</p> <p>Mean age NR (32-38 y)</p> <p>13 y follow-up</p> <p>Population: general population attending organised screening programme</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: Among enrolled participants, 12,091 women completed the baseline cytology and at least one follow-up test (96.5%). No uptake rate was provided specifically in the intervention group or control group.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: In total, 387 women were confirmed with CIN2+ while 230 women were diagnosed with CIN3+ during the 13-year follow-up. The number of CIN2+ cases in the intervention and control arms was 198 and 189, respectively. The CIN3+ cases were 119 in the intervention group compared with 111 in the control group. - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: The sensitivity of cytology in detection CIN2+ was 85.94% in the control group at 3 years while the sensitivity of HPV testing was 86.40% in the intervention group at 5 years. The longitudinal sensitivity of cytology in detecting CIN3+ was 92.02% in the control group at 3 years while HPV showed a sensitivity of 89.34% at 5 years in the intervention group. Higher NPV was observed for HPV testing compared to cytology in terms of CIN2+ and CIN3+ detection. 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>With long-term follow-up, the accumulated cases of CIN2+ became similar between HPV testing and cytology screening, for which the authors suggested that the increased sensitivity of HPV testing might reflect early detection instead of overdiagnosis.</p>
<p>Intervention targeting long-term</p>	<p>Sweden</p>	<p>N = 8000 I₁ = 2000 I₂ = 2000 I₃ = 2000</p>	<p>Uptake: The total uptake rate was 8.2% (658 of 8000). The uptake rate by arm was 18.7% in Arm 1; 10.7% in Arm 2; 1.9% in Arm 3; 1.7% in the routine practice arm as control.</p>	<p><i>Power calculation: Y</i></p>

<p>nonattenders of cervical screening (Elfström et al., 2019)</p>	<p>2016</p> <p>1) HPV self-sampling kit sent directly (Arm 1; I₃)</p> <p>2) Invitation to order an HPV self-sampling kit using new web application (Arm 2; I₂)</p> <p>3) Invitation to consulting a midwife for questions and concerns (Arm 3; I₃)</p> <p>4) Standard annual renewed invitation with pre-booked appointment (routine practice; C)</p>	<p>C = 2000 S = 658</p> <p>Mean age 47.6 (33-60 y)</p> <p>7 m follow-up</p> <p>Population: general population eligible but not attending the CC screening programme in 10 years</p>	<p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC/CIN incidence: Among women tested positive at screening 39.1% were diagnosed with CIN2+ lesions, of which 72% were CIN3+ lesions. - Detection rate: Among women returning HPV self-sampling specimen, 12.2% were positive for high-risk HPV. The corresponding detection rate of CIN2+ per arm was: 4.5% in Arm 1; 2.3% in Arm 2; 5.4% in Arm 3; 2.9% in routine practice control arm. The overall detection rate of CIN2+ was 3.8%. - Stage: NR - CC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: The PPV for CIN2+ per arm was: 47.2% in Arm 1; 22.7% in Arm 2; 50.0% in Arm 3; 100% in routine practice arm, leading to an overall PPV of 39.1%. 	
---	--	--	--	--

Abbreviations and Acronyms

N=Total number in trial; I=in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S=No. screened
Uptake: Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial

	<i>Compliance</i> : Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening
CC	Cervical cancer
CIN	Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia
CHOICE	Cervical HOme-based CancEr screening
CRIS	Cancer Risk Intake System
FDR	First-degree relatives
HC	Hybrid capture
HR	Hazard ratio
HPV	Human papillomavirus
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IT	Information technology
LBC	Liquid-based cytology
LYG	Life-years gained
m	Month
NA	Not applicable
NR	Not reported
NTCC	New Technologies for Cervial Cancer Screening
OHR	Other high risk (HPV genotypes)
OR	Odds ratio
Pap-smear	Papanicolaou cytology
PD	Absolute difference in participation rate
PN	Patient navigation
POBASCAM	Population-based screening study Amsterdam
PPV	Positive predictive value
PROTECT	PRotection by Offering Hpv Testing on Cervicovaginal specimens Trial
QALY	Quality adjusted life years
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
RR	Rate ratio
y	Year

Colorectal cancer

Trial	Trial Details	Participants	Outcomes/Results	Notes
ACCS (Paskett et al., 2020)	US 2013-2017 1) Website intervention plus PN (I) 2) Website intervention control (C)	N = 1043 I = 515 C = 528 S = NA Mean age 51.7 y (25-75 y) 49.6% Male 5 y follow-up Population: adult FDRs of CRC patients	<p>Uptake: A total of 1225 and 1178 eligible FDRs randomised to control and intervention group, respectively, among which 528 (43%) and 515 (44%) were finally enrolled for analysis.</p> <p>Compliance: An overall of 78.6% participants were adherent to the CRC screening recommendation received from the website survey. The ratio was similar between PN and control group (OR 1.27; 95%CI 0.92-1.75; $P = 0.14$). Yet among those receiving recommendation for a colonoscopy, higher adherence was observed in the PN group compared to the control group (52.8% vs 29.8%), leading to an OR of 2.98 (95%CI 1.68-5.28; $P = 0.0002$).</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Barriers to screening: Most participants in the PN group reported no barrier to following the screening adherence (77.7%). The most common barriers reported included: not a priority/too much bother/unwillingness (45.1%); other priorities or health issues (33.3%); not enough time (32.4%); no or controversial recommendation from doctor (24.5%) and not at risk or not necessary (23.5%). 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>This trial was designed to evaluate whether PN intervention would improve the adherence of FDRs of CRC patients to recommended CRC screening.</p> <p>The 1043 FDRs were enrolled across 513 families.</p> <p>The website survey for personal CRC screening recommendation was based on the National Comprehensive Cancer Network guidelines version 2.2012.</p> <p>PN was accessed via telephone to address any individual barriers to adhering to the personal CRC screening recommendation.</p>

<p>ACTRN12609000628 246 (Carey et al., 2016; Reeves et al., 2019)</p>	<p>Australia 2009-2011</p> <p>1) Risk-level tailored advice (I) 2) General information control (C)</p>	<p>N = 574 I = 322 C = 252 S = NA</p> <p>Mean age 51 y (> 18 y) 43.3% Male</p> <p>12 m follow-up</p> <p>Population: adult FDRs of CRC patients</p>	<p>Uptake: Among eligible index cases and FDRs, 752 (25%) and 574 (34%), respectively, consented to participate the trial and completed the baseline interviews.</p> <p>Compliance: The adherence rate to CRC screening guidelines was 61% in the intervention arm compared to 58% in the control arm (mixed effects logistic regression group by time interaction effect = 2.7; 95%CI 1.2-5.9; $P = 0.013$). Another study with extended follow-up revealed the adherence rate of 59% and 52% in the intervention and control arm, respectively, resulting an incremental of 6.6%.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Cost-effectiveness: The QALYs was comparable between two groups (0.82 for intervention; 0.83 for control). From the health care perspective, the ICER was 258 AUD per person appropriately screened while the ICER amounted 275 AUD from the societal perspective. That was about 13% more of cost per person screened for every 15 people receiving screening message. 	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>This trial was designed to evaluate whether the intervention with advice tailored to risk-level would improve the adherence of FDRs of CRC patients to colorectal cancer screening.</p> <p>Screening adherence was assessed at baseline and at 12 months through self-report.</p> <p>The cost-effectiveness was estimated based on the Standard Australian unit cost for 2016/2017.</p>
<p>Blood test of methylated SEPT9 DNA and CRC testing uptake (Liang et al., 2021)</p>	<p>NR NR</p> <p>1) Informed of overdue screening with an additional option of a blood test</p>	<p>N = 359 I = 181 C = 178 S = NA</p> <p>Mean age NR (50- 75 y) % Male NR</p>	<p>Uptake: The uptake rate of CRC screening was 18.2% in the intervention arm (33 of 181; 5 colonoscopy; 17 FIT; 11 blood test) compared to 10.7% in the control arm (19 of 178; 2 colonoscopy; 17 FIT) ($P = 0.04$).</p> <p>Compliance: Taking COVID into consideration for the screening completion rate, 19.9% of intervention participants completed screening compared to 9.6% in the control group ($P = 0.01$).</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>This trial was designed to evaluate whether an additional option of blood test, where positive results obtained, would</p>

	<p>provided colonoscopy or FIT was not preferred (I)</p> <p>2) Informed of overdue screening with colonoscopy or FIT (C)</p>	<p>6 m follow-up</p> <p>Population: screen-eligible Veterans who refused colonoscopy or FIT with the previous 6 m</p>	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: FIT positivity was 8.8% while blood-test positivity was 18.2%. - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>improve the uptake of CRC screening.</p>
<p>COLONPREV (Salas et al., 2014; Urturi et al., 2012)</p>	<p>Spain</p> <p>2009-2011</p> <p>1) One-time colonoscopy (I₁)</p> <p>2) Biennial FIT (I₂)</p>	<p>N = 37,311 I₁ = 19,868 I₂ = 17,443 C = NA S = 14,100</p> <p>Mean age NR (50-69 y)</p> <p>47.9% Male</p> <p>10 y follow-up</p> <p>Population: general</p>	<p>Uptake: Uptake was higher in participants of the FIT arm (34.25%) than the colonoscopy arm (25.38%; $P < 0.001$). In terms of sex, women were more prone to screening uptake than men regardless of the screening type (25.89% vs 24.81% in colonoscopy, $P = 0.045$; 35.31% vs 33.06% in FIT, $P < 0.001$). In terms of age, participants aged 50-59 years were more likely to take up screening than those aged 60-69 years, which was 25.86% vs 24.76% in colonoscopy, $P = 0.042$ and 34.89% vs 33.43% in FIT, $P = 0.013$). The multivariate analysis with two models reported a lower participation rate when invited to colonoscopy than FIT with OR ranging 0.43-0.64.</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: The CRC detection rate was 0.52% with colonoscopy and 0.36% with FIT ($P = 0.002$). The detection rate of advanced adenoma was 9.90% with colonoscopy compared to 2.41% with FIT ($P < 0.001$). Overall, the OR of detecting any neoplasm was 12.06 (95%CI 10.73-13.55) using colonoscopy than FIT. Yet it was less likely to detect any 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>This trial compared two strategies of CRC screening.</p> <p>The crossover between two strategies was allowed. The crossover was mainly from the colonoscopy arm to FIT arm (24.17% vs 1.2%).</p>

			<p>lesion in women aged 50-59 years than men aged 60-69 years (OR 0.33; 95%CI 0.29-0.39).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: The accuracy of FIT was evaluated using different positivity cutoff levels (75, 100, or 125 ng/ml). Whilst the detection rates were similar among 3 different cutoffs in general, the sensitivity of detection in men > 60 years decreased 8.1% in cutoff levels of 100 and 125 ng/ml compared to 75 ng/ml. The sensitivity of detecting advanced adenoma and advanced neoplasms also dropped 7-11% in men of all age with an incremental in the positive cutoff levels. 	
<p>CRIS (Skinner et al., 2015)</p>	<p>US NR</p> <p>1) CRIS + tailored printouts (I₁)</p> <p>2) CRIS + standard information (I₂)</p> <p>3) No contact control (C)</p>	<p>N = 1012 I₁ = 329 I₂ = 322 C = 361 S = NA</p> <p>Mean age 59.0 y (25-75 y)</p> <p>37.1% Male</p> <p>12 m follow-up post-randomisation</p> <p>Population: general; potentially eligible for CRC screening due to family history or personal history of inflammatory bowel</p>	<p>Uptake: The uptake rate of CRC testing was higher in the CRIS-implemented groups compared to no-contact control (47% vs 16%; <i>P</i> < 0.0001). Between the CRIS-implemented groups, higher participation of CRC testing was observed in patients aged > 50 years old with tailored printouts than those receiving standard information (53% vs 44%; <i>P</i> < 0.023).</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>This trial was designed to evaluate the impact of CRIS for patient risk-stratification and tailored communication of information on the participation of any type of colorectal cancer screening.</p>

		disease or adenomatous polyp		
GERA and CRC screening adherence (Myers et al., 2011; Myers et al., 2015; Weinberg et al., 2014)	US NR 1) Usual care (UC; C) 2) Intervention with GERA feedback (GERA; I)	N = 562 I = 369 C = 193 S = NA Mean age NR (50-79 y) 42% Male 6 m follow-up Population: general population eligible for CRC screening yet not taken	Uptake: The uptake of FIT was comparable between UC (35.7%) and GERA (33.1%) group. Compliance: The adjusted OR for screening completion was 0.88 (95%CI 0.64-1.22). No statistically significant was found between GERA participants with various risk levels (OR 0.75 for elevated-risk vs average-risk; 95%CI 0.39-1.42). Multivariate analyses revealed an interaction between race and GERA feedback status in terms of screening adherence ($P = 0.043$), specifically among those at elevated risk where adherence was higher in whites (66.7%) compared to non-whites (33.3%). Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	Power calculation: Y This trial was designed to evaluate the impact of GERA feedback on the uptake and adherence of CRC screening (FIT). The GERA was based on a blood test for polymorphic variants of methylene tetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR) and serum folate level.
NCT02553538 (Percac-Lima et al., 2016)	US 2014 1) PN intervention (I) 2) Usual care (UC; C)	N = 1612 I = 792 C = 820 S = NA Mean age 57 y (50-75 y) 39.5% Male 8 m follow-up Population:	Uptake: The trial examined differential uptake amongst all patients overdue for at least one cancer screening The mean CRC screening completion rate was 7.6% in the PN arm compared to 4.6% in the UC arm ($P = 0.01$) in the intention-to-treat analysis. In as-treated analysis, the completion rate was 9.9% in the PN arm compared to 4.9% in the UC arm ($P < 0.001$). Among participants overdue for CRC screening during follow up, the completion rate was found higher in the PN group than UC group in both intent-to-treat analysis ((13.7% vs 7.0%; 95%CI 3.2-10.4%; $P < 0.001$)) and as-treated analysis (18.1% vs 7.6%; 95%CI 6.3-14.9%; $P < 0.001$). Compliance: Not applicable	Power calculation: Y Participants randomized to the PN intervention group were referred to navigators via IT system to track, contact and provide help for screening completion. The type of CRC screening was not specified.

		general population due or overdue for CRC screening	Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
NCT03819920 (Yen et al., 2021)	US 2015-2018 1) Tailored risk assessment using CCRAT (I) 2) Control with standard education (C)	N = 230 I = 114 C = 116 S = NA Mean age 59.1 y (50-75 y) 41.3% Male 360 days follow-up Population: general population due for CRC screening	Uptake: The behavioural change was assessed using the transtheoretical model. In terms of screening intent, the respective proportion of participants in the pre-contemplative, contemplative and preparation stages were 36.9%, 56.9% and 6.2% in the CCRAT arm compared to 54.0%, 33.3% and 12.7% in the control arm at 12 months ($P = 0.021$). Compliance: In terms of screening completion, the completion rate was 38.6% in the CCRAT arm compared to 44.0% in the control arm (OR 0.80; 95%CI 0.47-1.37; $P = 0.41$). The proportion of test chosen was comparable between two arms: half-half between FIT and colonoscopy in the CCRAT groups while 52.9% and 47.1% of control participants chose FIT and colonoscopy, respectively. Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	Power calculation: Y This trial was designed to evaluate the impact of CCRAT on CRC screening uptake and completion.
Nurse-led tailored intervention and colonoscopy uptake	France 2010-2013	N = 304 I = 160 C = 144 S = NA	Uptake: The uptake rate of colonoscopy was 56.3% in the intervention arm compared to 35.4% in the control arm ($P = 0.0027$). Compliance: After adjustment for those refusing to participate, the rates were 69.2% and 37.0%, respectively ($P < 0.0001$).	Power calculation: Y This trial was designed to evaluate the impact of nurse-

<p>(Ingrand et al., 2016; Ingrand et al., 2019)</p>	<p>1) Tailored leaflets and telephone interview (I) 2) Control with standard information (C)</p>	<p>Mean age 53.5 y (17-75 y) 52% Male 1 y follow-up post diagnosis of the index patients Population: adult FDRs of CRC or CAR patients</p>	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: Among those accepted colonoscopy, one was diagnosed with invasive carcinoma (0.6%) in the intervention group while none in the control group. Higher proportion of advanced adenoma was found in the intervention group than control group (6.9% vs 3.5%; $P = 0.022$). - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>led tailored information on the colonoscopy uptake of FDRs of CRC/CAR patients.</p>
<p>TARGET-C (Chen et al., 2019; H. Chen et al., 2020; H. D. Chen et al., 2020)</p>	<p>China 2018-2019 1) One-time colonoscopy (I₁) 2) Annual FIT for consecutive 4 years (I₂) 3) Annual risk-adapted screening strategy for consecutive 4 years (I₃)</p>	<p>N = 19,582 I₁ = 3937 I₂ = 7858 I₃ = 7787 C = NA S = 19,546 Mean age 60.5 y (50-74 y) 41.7% Male 10 y follow-up Population: general</p>	<p>Uptake: The uptake rates were 42.5% for colonoscopy screening, 94.0% for FIT and 85.2% for risk-adapted screening. Among those assessed to be high-risk of CRC in the risk-adapted group (18.9%, 1472 of 7776), 49.2% accepted colonoscopy screening ($P < 0.05$ compared to 42.5% of colonoscopy group). The uptake was lower in men than in women (48.5% vs 61.0%; OR 0.57; $P = 0.023$). No difference was observed between FIT group and low-risk subjects in the risk-adapted group in terms of FIT uptake (both 94.0%). Compliance: The overall positivity rate of FIT was 14.3%, among which over 85% accepted further diagnostic colonoscopy. Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: The incidence of CRC was 0.23%, 0.09% and 0.17% in colonoscopy, FIT and risk-adapted screening groups, respectively. The diagnostic yield of advanced neoplasms was 2.40% in colonoscopy, 1.13% in FIT and 1.66% in the risk-adapted screening arm, resulting in ORs of 2.16 (Colonoscopy vs FIT; 95%CI 1.61-2.90; $P < 0.0001$), 1.45 (Colonoscopy vs risk-adapted screening; 95%CI 	<p>Power calculation: Y The risk-adapted screening strategy used the Asian-Pacific Colorectal Screening Score where high-risk participants were referred for colonoscopy whilst low-risk participants were referred for FIT. Those with positive FIT results were further referred for diagnostic colonoscopy.</p>

			<p>1.10-1.90; $P = 0.001$), and 1.49 (risk-adapted screening vs FIT; 95%CI 1.13-1.97; $P = 0.004$).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: The detection rate of CRC was better in colonoscopy than FIT (0.54% vs 0.10%; OR 5.11; 95%CI 1.88-14.44; $P = 0.001$). The detection rate of advanced neoplasms was 5.68% in colonoscopy, 1.25% in FIT and 2.00% in the risk-adapted screening arm, resulting in ORs of 4.19 (Colonoscopy vs FIT; 95%CI 3.10-5.66; $P < 0.0001$), 2.38 (Colonoscopy vs risk-adapted screening; 95%CI 1.79-3.14; $P < 0.0001$), and 1.83 (risk-adapted screening vs FIT; 95%CI 1.39-2.42; $P < 0.0001$). - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: Fewer colonoscopies were required to detect one advanced colorectal neoplasm in the FIT (10) and risk-adapted screening (11) compared to the colonoscopy arm (18). - Resource load: For detecting one advanced colorectal neoplasm, 18 subjects need to be screened in the colonoscopy arm; 81 in the FIT arm; 50 in the risk-adapted screening arm. 	
<p>Targeted or tailored intervention on the CRC screening (Lairson et al., 2008)</p>	<p>US NR 1) Usual care control (C)</p>	<p>N = 1546 I₁ = 387 I₂ = 386 I₃ = 386 C = 387 S = NR</p>	<p>Uptake: Compliance: Around 33% participants were screened in the usual care group compared with 46% in the standard intervention group, 44% in the tailored intervention group and 48% in the tailored plus telephone call group.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR 	<p><i>Power calculation: Y</i></p> <p><i>This trial was designed to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of various interventions for promoting CRC screening.</i></p> <p><i>Costs were shown in \$USD.</i></p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR <p>Cost-effectiveness: The cost of SI was \$42 per individual while \$150 for TI. An additional \$50 per individual was incurred in the TIP group, making the total cost of \$200. The ICER was amounted \$319 in SI compared to usual care, which was more effective and dominated TI. The ICER was amounted \$5843 in TIP when compared to SI.</p>	
TeleCARE (Kinney et al., 2014)	US 2009-2011 1) TeleCARE (I) 2) Low-intensity control (C)	N = 481 I = 232 C = 249 S = NA Mean age 50.3 y (30-74 y) 42.6% Male 9 m follow-up post randomisation Population: eligible for CRC screening due to family history	<p>Uptake: In total 79.8% participants completed the risk assessments. The uptake rate of colonoscopy was 35.4% in the TeleCARE group while 15.7% in the control group. The intent-to-treat analysis revealed that TeleCARE participants were more likely to accept screening than the control group (OR 2.83; 95%CI 1.87-4.28; $P < 0.001$).</p> <p>Compliance:</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	Power calculation: Y This trial was designed to evaluate whether intensive, personalised remote intervention (TeleCARE) would influence the uptake of medically verified colonoscopy.
Telephone counseling and colonoscopy adherence (Lowery et al., 2014)	US 2005-2006 1) Tailored telephone counseling intervention (I)	N = 632 I = 322 C = 310 S = NA Mean age NR (25-80 y) 41.3% Male 24 m follow-up	<p>Uptake: In total 328 participants had a colonoscopy during follow-up. The uptake rate of colonoscopy dropped slightly from 52.1% to 49.8% in the mailed group after 24 months. The uptake rate of colonoscopy increased from 43.2% to 54% after 24 months in the group receiving tailored telephone intervention.</p> <p>Compliance: The intent-to-treat analysis revealed that telephone intervention was associated with 24% (unadjusted bivariate analysis; HR 1.24; $P = 0.04$) to 32% (adjusted multivariate analysis; HR 1.32; $P = 0.01$) increase of colonoscopy adherence.</p>	Power calculation: Y This trial was designed to evaluate whether tailored telephone intervention would improve the adherence of high-

	2) Mailed intervention control (C)	Population: Adult FDRs of CRC patients due for colonoscopy within 24 m	Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CRC/advanced neoplasm incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - CRC and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	risk patients to colonoscopy (24 m vs baseline).
--	------------------------------------	---	--	--

Abbreviations and Acronyms	
	N=Total number in trial; I=in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S=No. screened <i>Uptake:</i> Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial <i>Compliance:</i> Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening
ACCS	The Adherence to Colorectal Cancer Screening study
ACRTN	Australian and New Zealand Clinical Trials Registry
CAR	Colorectal adenomatous polyps
CARES	Colorectal Cancer Awareness, Research, Education and Screening
CCRAT	National Cancer Institute's CRC Risk Assessment Tool
CRC	Colorectal cancer
CRIS	Cancer Risk Intake System
FDR	First-degree relatives
FIT	Faecal immunochemical test
FOBT	Faecal occult blood test
GERA	Genetic and environmental risk assessment
HR	Hazard ratio
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IT	Information technology
m	Month
NA	Not applicable
NR	Not reported
OR	Odds ratio

PN	Patient navigation
QALY	Quality adjusted life years
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
RR	Rate ratio
SI	Standard intervention
TeleCARE	Tele-Cancer Risk Assessment and Evaluation
TI	Tailored intervention
TIP	Tailored intervention plus telephone
y	Year

2.2 Bottom line results

Based on data from the 67 papers included in the rapid review (including many randomised controlled trials) some key findings relating to the evidence on efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness may be summarised as follows.

Breast cancer:

Modelling data suggest that risk-adapted strategies can improve benefit-harm ratio with reasonable cost-effectiveness in the European setting (Canelo et al. 2018; Khan et al. 2021; Mühlberger et al. 2021).

Consistent evidence across risk stratification and screen methods showed uptake was typically between 50 and 70%. Compliance/uptake of ultrasound and/or MRI suggests that they are feasible supplementary screening modalities (Bakker et al. 2019; Berg et al. 2012; Constock et al. 2020; Huang et al. 2010; Veenhuizen et al. 2021).

Long-term follow up supports annual mammographic screening in terms of mortality reduction (Bjurstam et al. 2016; Duffy et al. 2020; Miller et al. 2014) with one (controversial) trial noting a slight increase in risk of breast cancer-specific death for women 40–49 years (Narod et al. 2014). Overdiagnosis across screening and risk methods may not be a significant problem for younger European women (Duffy et al. 2020; Gunsoy et al. 2012; Hofvind et al. 2021; Johns et al. 2010; Veenhuizen et al. 2021), particularly women in their mid to late 40s.

Trial data are limited to cancer detection for other screening methods: Annual standard digital mammography ± ultrasound (Huang et al. 2010; Taiwan) ± digital breast tomosynthesis (Pattacini et al. 2018) ± MRI (Acerbi et al. 2021, Bakker et al. 2019) is likely to be feasible, acceptable and effective in high risk 40–49 year-old European women; the age group most studied within randomised controlled trials. The European MyPeBS trial should provide further evidence of the role of MRI and ultrasound in the risk-stratified detection of advanced disease of a whole screening population.

The supplemental value for MRI over mammographic screening alone is between 7 and 16.5 per 1000 women in women with dense breasts (Bakker et al. 2019, Berg et al. 2014, Comstock et al. 2020). MRI was associated with ‘significantly fewer interval cancers’ than mammography alone (Bakker et al. 2019). Modelling studies (Canelo et al. 2018; Khan et al. 2021; Mühlberger et al. 2021) and evidence from the Dense Tissue and Early Breast Neoplasm Screening (DENSE) trial suggest that risk-based strategies are likely to be reasonably cost-effective for high-risk groups. MRI at a four-year interval was most cost effective (€15,620 per QALY) for women with extremely dense breasts (Geuzinge et al. 2021).

Cervical cancer:

Screening with HPV self-sampling increases the screening uptake, especially for under-screened women. Consistent with other RCTs reviewed (Gök et al., 2012; Sancho-Garnier et al., 2013; Tranberg et al., 2018), a meta-analysis pooling data across 33 studies (29 RCTs and 4 observational

studies) reported that HPV self-sampling promoted the screening uptake substantially (RR 2.13; 95% CI 1.89-2.40) compared to the standard care control (Yeh et al. 2019).

In terms of HPV testing as a risk-stratification approach, the long-term follow-up data from Swedescreen trial showed a similar number of CIN2+ cases between HPV testing and conventional cytology screening, which may reflect an early detection function of HPV testing (Elfstrom 2014). A meta-analysis pooling data across 4 RCTs (176,464 women in total) also suggested that HPV-based screening may provide better protection against cervical cancer compared to conventional cytology testing (Ronco et al. 2014).

Screening intervals may be extended for women with negative HPV results and older age (Dijkstra et al., 2016; Gilham et al., 2019).

HPV self-sampling is cost-effective compared to the standard cytology testing (Malone et al., 2020; Sroczynski et al., 2018).

Colorectal cancer:

The majority of the population prefers FIT to colonoscopy in terms of CRC screening uptake, in spite of the higher risk of undiagnosed CRC. The largest RCT in Europe showed that the general population with average risk were more prone to accept biennial FIT than one-time colonoscopy in terms of CRC screening (34.25% vs 25.38%; $P < 0.001$) (Salas et al., 2014; Urturi et al., 2012).

The uptake and compliance across screening methods in general was between 50-60%, which can be improved by several pro-active interventions (Carey et al., 2016; Ingrand et al., 2016; Ingrand et al., 2019;; Kinney et al., 2014; Lairson et al., 2008; Liang et al., 2021; Lowery et al., 2014; Paskett et al., 2020; Percac-Lima et al., 2016; Reeves et al., 2019; Skinner et al., 2015; Yen et al., 2021). Risk-stratification using the Genetic and Environmental Risk Assessment (GERA) did not improve the uptake of CRC screening; however, the GERA feedback might improve screening adherence (Myers et al., 2011; Myers et al., 2015; Weinberg et al., 2014).

In general, the CRC detection rate was higher by means of colonoscopy compared to other screening types (Chen et al., 2019; H. Chen et al., 2020; H. D. Chen et al., 2020; Liang et al., 2021; Salas et al., 2014; Urturi et al., 2012). The largest RCT in Europe showed that the detection rate of any neoplasms using colonoscopy was much higher compared to FIT (OR 12.06; 95%CI 10.73-13.55) (Salas et al., 2014; Urturi et al., 2012). However, a meta-analysis pooling 46 trials and other studies revealed that the specificity of FIT for CRC detection could increase from 69% to 80% when lowering the positivity threshold from $>10-20 \mu\text{g/gto} \leq 10 \mu\text{g/gat}$ the expense of slightly decreased specificity (-3%) (Selby et al., 2019), implying the potential of this more inclusive screening approach.

Two trials undertook a cost-effectiveness analysis but both were outside Europe, and exploring different methods for promoting screening uptake rather than the cost of screening itself (Lairson et al., 2008; Reeves et al., 2019).

3. Discussion

3.1 Summary

This rapid review provides evidence for the efficacy of a number of screening regimens, based on the findings of controlled trials.

Although not within the remit of this review, since the topic relates to vaccination rather than screening, it is noted that HPV vaccination as a strategy is being adopted in almost all EU states (see workshop report, available on SAPEA website).

A key issue in relation to the overall reach and impact of screening programmes in the general population is the overall measure of those willing to participate based on the screening offer. Within this rapid review, data giving the reported uptake (the % of the invited population agreeing to participate in the trial) and compliance rates (the % of the trial population screened and/or adherence to multiple screening rounds) are provided within the Evidence Tables (Section 2.1). Information on compliance only may over-estimate the true proportion likely to take up the screening offer in a real-life situation.

3.2 Strengths and limitations of this Rapid Review

3.2.1 Strengths

This review summarises a valuable sub-set of the evidence base. This review emphasises the findings from recent randomised and other controlled clinical trials, providing the evidence with the least potential for bias. Despite the very short time period available for the review, a very large number of trial reports, and modelling studies based on trials, have been included in the summary.

3.2.2 Limitations

In order to complete the review in a timely fashion a pragmatic and precise search strategy was employed. It is possible that further studies would have been identified should there have been time for a detailed and sensitive systematic search. It is acknowledged that other types of non-trial evidence are relevant to the topic, notably 'real life' screening populations and modelling studies derived from screening cohorts.

The timeline also precluded any statistical or meta-analysis of findings unless these were available from published systematic reviews. No formal critical appraisal was carried out although information is provided on whether the trial included a power calculation. Data extraction and summary were undertaken by different reviewers and, although reviewed by another author, these have not been independently checked for accuracy and consistency.

4. References: Breast cancer

1. Acerbi, I., et al., *Personalized breast cancer screening in a population-based study: women informed to screen depending on measures of risk (WISDOM)*. *Cancer research*, 2021. **81**(4 SUPPL) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1538-7445.SABCS20-OT-21-01>.
2. Anon, *Breast Cancer Screening in the Precision Medicine Era: risk-Based Screening in a Population-Based Trial*. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 2017. **109**(5) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djw290>.
3. Arnold, M., *Simulation modeling for stratified breast cancer screening - a systematic review of cost and quality of life assumptions*. *BMC health services research*, 2017. **17**(1): p. 802 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12913-017-2766-2>.
4. Bakker, M.F., et al., *Supplemental MRI Screening for Women with Extremely Dense Breast Tissue*. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 2019. **381**(22): p. 2091-2102 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1903986>.
5. Berg, W.A., et al., *Detection of breast cancer with addition of annual screening ultrasound or a single screening MRI to mammography in women with elevated breast cancer risk*. *J. Am. Med. Assoc.*, 2012. **307**: p. 1394-1404 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2012.388>.
6. Bjurstam, N.G., L.M. Bjorneld, and S.W. Duffy, *Updated results of the Gothenburg Trial of Mammographic Screening*. *Cancer*, 2016. **122**(12): p. 1832-1835 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cncr.29975>
7. Canelo, C., et al., *Decision Analytic Models to Inform About the Optimal Mammography Screening Intervals: A Systematic Review*. *Value in Health*, 2018. **21**(Supplement 3): p. S378 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2018.09.2249>.
8. Comstock, C.E., et al., *Comparison of Abbreviated Breast MRI vs Digital Breast Tomosynthesis for Breast Cancer Detection Among Women With Dense Breasts Undergoing Screening*. *JAMA*, 2020. **323**(8): p. 746-756 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.0572>.
9. Duffy, S., et al., *Annual mammographic screening to reduce breast cancer mortality in women from age 40 years: long-term follow-up of the UK Age RCT*. *Health technology assessment (Winchester, England)*, 2020. **24**(55): p. 1-24 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3310/hta24550>.
10. Duffy, S.W., et al., *Effect of mammographic screening from age 40 years on breast cancer mortality (UK Age trial): final results of a randomised, controlled trial*. *The lancet. Oncology*, 2020. **21**(9): p. 1165-1172 DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(20\)30398-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(20)30398-3).
11. Geuzinge, H.A., et al., *Cost-Effectiveness of Magnetic Resonance Imaging Screening for Women With Extremely Dense Breast Tissue*. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 2021. **113**(11): p. 1476-1483 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djab119>
12. Gunsoy, N.B., M. Garcia-Closas, and S.M. Moss, *Modelling the overdiagnosis of breast cancer due to mammography screening in women aged 40 to 49 in the United Kingdom*. *Breast cancer research*, 2012. **14**(6): p. R152 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/bcr3365>.

13. Hofvind, S., et al., *Interval and Subsequent Round Breast Cancer in a Randomized Controlled Trial Comparing Digital Breast Tomosynthesis and Digital Mammography Screening*. *Radiology*, 2021. **300**(1): p. 66-76 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2021203936>.
14. Huang, C., et al., *A Population-Based Cross-Over Randomized Controlled Trial of Breast Cancer Screening with Alternate Mammography and Ultrasound for Women Aged 40 to 49 Years in Taiwan*. 2010. **69**(24 Supplement) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/0008-5472.SABCS-09-73>.
15. Ishida, T., et al., *A randomized controlled trial to verify the efficacy of the use of ultrasonography in breast cancer screening aged 40-49 (J-START): 76 196 women registered*. *Japanese journal of clinical oncology*, 2014. **44**(2): p. 134-140 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jjco/hyt199>
16. Johns, L.E. and S.M. Moss, *False-positive results in the randomized controlled trial of mammographic screening from age 40 ("Age" trial)*. *Cancer epidemiology, biomarkers & prevention*, 2010. **19**(11): p. 2758-2764 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-10-0623>.
17. Khan, S.A., et al., *Cost-effectiveness of risk-based breast cancer screening: A systematic review*. *International Journal of Cancer*, 2021. **12**: p. 12 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijc.33593>.
18. Lairson, D.R., et al., *Cost-effectiveness of targeted versus tailored interventions to promote mammography screening among women military veterans in the United States*. *Evaluation and program planning*, 2011. **34**(2): p. 97-104 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2010.07.003>.
19. Miller, A.B. and S.W. Fletcher, *Annual mammography screening did not reduce long-term breast cancer mortality in women 40 to 59 years of age*. *Annals of internal medicine*, 2014. **160**(10): p. JC7 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-160-10-201405200-02007>.
20. Moser, K., et al., *Extending the age range for breast screening in England: pilot study to assess the feasibility and acceptability of randomization*. *Journal of medical screening*, 2011. **18**(2): p. 96-102 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1258/jms.2011.011065>.
21. Moshina, N., et al., *Comparing Screening Outcomes for Digital Breast Tomosynthesis and Digital Mammography by Automated Breast Density in a Randomized Controlled Trial: Results from the To-Be Trial*. *Radiology*, 2020. **297**(3): p. 522-531 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2020201150>.
22. Muhlberger, N., et al., *Cost effectiveness of breast cancer screening and prevention: a systematic review with a focus on risk-adapted strategies*. *European Journal of Health Economics*, 2021. **03**: p. 03 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10198-021-01338-5>.
23. MyPeBS, *Randomized Comparison Of Risk-Stratified versus Standard Breast Cancer Screening In European Women Aged 40–70 (MyPeBS) [No full text identified]*. 2017.
24. Naeim, A., et al., *Participation in a personalized breast cancer screening trial does not increase anxiety at baseline*. *Cancer research*, 2018. **78**(4) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1538-7445.SABCS17-PD2-14>
25. Narod, S.A., et al., *Impact of screening mammography on mortality from breast cancer before age 60 in women 40 to 49 years of age*. *Current oncology (toronto, ont.)*, 2014. **21**(5): p. 217-221 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3747/co.21.2067>

26. Pasyнков, D.V., et al., *Ultrasound breast cancer screening in dense parenchyma: the value of computer aided detection system for mammography (single-center, prospective, randomized clinical trial)*. Russian electronic journal of radiology, 2021. **11**(1): p. 103-113 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21569/2222-7415-2021-11-1-103-113>.
27. Percac-Lima, S., et al., *Patient Navigation for Comprehensive Cancer Screening in High-Risk Patients Using a Population-Based Health Information Technology System: a Randomized Clinical Trial*. JAMA internal medicine, 2016. **176**(7): p. 930-937 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2016.0841>.
29. Saadatmand, S., et al., *Cost-effectiveness of screening with additional MRI for women with familial risk for breast cancer without a genetic predisposition*. European journal of surgical oncology, 2012. **38**(9): p. 761- DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejso.2012.06.092>.
30. Shieh, Y., L. Esserman, and M. Eklund, *Simulated outcomes of personalized versus guideline-based breast cancer screening*. Cancer research, 2019. **79**(4) DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1538-7445.SABCS18-P4-09-03>.
31. Van Ravesteyn, N.T., et al., *Prediction of higher mortality reduction for the UK Breast Screening Frequency Trial: a model-based approach on screening intervals*. British journal of cancer, 2011. **105**(7): p. 1082-1088 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/bjc.2011.300>.
32. Veenhuizen, S.G.A., et al., *Supplemental Breast MRI for Women with Extremely Dense Breasts: Results of the Second Screening Round of the DENSE Trial*. Radiology, 2021. **299**(2): p. 278-286 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2021203633>
33. Yuan, W.H., *Supplemental breast cancer-screening ultrasonography in women with dense breasts: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. 2020 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41416-020-0928-1>.

5. References: Cervical cancer

1. Canfell, K., et al., *Cervical screening with primary HPV testing or cytology in a population of women in which those aged 33 years or younger had previously been offered HPV vaccination: results of the Compass pilot randomised trial*. PLoS medicine, 2017. **14**(9): p. e1002388 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002388>.
2. Dijkstra, M.G., et al., *Safety of extending screening intervals beyond five years in cervical screening programmes with testing for high risk human papillomavirus: 14 year follow-up of population based randomised cohort in the Netherlands*. BMJ (Clinical research ed.), 2016. **355**: p. i4924 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i4924>.
3. Elfström, K.M., et al., *Long term duration of protective effect for HPV negative women: follow-up of primary HPV screening randomised controlled trial*. BMJ, 2014. **348** DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g130>
4. Elfström, K.M., et al., *Increasing participation in cervical screening by targeting long-term nonattenders: randomized health services study*. International journal of cancer, 2019. **145**(11): p. 3033-3039 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijc.32374>.
5. Gilham, C., et al., *HPV testing compared with routine cytology in cervical screening: long-term follow-up of ARTISTIC RCT*. Health

- Technology Assessment (Winchester, England), 2019. **23**(28): p. 1-44.
6. Gök, M., et al., *Experience with high-risk human papillomavirus testing on vaginal brush-based self-samples of non-attendees of the cervical screening program*. International journal of cancer, 2012. **130**(5): p. 1128-1135 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijc.26128>.
 7. Louvanto, K., et al., *Baseline findings and safety of infrequent vs. frequent screening of human papillomavirus vaccinated women*. International Journal of Cancer, 2020. **147**(2): p. 440-447 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijc.32802>.
 8. Malone, C., et al., *Cost-effectiveness studies of HPV self-sampling: A systematic review*. Preventive Medicine, 2020. **132**: p. 105953 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2019.105953>.
 9. Percac-Lima, S., et al., *Patient Navigation for Comprehensive Cancer Screening in High-Risk Patients Using a Population-Based Health Information Technology System: a Randomized Clinical Trial*. JAMA internal medicine, 2016. **176**(7): p. 930-937 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2016.0841>.
 10. Ronco, G., et al., *Efficacy of HPV-based screening for prevention of invasive cervical cancer: follow-up of four European randomised controlled trials*. The Lancet, 2014. **383**(9916): p. 524-532 DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62218-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62218-7).
 11. Ronco, G., et al., *Efficacy of human papillomavirus testing for the detection of invasive cervical cancers and cervical intraepithelial neoplasia: a randomised controlled trial*. Lancet oncology, 2010. **11**(3): p. 249-257 DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(09\)70360-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(09)70360-2).
 12. Sancho-Garnier, H., et al., *HPV self-sampling or the Pap-smear: a randomized study among cervical screening nonattenders from lower socioeconomic groups in France*. International journal of cancer, 2013. **133**(11): p. 2681-2687 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijc.28283>.
 13. Sroczyński, G., et al., *Cervical Cancer Screening in Europe - a Systematic Review on Cost Effectiveness Studies with Specific Interest on Risk-Adapted Strategies*. Value in Health, 2018. **21**(Supplement 3): p. S257 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2018.09.1532>.
 14. Tranberg, M., et al., *Hpv self-sampling in cervical cancer screening: the effect of different invitation strategies in various socioeconomic groups – a randomized controlled trial*. Clinical epidemiology, 2018. **10**: p. 1027-1036 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2147/CLEP.S164826>.
 15. Yeh, P.T., et al., *Self-sampling for human papillomavirus (HPV) testing: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. BMJ Global Health 2019. **4**:e001351 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2018-001351>

6. References: Colorectal cancer

1. Carey, M., et al., *Can a print-based intervention increase screening for first degree relatives of people with colorectal cancer? A randomised controlled trial*. Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health, 2016. **40**: p. 582-587 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1753-6405.12579>
2. Chen, H., et al., *Comparative evaluation of colonoscopy, fecal immunochemical test, and a novel risk-adapted approach for colorectal cancer screening: preliminary baseline results of a multicentre randomised*

- controlled trial (Target-C)*. *Lancet*, 2019. **394**: p. S35- DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)32371-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)32371-2)
3. Chen, H., et al., *Comparative Evaluation of Participation and Diagnostic Yield of Colonoscopy vs Fecal Immunochemical Test vs Risk-Adapted Screening in Colorectal Cancer Screening: interim Analysis of a Multicenter Randomized Controlled Trial (TARGET-C)*. *American journal of gastroenterology*, 2020. **115**(8): p. 1264-1274 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14309/ajg.0000000000000624>
 4. Chen, H.D., et al., *Rates on the acceptance of colonoscopy, fecal immunochemical test and a novel risk-adapted screening approach in the screening programs of colorectal cancer as well as related associated factors*. *Zhonghua liu xing bing xue za zhi*, 2020. **41**(10): p. 1655-1661 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3760/cma.j.cn112338-20200227-00196>
 5. Ingrand, I., et al., *Colonoscopy uptake for high-risk individuals with a family history of colorectal neoplasia: a multicenter, randomized trial of tailored counseling versus standard information*. *Medicine*, 2016. **95**(33): p. e4303 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000004303>
 7. Ingrand, I., et al., *Family risk information for colorectal cancer. Perspectives on the effectiveness of a tailored intervention*. *Sante publique (Vandoeuvre-les-Nancy, France)*, 2019. **S2**(HS2): p. 79-89 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3917/spub.197.0079>
 8. Kinney, A.Y., et al., *Telehealth personalized cancer risk communication to motivate colonoscopy in relatives of patients with colorectal cancer: the family CARE Randomized controlled trial*. *Journal of clinical oncology*, 2014. **32**(7): p. 654-662 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2013.51.6765>
 10. Lairson, D.R., et al., *Cost-effectiveness of targeted and tailored interventions on colorectal cancer screening use*. *Cancer*, 2008. **112**(4): p. 779-788 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/cncr.23232>
 11. Liang, P.S., et al., *ID: 3523488 BLOOD TEST INCREASES COLORECTAL CANCER SCREENING UPTAKE IN INDIVIDUALS WHO HAVE DECLINED COLONOSCOPY AND FECAL IMMUNOCHEMICAL TESTING: a RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL*. *Gastrointestinal endoscopy*, 2021. **93**(6): p. AB100-AB101 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gie.2021.03.254>
 12. Lowery, J.T., et al., *A randomized trial to increase colonoscopy screening in members of high-risk families in the colorectal cancer family registry and cancer genetics network*. *Cancer epidemiology, biomarkers & prevention*, 2014. **23**(4): p. 601-610 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-13-1085>
 13. McGeoch, L., et al., *Risk Prediction Models for Colorectal Cancer Incorporating Common Genetic Variants: A Systematic Review*. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention*, 2019. **28**(10): p. 1580-1593 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-19-0059>
 14. Myers, R.E., et al., *A randomized trial of genetic and environmental risk assessment (GERA) for colorectal cancer risk in primary care: trial design and baseline findings*. *Contemporary clinical trials*, 2011. **32**(1): p. 25-31 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cct.2010.08.013>
 15. Myers, R.E., et al., *Effects of genetic and environmental risk assessment feedback on colorectal cancer screening adherence*. *Journal of behavioral medicine*, 2015. **38**(5): p. 777-786 DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)32371-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)32371-2)

- <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10865-015-9626-5>
16. Paskett, E.D., et al., *Comparative Effectiveness of Two Interventions to Increase Colorectal Cancer Screening for Those at Increased Risk Based on Family History: results of a Randomized Trial*. *Cancer epidemiology, biomarkers & prevention*, 2020. **29**(1): p. 3-9 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-19-0797>
 17. Percac-Lima, S., et al., *Patient Navigation for Comprehensive Cancer Screening in High-Risk Patients Using a Population-Based Health Information Technology System: a Randomized Clinical Trial*. *JAMA internal medicine*, 2016. **176**(7): p. 930-937 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2016.0841>
 18. Reeves, P., et al., *Costs and Cost-Effectiveness of Targeted, Personalized Risk Information to Increase Appropriate Screening by First-Degree Relatives of People With Colorectal Cancer*. *Health education & behavior*, 2019. **46**(5): p. 798-808 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1090198119835294>
 21. Salas, D., et al., *Participation and detection rates by age and sex for colonoscopy versus fecal immunochemical testing in colorectal cancer screening*. *Cancer causes & control*, 2014. **25**(8): p. 985-997 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10552-014-0398-y>
 22. Selby, K., et al., *Effect of Sex, Age, and Positivity Threshold on Fecal Immunochemical Test Accuracy: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis*. *Gastroenterology*, 2019. **157**(6): p. 1494-1505 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2019.08.023>
 24. Skinner, C.S., et al., *Impact of Risk Assessment and Tailored versus Nontailored Risk Information on Colorectal Cancer Testing in Primary Care: a Randomized Controlled Trial*. *Cancer epidemiology, biomarkers & prevention*, 2015. **24**(10): p. 1523-1530 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-15-0122>
 25. Urturi, C.A., et al., *Should faecal immunochemical test (FIT) positivity cutoff be sex and-age specific in colorectal cancer (CRC) screening?* *Gastroenterology*, 2012. **142**(5): p. S774- DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0016-5085\(12\)63000-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0016-5085(12)63000-5)
 26. Weinberg, D.S., et al., *Genetic and environmental risk assessment and colorectal cancer screening in an average-risk population: a randomized trial*. *Annals of internal medicine*, 2014. **161**(8): p. 537-545 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7326/M14-0765>
 27. Yen, T., et al., *Randomized Controlled Trial of Personalized Colorectal Cancer Risk Assessment vs Education to Promote Screening Uptake*. *American journal of gastroenterology*, 2021. **116**(2): p. 391-400 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14309/ajg.000000000000963>

7. Rapid review method

7.1 Eligibility criteria

- Randomised controlled trial (RCT), controlled clinical trial³, or modelling study based on trial data
- All interventions including: targeting specific populations (by risk factors including age, gender, ethnicity/race and other socio-demographic differences); interval & interval by age comparisons; screening method comparisons
- Published during or after 2007
- Screening for first diagnosis of breast, cervical or colorectal cancer
- Inclusion of data on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost-effectiveness relating to targeting screening uptake and screening methods
- All locations, all languages but to emphasise the findings from EU studies within the narrative write up

7.2 Literature search strategy

Searches were carried out for publications from 2016 onwards using title and Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) searches of the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CCTR). This includes trial data from Medline, Embase and the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP). Supplementary searching of Medline, Embase and the ICTRP was carried out for publications in 2021 that may not yet have been included in the CCTR.

To ensure coverage of trial reports back to 2007, Cochrane Reviews, Health Technology Assessment and the US Preventive Services Taskforce (USPSTF) was searched for systematic reviews on the topics. These were then examined for relevant trial reports.

Text word terms: [breast OR cervi* OR colorectal OR colon OR bowel] *in Record Title* AND [cancer* OR neoplasm*] *in Record Title* AND [screen* OR “early detection”] *in Record Title*

OR

MeSH terms: (exp⁴ breast neoplasms OR uterine cervical neoplasms OR exp colorectal neoplasms) AND (early detection of cancer)

AND

(stratif* OR target* OR pre-select* OR risk assess* OR risk based OR risk adapted OR genetic* OR age OR gender OR socio* OR demographic* OR race OR ethnic* OR interval OR subsequent round OR inform* OR personali*) *in Record Title*

In Medline using above terms [AND randomized controlled trial.pt OR controlled clinical trial.pt OR pragmatic clinical trial.pt OR systematic review.m+titl]; In Embase using above terms [AND exp controlled clinical trial/ OR systematic review.m+titl].

³ Quasi-randomised and other controlled trials where randomisation is not explicit, but cannot be ruled out

⁴ The exp (explode) function directs the selection of all papers tagged with this heading and any more specific sub-headings.

Additional search methods: Relevant systematic reviews published since 2016 were examined for additional trials. Some studies identified in early scoping searches for the topic and as suggested by the scientific writers were added that met the review inclusion criteria. The screened results were provided to the co-chairs of the Expert Workshop who were asked to liaise with workshop attendees and the workshop report was scrutinised to note any additional studies meeting the inclusion criteria.

7.3 Resources list

Clinical trials.gov

Cochrane Library [Cochrane Reviews/Cochrane Central Register of Controlled trials]

Health Technology Assessment

Embase

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

Medline

US Preventive Services Taskforce (USPSTF)

7.4 Study selection process

Results from the literature searches were imported into EndNote 20, where duplicates were removed. Titles and abstracts were screened for inclusion followed by full text screening. Both screening stages were undertaken by a team of reviewers according to the eligibility criteria in Section 5.1. Identified systematic reviews were examined for trials dating back to 2007.

7.5 Study selection flow chart

7.6 Data extraction

Data from main trial report(s) on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost effectiveness were extracted into a summary table for each cancer by a single reviewer (Section 2.1).

7.7 Quality appraisal

Each included study was identified as RCT or controlled clinical trial (CCT) according to the study design as provided in the database(s) within the evidence table (Section 2.1) along with a note as to whether a power calculation was included as part of the trial. No other formal critical appraisal was carried out.

7.8 Synthesis

The findings are summarised in a narrative report, drawing from the summary tables with brief findings based on the consensus from the included studies.

8. Additional information

8.1 Conflicts of interest

None

8.2 Acknowledgements

This template is based, with permission, on the rapid review template used within the Palliative Care Evidence Review Service ([PaCERS](#)) and the [Welsh Covid 19 Evidence Centre](#).

9. About the review team

The [Specialist Unit for Review Evidence \(SURE\)](#) is a team of experienced systematic reviewers and information specialists at Cardiff University who conduct all forms of systematic and other evidence reviews, and teach evidence review methods. The team work across all topic areas and also specialise in health and social care. Staff have carried out a number of reviews for SAPEA, working closely with Academia Europaea and experienced reviewers within the University's Library Service. Reviews are carried out in close collaboration with subject specialists for each review topic. For these rapid reviews the subject specialists are Dr Hui-Ling Ou (Cambridge University) and Dr Nicholas Courtier (Cardiff University).

SAPEA is part of the European Commission's Scientific Advice Mechanism, which provides independent, interdisciplinary, and evidence-based scientific advice on policy issues to the European Commission.

SAPEA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 737432.

www.sapea.info
@SAPEAnews

Cancer screening in Europe

Rapid review 3

What is the evidence from recent trials and reviews for the efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness of new technologies in cancer screening and early diagnosis?

To download the latest version of this document, together with the full Evidence Review Report that it informed, please visit:

www.sapea.info/cancerscreening

SAPEA

Science Advice for Policy by European Academies

The text of this work is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution licence which permits unrestricted use, provided the original author and source are credited. The licence is available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>. Images reproduced from other publications are not covered by this licence and remain the property of their respective owners, whose licence terms may be different. Every effort has been made to secure permission for reproduction of copyright material. The usage of images reproduced from other publications has not been reviewed by the copyright owners prior to release, and therefore those owners are not responsible for any errors, omissions or inaccuracies, or for any consequences arising from the use or misuse of this document.

This document has been produced by the SAPEA consortium. The information, facts and opinions set out in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The SAPEA Consortium is not responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained in this report by anyone, including the European Union institutions and bodies or any person acting on their behalf.

- DOI: -forthcoming
- Downloadable from <https://www.sapea.info/cancer-screening/>

Version history

Version	Date	Summary of changes
1.0	2 March 2022	First published version

Publisher

SAPEA
c/o acatech
Pariser Platz 4a
10117 Berlin, Germany

Contact

SAPEA Communications Office
Rue d'Egmont 13
1000 Brussels, Belgium
contact@sapea.info

Rapid Review 3

What is the evidence from recent trials and reviews for the efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness of new technologies in cancer screening and early diagnosis?

Rapid Review Details

Review conducted by:

A team led by the Specialist Unit for Review Evidence (SURE) for SAPEA (Science Advice for Policy by European Academies)

Review Team:

- Dr Hui-Ling Ou, Research Associate, Cambridge Centre Lung Cancer Early Detection Group, University of Cambridge, UK
- Dr Nicholas Courtier, Senior Lecturer Radiography, School of Healthcare Sciences, Cardiff University, UK
- Dr Alison Weightman, Director Specialist Unit for Review Evidence, Cardiff University, UK
- Louise Edwards, Hub Manager, Academia Europaea, Cardiff University, UK

Method:

This is one of three rapid reviews - a lighter form of a full systematic review that takes account of time constraints. The top-line results are included in the main SAPEA Evidence Review Report, with cross-referencing between the documents.

The review summarises a valuable subset of the evidence base, emphasising the findings from recent randomised and other controlled clinical trials. This review includes diagnostic accuracy studies carried out within controlled trials published since 2017, supplemented with data from published systematic reviews of case-control and diagnostic accuracy studies. To meet deadlines, a pragmatic and precise search strategy was employed; it is possible that further controlled trials would have been identified if there had been time for a detailed and sensitive systematic search. The timeline also precluded any statistical or meta-analysis of findings unless these were available from published systematic reviews. No formal critical appraisal was carried out although information is provided on whether the trial included a power calculation. Data extraction and summary were undertaken by different reviewers and, although reviewed by another author, these have not been independently checked for accuracy and consistency.

Acknowledgements:

The advisory group for the review team, comprising the Chairs of the Expert Workshop, Professor Ole Petersen (Academia Europaea), members of SAPEA, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (Advisors) and the SAM Unit. Professor Adrian Edwards (Professor of General Practice, Cardiff University) and Professor Jacek Jassem (Head, Department of Oncology & Radiotherapy, Medical University of Gdańsk) for reviewing and commenting on the draft pre-publication.

Disclaimer: The authors of this work declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

‘What is the evidence from recent trials and reviews for the efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness of new technologies in cancer screening and early diagnosis?’

TOPLINE SUMMARY

Who is this summary for?

To support the work of SAPEA in providing evidence to the European Commission’s Group of Chief Scientific Advisors on cancer screening in Europe.

Background

This review is one of three rapid reviews conducted on the topic of cancer screening in Europe. It was produced specifically for the expert workshop convened to discuss the main scientific elements to consider, and best practices to promote, for optimising risk-based cancer screening and early diagnosis throughout the EU. This final version has been revised to address feedback received on earlier drafts and supplements the workshop report (available on the SAPEA website).

Aim

To examine the published evidence base for the question: ‘What is the evidence from recent trials for the efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness of new technologies in cancer screening and early diagnosis?’.

Rapid review method

A literature search was conducted in October 2021 for diagnostic accuracy studies carried out within controlled trials published since 2017, supplemented with data from published systematic reviews of case-control and diagnostic accuracy studies. Trials and systematic reviews were included if they examined new technologies (including artificial intelligence [AI], imaging and biomarkers) in screening for first diagnosis of any cancer, and included data on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost-effectiveness.

Key findings

Biomarkers [11 studies within trials and 11 systematic reviews of diagnostic studies]:

- Biomarker panels show better specificity in cancer detection than single markers.
- Biomarkers not only facilitate cancer detection, but also enhance detection of pre-cancerous lesions, e.g., Cytosponge®-TFF3 and saliva cytokines.
- Across various cancer types, the biomarkers for colorectal cancer screening are the most intensively studied, including genomic, epigenetic and protein markers detected in blood, stool, urine and tissue.

Imaging and artificial intelligence [8 studies within trials and 1 systematic review of diagnostic studies]:

- Novel image-enhanced endoscopy can improve early detection of upper GI-tract lesions in high-risk populations.
- There is small-scale evidence for superiority of blue light imaging in bright mode over linked colour imaging in detection of colorectal adenomas but this requires confirmation.

- Retrospective evidence, and lack of prospective evidence, suggest that current AI is not sufficiently specific to replace double radiologist reading in breast screening programmes.

Strength of evidence

The evidence is derived from studies embedded within controlled clinical trials and systematic reviews of case-control or diagnostic test accuracy studies.

Full report

Table of Contents

1. Background.....	5
1.1 Purpose of this review	5
1.2 Research question	5
2. Results	5
2.1 Summary of the evidence base	5
Biomarkers.....	6
2.1 Summary of the evidence base [table]	9
2.2 Bottom line results	40
3. Discussion	41
3.1 Summary	41
3.2 Strengths and limitations of this Rapid Review.....	41
3.2.1 Strengths	41
3.2.2 Limitations.....	41
4. References:.....	42
5. Rapid review method	45
5.1 Eligibility criteria.....	45
6.2 Literature search strategy.....	45
6.3 Resources list	46
6.4 Study selection process	46
5.5 Study selection flow chart.....	47
5.6 Data extraction.....	47
5.7 Quality appraisal.....	47
5.8 Synthesis	47
6. Additional information	47
6.1 Conflicts of interest	47
6.2 Acknowledgements	48
7. About the review team	48

1. Background

This Rapid Review is one of three reviews being conducted to support the work of Expert Groups convened to assist the European Commission Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM) in developing policy guidance in relation to cancer screening. As described in the Scoping Paper¹, this review supports the third of the Expert Group workshops convened to discuss the question **“Which are the main scientific elements to consider, and best practices to promote, for optimising risk-based cancer screening and early diagnosis throughout the EU?”**

An advisory group was formed to provide guidance to the review team, comprising the Chairs, Professor Ole Petersen (Academia Europaea), members of SAPEA, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors and the SAM Unit.

1.1 Purpose of this review

Following detailed discussions with the advisory group, the specific question for the rapid review to inform the third workshop was:

“What is the evidence from recent controlled trials for the efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness of new technologies in cancer screening and early diagnosis?”

Following completion of the search, it was subsequently agreed to include published systematic reviews of case-control and test-accuracy studies, given the large amount of evidence summarised within these reviews.

1.2 Research question

Rapid Review Question
What is the evidence from recent controlled trials, and systematic reviews of case-control and test accuracy studies, for the efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness of new technologies in cancer screening and early diagnosis?

2. Results

2.1 Summary of the evidence base

In all, 19 studies included within trials and 12 systematic reviews of case control/diagnostic accuracy studies have been summarised. We provide a narrative overview of the identified evidence below under two headings:

- Biomarkers

¹ Scientific Advice Mechanism. European Commission’s Group of Chief Scientific Advisors. [Scoping Paper: Cancer Screening](#). 22 April 2021

- Imaging & Artificial Intelligence

A summary of each included study is provided in Section 2.2.

Biomarkers

Data from 11 trial reports and 11 systematic reviews (of case control/diagnostic accuracy studies) were included. Information from studies within individual trials or systematic reviews of multiple case-control or diagnostic accuracy studies were extracted and summarised in the Table (Section 2.2). Most studies focused on identifying biomarkers for cancer early diagnosis using liquid biopsies, which can be further divided into protein biomarkers, epigenetic biomarkers, DNA (circulating tumour DNA and mitochondrial DNA) and extracellular RNAs.

Specific protein or antibody biomarkers have been reported useful for discriminating between cancer patients and cancer-free controls. Some markers are specific for cancer type, e.g., serum IDH1 level for non-small cell lung cancer (Sun et al., 2020) and pepsinogen for digestive tract cancers (In et al., 2021; Kunzmann et al., 2018), whilst some markers are mutually shared among different cancers, e.g., p53 antibody for lung and colorectal cancer (Harlid et al., 2021; Sullivan et al., 2021). In addition to cancer detection, a particular biomarker - TFF3 used together with a special specimen collection device - Cytosponge® has shown promising effect on early diagnosis of Barrett's oesophagus, which is the pre-cancerous lesion of oesophageal adenocarcinoma (Fitzgerald, di Pietro, O'Donovan, Maroni, et al., 2020; Fitzgerald, Di Pietro, O'Donovan, Muldrew, et al., 2020; Swart et al., 2021). To mitigate invasive procedures during screening, levels of several cytokines in saliva could be of good use for risk stratification in oral cancer screening (Chiamulera et al., 2021).

Plasma DNA and the methylation frequency are also widely studied across different cancer types, including breast (Sturgeon et al., 2017; Sturgeon et al., 2021), colorectal (Anghel et al., 2021), lung (Hubers et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2017) and melanoma (Guo et al., 2019). Specifically, the methylation status of the adenomatous polyposis coli (APC) promoter has been shown correlated with higher risk of gastric cancer, based on a meta-analysis pooling data from 8 RCTs. Higher incidence of APC was observed in tissues and blood of patients with gastric cancer (OR 3.86; 95%CI 1.71-8.74; $P = 0.001$) compared with patients without (Zhou et al., 2020). In general, a biomarker panel demonstrated higher specificity for cancer detection than single marker. Similar to protein biomarkers, methylation levels of specific genes were shared among different cancer types, which may be used for general cancer screening.

Several studies also evaluated the efficiency of extracellular RNAs such as miRNA, lncRNA or circular RNA in screening of colorectal, gastric, oesophageal, lung and ovarian cancer (Chu et al., 2018; Hulstaert et al., 2021; Saheb Sharif-Askari et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2020). One miRNA family, miR-21, was found associated with worse overall survival of colorectal cancer (Saheb Sharif-Askari et al., 2020). Panels of miRNA rendered better sensitivity and specificity in detecting lung and ovarian cancer (Chu et al., 2018; Hulstaert et al., 2021).

One study reported the efficiency of DNA quantitative cytology in detecting endometrial cancer (Yang et al., 2019). In terms of kidney cell carcinoma, a recent meta-analysis across 6 RCTs revealed that liquid biomarkers, e.g., miRNAs, proteins and metabolites in urine or plasma, might not be

ready for clinical integration of cancer diagnosis, for which more validation is required (Campi et al., 2021).

As far as the invasiveness is concerned, urinary biopsy is among the least invasive diagnostic tools. One recent systematic review pooled results across 13 RCTs and assessed the quality of using urinary volatile organic compounds (VOCs) for cancer early detection. Despite distinctive VOC profiles in different cancer types (prostate cancer, gastrointestinal cancer, leukaemia/lymphoma, lung cancer and bladder cancer) and promising performance, inconsistencies across RCTs undermine the application of such method to broader populations (Wen et al., 2020).

In summary, there is consistency across various studies embedded in trials, in relation to biomarkers, but the small size of validation groups and heterogeneity of population included per trial may limit the extrapolation of results. Biomarker panels tend to show better specificity in cancer detection than single markers. (Anghel et al. 2021; Carozzi et al. 2017 a/b; Chu et al. 2018; Hulstaert et al. 2021; Tarney et al. 2019).

Two studies reported cost-effectiveness of biomarkers in cancer screening in very different settings. Sullivan et al (2020) found that the cost per stage I/II lung cancer detected using the autoantibody test within EarlyCDT after 2 years was £116,000. In relation to Cytosponge use for Barrett's oesophagus, an additional 0.015 QALYs per patients was generated with the Cytosponge®-TFF3 screening, rendering an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of £5500 per QALY gained (Fitzgerald, di Pietro, O'Donovan, Maroni, et al., 2020; Fitzgerald, Di Pietro, O'Donovan, Muldrew, et al., 2020; Swart et al., 2021).

Imaging and artificial intelligence

Seven studies of novel imaging technologies were identified. Five RCTs focused on early detection of gastrointestinal cancers (Dohi et al. 2019; Gao et al., 2021; Gruner et al. 2021; Ferreira et al. 2021; Yoshida et al. 2021), one on improved discrimination/management of skin malignancy (Ferrándiz et al. 2017), and a modelling study that sought to personalise lung cancer risk in a large-scale RCT-derived cohort (Hostetter et al. 2017). All study populations were of average to high risk for the target cancer. Two populations were European (Ferrándiz et al. 2017; Gruner et al. 2021). A further, single arm trial, is also summarised in the text (Chauvie et al. 2020).

One systematic review of AI image analysis in breast cancer screening was included, drawing together the evidence from 12 test accuracy studies (Freeman et al. 2021).

GI tract cancers: Overall, improved **detection efficacy** for early gastric and oesophageal lesions was demonstrated for image-enhanced endoscopy using magnification plus narrow-band imaging (NBI) or laser light techniques – light linked colour imaging (LCI) or blue laser imaging (BLI) in bright mode – compared to standard white light imaging (WLI). Evidence for the upper GI tract sites is moderate to high based on consistency of RCT results. **Mortality** and **cost-effectiveness** outcomes were not reported.

Gastric cancer: The largest trial (Yoshida et al. 2021) reported comparable detection rates for second generation NBI versus WLI but with slightly improved positive predictive value for NBI, suggesting potential to reduce false-positive results. Smaller RCTs found BLI-bright (Dohi et al. 2019) and LCI (Gao et al. 2021) had significantly improved detection rate compared to WLI (across disease stage and histology).

Oesophageal cancer: A French RCT (Gruner et al. 2021) found NBI was more specific (80% vs 66%) and sensitive (38% vs 21%) than Lugol chromoendoscopy for the detection of squamous cancers. Supplemental NBI imaging could improve the detection of early neoplasia.

Colorectal cancer: A small Brazilian study (Ferreira et al. 2020) reported a significantly higher adenoma detection rate for LCI (68%) versus both WLI (56%) and BLI-bright (56%); including a superior flat-lesion detection rate.

Skin malignancy: The addition of tele-dermoscopic images to standard clinical images improved the accuracy index (correct decisions percentage) for suspicious skin lesions from 79.2% to 94.3% (Ferrándiz et al. 2017). This higher accuracy made tele-dermoscopy the dominant strategy, with a significantly lower cost-effectiveness ratio.

Lung cancer: Incorporating three clinically-accessible personalised data points – smoking history, sex, nodule location – to an established non-personalised risk model enabled improved malignancy risk predictions and follow-up recommendations to be made (Hostetter et al. 2017).

Another trial, Chauvie et al (2020), reported that AI may facilitate conventional screening but this was a single arm trial (the SOS study) so it does not strictly meet the criteria for inclusion in this review.

The **systematic review** (Freeman et al. 2021) tested accuracy of standalone AI algorithms or AI-assisted radiologists to detect breast cancer in digital mammogram screening or test sets. Cancer type (e.g. grade, stage, prognosis) was the secondary outcome. Twelve studies totalling 131,822 screened women included eight with European data. All studies measuring test accuracy of AI in screening practice were either retrospective or enriched laboratory test set studies. Low methodological quality according to the QUADAS-2 tool related to concerns about risk of bias and applicability to the clinical context of included studies.

In a retrospective evaluation including 79,910 women, 34/36 (94%) AI systems were less accurate than a single radiologist's original decision; all were less accurate than consensus of two or more radiologists. Five smaller studies (1086 women, 520 cancers) at high risk of bias and low applicability evaluated AI systems as more accurate than a single radiologist reading a test set. In three studies, AI used for triage screened out 53%, 45%, and 50% of women at low risk but also 10%, 4%, and 0% of cancers detected by radiologists.

2.1 Summary of the evidence base [table]

2.1.1 Biomarkers

Technologies	Trial- (Cancer type)	Trial Details	Participants	Outcomes/Results	Notes
Biomarker-protein (Sun et al., 2020)	Serum IDH1 level for early diagnosis of NSCLC	China NR 1) Training cohort (620) 2) Validation cohort (546)	N = 1223 Mean age NR (17-86 y) 48.9% Male Follow-up NR Population: selected subjects with NSCLC or benign pulmonary conditions (BPCs), or other cancers (OC), or good health (healthy control, HC)	Uptake: NR Compliance: NR Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs IDH1 level: In general, the serum IDH1 levels were higher in the NSCLC patients (6.13 ± 4.80 ng/ml) compared to other participants (BPC+OC+HC, 1.90 ± 2.81 ng/ml; $P < 0.001$). When compared specifically with patients with other cancers, the IDH1 level was still higher in NSCLC patients (2.29 ± 3.71 ng/ml vs 6.13 ± 4.80 ng/ml; $P < 0.001$). No difference was observed between healthy control and patients with other cancers in terms of IDH1 serum levels. - Detection rate: NR - Stage: Using the IDH1 cut off at 5 ng/ml, the specificity for discriminating between early-stage (Stage 0-IA) NSCLC patients and other participants (BPC+OC+HC) in the training cohort was 86.8% with sensitivity of 58.6%. The 	Power calculation: NR The serum level of IDH1 was determined using ELISA. The model used for training was not specified.

				<p>PPV was estimated 79.3% and NPV was 70.9%. Likewise in the validating cohort, the specificity was 86.3% with sensitivity of 59.1% for discriminating between early-stage NSCLC patients and other participants (BPC+OC+HC). The corresponding PPV was 53.4% and NPV 88.8%.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: When the IDH1 cut off was set at 5 ng/ml, the specificity was 92.9% with sensitivity of 63.3% for discriminating between NSCLC patients and healthy subjects in the training cohort. The PPV was estimated 95.4% and NPV was 52.0% Using the same settings, the specificity was 89.3% with sensitivity of 55.0% for discriminating between NSCLC patients and healthy subjects in the validating cohort. The corresponding PPV was 92.7% and NPV 44.6%. - Model performance: The AUC of IDH1 values was 0.915 and 0.730 for NSCLC diagnosis in the training and validation cohorts, respectively. When it came to disease stage, the AUC was 0.859 and 0.797 for diagnosing early-stage NSCLC in the training and validation cohorts, respectively. 	
<p>Biomarker-protein (Kazarian et al., 2017)</p>	<p>Serum levels of CA15-3, HSP90A and PAI-1 as early diagnosis/pr</p>	<p>UK 2001-2014 1) UKCTOCS participants who</p>	<p>N = 478 Mean age 61 (50-76 y) Median to diagnosis 13.8 m (up to 5 y)</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: NR Outcomes:</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR The serum level of all biomarkers was measured using ELISA.</p>

	Diagnostic markers for BC	<p>developed breast cancer (239)</p> <p>2) Matched cancer-free control (239)</p>	<p>Population: post-menopausal women with BC or matched controls in the UKCTOCS trial</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs biomarker levels: No biomarker candidates, either alone or in combination, were accurate markers for BC prediction. - Detection rate: NR - Stage: In relation to clinic-pathological predictions, CA15-3 levels were found raised in samples from late-stage (Stage 3/4) BC patients compared to cancer-free control ($P = 0.0215$). Yet CA15-3 levels were lower in grade 1 BC cases than control ($P = 0.0254$). Serum levels of PAI-1 were significantly lower in patients diagnosed with grade 3 cancer compared to control ($P = 0.0491$). Likewise, HSP90A levels were lower in grade 3 BC cases than cancer-free control ($P = 0.0174$). - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Model performance: The logistic regression model combining all markers for NPI-based prognosis estimated an AUC of 0.77, considering samples taken within 1.15 y of diagnosis. 	<p>This was a nested study within the UKCTOCS trial.</p>
<p>Biomarker-protein (Fitzgerald, di Pietro, O'Donovan, Maroni, et al., 2020; Fitzgerald, Di</p>	<p>BEST3 Cytosponge® combined with TFF3 for early diagnosis of BE, the pre-</p>	<p>UK</p> <p>2017-2019</p> <p>1) Usual care control group (6531)</p> <p>2) Usual care + offer of</p>	<p>N = 13,514</p> <p>I = 6983</p> <p>C = 6531</p> <p>S = 1654</p> <p>Median age 69 y</p> <p>48% Male (among participants taking Cytosponge®)</p>	<p>Uptake: Among participants randomised to the intervention group, 39% (2679 of 6983) expressed interest of taking the Cytosponge®-TFF3 procedure, 65% (1750 of 2679) of which met the eligibility criteria and received the procedure</p> <p>Compliance: 95% (1654 of 1750) eligible participants successfully swallowed the Cytosponge® for sample production (overall uptake 24%).</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y</p> <p>An endoscopy was offered when TFF3-positive cells were identified in the intervention group or upon advised by general</p>

<p>Pietro, O'Donovan, Muldrew, et al., 2020; Swart et al., 2021)</p>	<p>cancerous lesion of EAC</p>	<p>Cytosponge®-TFF3 procedure (6983)</p>	<p>Mean follow-up 12 m</p> <p>Population: Patients with long-term symptoms of gastro-oesophageal reflux and received treatment for > 6 m</p>	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer/BE incidence: Within the follow-up period, 2% (140 of 6834) participants in the intervention group vs <1% (13 of 6388) in the control group were diagnosed with BE (RR 10.6, 95%CI 6.0-18.8; $P < 0.0001$). Nine cases with early-stage neoplasia were diagnosed in the intervention group compared to none in the control group. - Detection rate: Among participants taking the Cytosponge®-TFF3 procedure, 13% (221 of 1654) underwent endoscopy due to positive TFF3 results, 59% of which (131 of 221) were diagnosed with BE or EAC. - Stage: Among 9 cases of neoplasia diagnosed in the intervention group, 4 were dysplastic BE while 5 were stage-I oesophago-gastric cancer. - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: The specificity of the Cytosponge®-TFF3 procedure for detection of BE, dysplasia, or cancer was estimated 94%. - Cost-effectiveness: Compared with usual care, the one-off Cytosponge®-TFF3 screening together with incurred treatment and palliative care for identified BE/EAC led to an incremental of 82 per patient with gastro-oesophageal reflux. An additional 0.015 QALYs per patients was generated with the Cytosponge®-TFF3 screening, rendering an ICER of £5500 per QALY gained. The probabilistic sensitivity analysis revealed an incremental cost of £78 and 0.015 QALYs for Cytosponge®-TFF3 	<p>practitioners in the control group.</p>
---	---------------------------------------	--	--	---	--

				<p>screening compared to usual care, giving an ICER of £5405 (95%CI -6791 to 17,600). Considering the willingness-to-pay threshold at £20,000 per QALY, there was a high probability of Cytosponge®-TFF3 being cost-effective than usual care (97%). The total budget impact was also evaluated using the additional cost-per-patient of £82 for one round of Cytosponge®-TFF3 screening, which would cost a total of £21,636,235 spreading over 29 years at an annual cost of £746,077 in the UK settings.</p>	
<p>Biomarker-antibody (Sullivan et al., 2021)</p>	<p>ECLS Early CDT-Lung test for predicting LC risk</p>	<p>UK 2013-2016 1) Usual care control group (6121) 2) EarlyCDT-Lung test + LDCT 6-monthly if test-positive (6087)</p>	<p>N = 12,208 I = 6087 C = 6121 S = NR Mean age 60.5 (50-75 y) 51% Male Mean follow-up 24 m Population: former or current smokers^b or smokers^a with immediate family history of LC</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: Over 2-year follow-up, the adherence rate to protocol was 89.9%. Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence: The incidence of LC was 520 per 100,000 per annum (0.52%). A total of 56 cases of LC were confirmed in the intervention group (0.92%) whilst 71 cases in the control group (1.16%) within 2 years. - Detection rate: Among intervention participants, 9.8% (598 of 6087) were tested positive with EarlyCDT-Lung test and 3.0% (18 of 598) were diagnosed with LC. For those who tested negative, 38 were diagnosed with LC (0.7%). On average, LC patients were diagnosed 87.3 days earlier in the intervention group than control group. - Stage: The LC cases of stage III/IV/unspecified were 0.5% (33 of 6087) in the intervention group compared to 0.8% (52 of 6121) in the control group, resulting in a HR of 0.64 	<p>Power calculation: Y EarlyCDT-Lung test is a ELISA-based assay, measuring levels of seven autoantibodies in blood samples. The autoantibodies tested include p53, NY-ESO-1, CAGE, GBU4-5, HuD, MAGE A4 and SOX2.</p>

				<p>(95%CI 0.41-0.99; $P = 0.0432$). An estimation of 325 patients was to be screened to prevent one LC case of stage III/IV/unspecified.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer and all-cause mortality: No statistically significant difference was observed in terms of LC mortality (0.39% vs 0.28%) or all-cause mortality (1.76% vs 1.43%) between control and intervention arm. - Sensitivity/Specificity: The sensitivity of Early CDT-Lung test was 52.2% for detecting stage I/II disease and 18.2% for detecting stage III/IV disease. The corresponding specificity was 90.3% and 90.2%, respectively. The PPV was estimated 2.0% for stage I/II disease and 1.0% for stage III/IV disease while the corresponding NPV was 99.8% for the former and 99.5% for the latter. - Cost-effectiveness: The cost per stage I/II LC detected after 2 years was £116,000. 	
<p>Biomarker-protein (Tarney et al., 2019)</p>	<p>Biomarker panel for early detection of endometrial cancer</p>	<p>US 1993-2001 1) Endometrial cancer cases (112) 2) Cancer-free matched control (NR)</p>	<p>N = NR Mean age NR Median follow-up 17 y (as PLCO) Population: postmenopausal women with endometrial cancer or matched controls in PLCO trial</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: NR Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: Forty seven proteins were found abundant differentially between cancer cases and matched controls ($P < 0.05$). The integrated risk score of 	<p>Power calculation: NR This was a nested study in the PLCO trial, where cases of endometrial cancer were matched with control for quantitative proteomics and phosphoproteomics of pre-diagnostic serum.</p>

				<p>6 proteins including complement factor B, serotransferrin, catalase, proteasome subunit beta type-6, beta-2-microglobulin, and protocadherin-18 were found directly associated with cancer incidence.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model performance: The AUC of the integrated biomarker panel for distinguishing cancer case and control was 0.80 (95%CI 0.72-0.88). 	
<p>Biomarker-protein (In et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Serum pepsinogen as a biomarker for GC</p>	<p>US 1993-2001 1) Gastric cancer cases (105: 70 non-cardia and 35 cardia) 2) Cancer-free matched controls (220)</p>	<p>N = 325 Mean age NR Median follow-up 17 y (as PLCO) Population: GC cases and matched controls in PLCO trial</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: NR Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence: NR - Detection rate: Higher PG+ rate was observed in GC patients compared to controls (31.4% vs 5.5%; $P < 0.001$). The risk of GC was significantly higher in PG+ than PG- participants, leading to a HR of 3.77 (95%CI 2.50-5.71; adjusted HR 4.42; 95%CI 3.14-6.21). Among sub-cohort of non-cardia GC, PG+ demonstrated an increased risk of GC compared to PG- (HR 5.65; 95%CI 3.67-8.70; adjusted HR 7.26; 95%CI 4.84-10.90). Yet such trend was not found in the cardia GC sub-cohort (HR 1.79; 95%CI 0.72-4.44; adjusted HR 1.95; 95%CI 0.81-5.37). - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR This was a nested study in the PLCO trial, where serum samples of GC cases were compared with those of control in terms of PG level using ELISA. HR was adjusted for family history of GC, smoking and BMI.</p>

<p>Biomarker - protein (Chiamulera et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Systematic review - Salivary cytokines as biomarkers for oral cancer</p>	<p>Multiple countries 2004-2018 28 case-control studies included</p>	<p>N = 18-300 Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified</p>	<p>Uptake: Not applicable Compliance: Not applicable Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs salivary cytokine: Compared with healthy controls, levels of specific salivary cytokines were significantly different in oral cancer patients: IL-8 (SMD 1.77; 95%CI 0.79-1.55), IL-6 (SMD 2.08; 95%CI 1.33-2.84), TNF-a (SMD 2.04; 95%CI 0.47-3.61), IL-1b (SMD 0.78 95%CI 0.44-1.13), IL-10 (SMD 0.46; 95%CI 0.05-0.86), IL-1a (SMD 2.21; 95%CI -0.36-4.77). - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR Only studies using ELISA for measuring salivary cytokines were included. The frequency of salivary cytokines examined were IL-8 (50%), IL-6 (50%), TNF-a (28.6%), IL-1b (21.4%), IL-10 (17.9%), IL-1a (10.7%), and IL-1, IL-1RA, IL-4 and IL-13 (3.6% each).</p>
<p>Biomarker - protein (Aalami et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Systematic review – Urinary angiogenin as biomarkers for bladder cancer</p>	<p>Egypt/USA 2004-2014 4 case-control studies included</p>	<p>N = 656* Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified *Pooled from all 4 RCTs</p>	<p>Uptake: Not applicable Compliance: Not applicable Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs urinary angiogenin: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR All included studies used ELISA for measuring urinary angiogenin levels despite varied cut-off.</p>

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitivity/Specificity: The analysis of pooled studies revealed a sensitivity of 0.71 (95%CI 0.60-0.75), specificity of 0.78 (95%CI 0.73-0.81), positive likelihood ratio of 3.34 (95%CI 2.02-5.53), negative likelihood ratio of 0.37 (95%CI 0.32-0.44), diagnostic odds ratio of 9.99 (95%CI 4.69-21.28) and AUC of 0.789. 	
<p>Biomarker-DNA (F. Carozzi et al., 2017; F. M. Carozzi et al., 2017)</p>	<p>ITALUNG Biomarker Panel (IBP) for LC detection</p>	<p>Italy 2004-2006 1) Lung cancer cases (36) 2) Cancer-free matched controls (481)</p>	<p>N = 517 Mean age 61.1 y 60.2% Male Follow-up 4 y Population: LC cases and matched controls in ITALUNG trial</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: Of 1,406 screened, 1,356 (96%) consented to give a sample of blood and sputum at baseline. Random selection then made of 517 samples.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence: Among 36 LC cases enrolled, 18 were detected at the baseline LDCT screening and another 18 detected at annual repeat LDCT. - Detection rate: Among 517 subjected screened, 146 were LDCT positive. The IBP positive rate among LC cases was 94.4% (17 of 18) and 66.7% (12 of 18) at baseline and repeat screening, respectively. - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: Based on the data of this cohort, the specificity of LDCT alone was 74% while IBP alone was 59%. The combination of both led to an improved specificity of 90% and PPV of 26%. A simulation was carried out to extrapolate the findings and found the sensitivity being the same (90%) for either approach 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>ITALUNG biomarker study was aimed to evaluate the efficiency of combining molecular markers and LDCT as a screening approach.</p> <p>Plasma DNA was quantified with real-time PCR while blood and sputum samples were subjected to assessment of MSI and LOH.</p>

				<p>alone at baseline with lower specificity for IBP (61% vs 71% for LDCT). The PPV was comparable, 4.3% for LDCT vs 3.3% for IBP. In terms of multimodal approach where LDCT was combined with IBP for screening, the specificity was improved to 89% as well as the PPV (10.6%) with unchanged sensitivity (90%). The probability of LC confirmation under circumstances of LDCT negative and IBP positive was estimated 3.4% throughout the whole screening cycle.</p>	
<p>Biomarker - DNA methylation (Zhou et al., 2020)</p>	<p>Systematic review – Methylation status of the APC promoter and GC risk</p>	<p>Multiple countries 2003-2015 8 case-control studies included</p>	<p>N = 985* Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified *Pooled from all 8 RCTs</p>	<p>Uptake: Not applicable Compliance: Not applicable Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs methylation of the APC promoter: Higher methylation of APC promoter was observed in patients with GC compared to patients without GC (OR 3.86; 95%CI 1.71-8.74; $P = 0.001$). - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR Tissues or blood specimen from patients were used for assessing the methylation status of APC promoter.</p>
<p>Biomarker - DNA methylation</p>	<p>DNA hypermethylation of biomarkers for LC</p>	<p>The Netherlands and Belgium 2003-2006</p>	<p>N = 284 Mean age NR % Male NR</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: Sputum was collected from 1,548 (20%) of 7,915 subjects in the LDCT screening arm. Samples then identified for analysis.</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR The DNA hypermethylation of the following biomarkers in</p>

<p>(Hubers et al., 2017)</p>	<p>detection in the NELSON trial</p>	<p>1) Lung cancer cases (65)</p> <p>2) Cancer-free controls with minor cytological aberrations (120)</p> <p>3) Cancer-free controls without cytological aberrations (99)</p>	<p>Follow-up 80 m</p> <p>Population: LC cases and matched controls in NELSON trial</p>	<p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: The DNA hypermethylation of RASSF1A may be useful for detecting invasive LC in a screening interval of 2 years with specificity of 93% (95%CI 89-96%) and sensitivity of 17% (95%CI 4-31%). Within 2-year interval, the biomarker panel consisting of RASSF1A, 3OST2 and PRDM14 could detect 28% of LC cases with specificity of 90% (95%CI 86-94%). 	<p>the sputum samples were examined: RASSF1A, APC, cytoglobin, 3OST2, FAM19A4, PHACTR3 and PRDM14. The cut-off values were determined for high specificity of diagnostic value assessment per biomarker.</p>
<p>Biomarker - DNA methylation (Sturgeon et al., 2021)</p>	<p>DNA methylation in WBC as biomarker for BC - CpG sites</p>	<p>US</p> <p>1993-2001</p> <p>1) Breast cancer cases (297)</p> <p>2) Cancer-free matched controls (297)</p>	<p>N = 594</p> <p>Mean age NR (55-74 y)</p> <p>Follow-up 17 y (as PLCO)</p> <p>Population: BC cases and matched controls in the intervention arm of PLCO trial</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: Overall 97% of participants provided two serial WBC DNA samples for analysis. On average, proximate samples were taken 1.82 years before diagnosis whilst distant samples were taken 5.7 years prior to diagnosis.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs CpG sites: One percentage increase in <i>ERCC1</i> CpG site in proximate WBC DNA samples was associated with increased BC risk (adjusted OR 1.29; 95%CI 1.06-1.57), but an inversely association was 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>This was a nested study in the PLCO trial, where blood samples of BC cases were compared with those of control in terms of CpG sites using targeted bisulphite amplification sequencing.</p>

				<p>observed in distant WBC DNA samples (adjusted OR 0.83; 95%CI 0.69-0.98).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
<p>Biomarker - DNA methylation (Sturgeon et al., 2017)</p>	<p>DNA methylation in WBC as biomarker for BC - %5-mdC</p>	<p>US 1997-2005 1) Invasive breast cancer cases (428) 2) Cancer-free matched controls (419)</p>	<p>N = 847 Mean age NR (55-74 y) Follow-up 17 y (as PLCO) Population: BC cases and matched controls in the intervention arm of PLCO trial</p>	<p>Uptake: NR Compliance: NR Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs %5mdc levels: No correlation was observed between DNA methylation in WBC samples and breast cancer risk. - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR This was a nested study in the PLCO trial, (Etiology and Early Marker Study, EEMS) where blood samples of BC cases were compared with those of control in terms of ratio of 5-mdC to dG using liquid chromatography-electrospray ionization-tandem mass spectrometry.</p>
<p>Biomarker - DNA methylation (Guo et al., 2019)</p>	<p>Systematic review - Promoter methylation as biomarkers for</p>	<p>Multiple countries NR</p>	<p>N = 7-206 Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified</p>	<p>Uptake: Not applicable Compliance: Not applicable Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs promoter methylation: Among 50 genes reported across 33 studies, hypermethylation of 	<p>Power calculation: NR In total the promoter methylation of 50 genes were reported in studies included.</p>

	melanoma diagnosis	33 case-control studies included		<p>the following genes were found higher in melanoma patients than in cancer-free controls: CLDN11 (OR 16.82; 95%CI 1.97-143.29; $P = 0.010$, MGMT (OR 5.59; 95%CI 2.51-12.47; $P < 0.0001$), p16 (OR 6.57; 95%CI 2.19-19.75; $P = 0.0008$), RAR-b2 (OR 24.31; 95%CI 4.58-129.01; $P = 0.0002$) and RASSF1A (OR 9.35; 95%CI 4.73-18.45; $P < 0.00001$).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: NR - Stage: In terms of disease stage, hypermethylation of CLDN11 (OR 14.52; 95%CI 1.84-114.55; $P = 0.01$), MGMT (OR 8.08; 95%CI 1.84-35.46; $P = 0.006$), p16 (OR 9.44; 95%CI 2.68-33.29; $P = 0.0005$) and RASSF1A (OR 7.72; 95%CI 1.05-56.50; $P = 0.04$) were found increased in primary melanoma compared with controls. When it comes to metastasis melanoma, the methylation frequency of CLDN11 (OR 25.56; 95%CI 2.32-281.66; $P = 0.008$), MGMT (OR 4.64; 95%CI 1.98-10.90; $P = 0.0004$), p16 (OR 4.31; 95%CI 1.33-13.96; $P = 0.01$) and RASSF1A (OR 10.10; 95%CI 2.87-35.54; $P = 0.0003$) was significantly higher in patients compared with controls. - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	
Biomarker - DNA methylation (Anghel et al., 2021)	Systematic review - Promoter methylation as biomarkers	Multiple countries NR 74 diagnostic accuracy	N = NR Mean age NR Follow-up NR	<p>Uptake: Not applicable</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs promoter methylation: NR 	Power calculation: NR Currently approved epigenetic tests for CRC screening are: ColoGuard® (US), Epi

	for CRC early detection	studies included	Population: not specified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: DNA methylation of SDC2 was estimated to have a sensitivity of 83.3-91.3% for detecting stage I/II disease and 89.6-100% for detecting stage III/IV disease. The SEPT9 methylation assessment processed 100% sensitivity for stage I disease when use in combination with FOBT. A gene panel capable of testing methylation of SDC2 and SEPT9 demonstrated a sensitivity of 69.1-81.8% for stage I disease, 85.7%-100% for stage II disease, 88.9-89.7% for stage III disease and 75-100% for stage IV disease. Though not yet approved, another panel testing 5 CTCF binding sites showed 93.54% sensitivity and 94.05% specificity for CRC detection. 	<p>proColon® (US), EarlyTect®-Colon Cancer (Korea) and Colosafe® (China).</p> <p>ColoGuard® is the first FDA-approved stool CRC screening kit, testing methylation level of NDRG4 and BMP3 as well as mutations of KRAS and β-actin. Epi proColon is the first FDA-approved blood-based screening kit, testing the methylation of SEPT9.</p> <p>SDC2 and SEPT9 were the most frequently assessed epigenetic markers for CRC detection</p>
Biomarker - extracellular RNA (miRNA, lncRNA, or circular RNA)	Systematic review - RNA biomarkers in biofluids for early diagnosis of	Multiple countries NR	N = 50-3079 Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified	<p>Uptake: Not applicable</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>The studies included were mostly focusing on blood-derived fluids (34 of 26). Only one study looked into urine while</p>

<p>(Hulstaert et al., 2021)</p>	<p>ovarian cancer</p>	<p>36 case-control studies included</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs RNA biomarkers: Higher levels of miR-21, the miR-200 family, miR-205, miR-10a and miR-346 were observed in biofluids of cancer patients compared to controls. In contrast, levels of miR-122, miR-193a, miR-223, miR-126 and miR-106b were lower. - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Model performance: The best RNA biomarkers reported had AUCs ranged between 0.694 to 1. The best performing model with validation was a panel consisting of 10 miRNAs (miR-320a, miR-665, miR-3184-5p, miR-6717-5p, miR-4459, miR-6076, miR-3195, miR-1275, miR-3185 and miR-4640-5p), with an AUC of 1, sensitivity of 0.99 and specificity of 1. The second-best performing model consisted of 4 miRNAs (miR-7, miR-429, miR-25 and miR-93) with an AUC of 0.98, sensitivity of 0.93 and specificity of 0.92. 	<p>another checked ascites.</p> <p>The method categories across included studies were reverse transcription quantitative PCR, microarray and RNA-sequencing.</p>
<p>Biomarker - extracellular RNA (miRNA, lncRNA, or circular RNA) (Yu et al., 2020)</p>	<p>Systematic review - lncRNA as biomarkers for early diagnosis of digestive tract cancer</p>	<p>Multiple countries NR 69 diagnostic accuracy studies included (40 in</p>	<p>N = NR Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified</p>	<p>Uptake: Not applicable</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs RNA biomarkers: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>The specimens included blood, tissue and, for GC, also gastric juice.</p>

		GC; 24 in CRC; 5 in EC)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: In general, the sensitivity and specificity of lncRNA in screening digestive track cancer was 0.78 and 0.80, respectively. The corresponding rate for cancer type was: 0.77 (95%CI 0.72-0.81) and 0.75 (95%CI 0.71-0.79) for GC; 0.82 (95%CI 0.76-0.86) and 0.84 (95%CI 0.79-0.88) for CRC; 0.74 (95%CI 0.67-0.80) and 0.86 (95%CI 0.72-0.93) for EC. - Model performance: The overall AUC of lncRNA in screening digestive track cancer was 0.86. In terms of each cancer type, the AUC was 0.83 for GC; 0.90 for CRC; 0.82 for EC. 	
Biomarker - extracellular RNA (miRNA, lncRNA, or circular RNA) (Chu et al., 2018)	Systematic review - miRNA signature classifier (MSC) as biomarkers for LC detection in MILD trial	Italy 2005-2011 939 plasma samples (69 from LC patients)	N = 939 Mean age NR (≥ 50 y) Follow-up 5 y Population: former ^d or current ^b smokers	<p>Uptake: Not applicable</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs RNA biomarkers: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: A total of 19 patients died due to LC and no participants died because of other cause during the follow-up. For LC mortality, MSC demonstrated a sensitivity of 95% (95%CI NR), specificity of 78% (95%CI 75-80%), PPV of 8% (95%CI 5-12%) and NPV of 99% (95%CI NR). - Sensitivity/Specificity: For LC detection, MSC demonstrated a sensitivity of 87% (95%CI NR), specificity 	Power calculation: NR MSC is a plasma-based miRNA panel including 24 miRNAs, based on which patients are categorized into low, intermediate, or high risk of LC.

				of 81% (95%CI 79-84%), PPV of 27% (95%CI 21-32%) and NPV of 98% (95%CI NR).	
Biomarker - extracellular RNA (miRNA, lncRNA, or circular RNA) (Chu et al., 2018)	Systematic review - miR-test as biomarkers for LC detection in COSMOS trial	Italy 2004-2005 1008 serum samples (36 from LC patients)	N = 1008 Mean age NR (> 50 y) Follow-up NR Population: Current ^b or former smokers	Uptake: Not applicable Compliance: Not applicable Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs RNA biomarkers: NR - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: Three patients died of LC during the follow-up. No all-cause mortality analysis was provided. For LC mortality, miR-test demonstrated a sensitivity of 100% (95%CI NR), specificity of 73% (95%CI 70-76%), PPV of 1.1% (95%CI NR) and NPV of 100% (95%CI NR). - Sensitivity/Specificity: For LC detection, miR-test demonstrated a sensitivity of 78% (95%CI NR), specificity of 75% (95%CI 72-78%), PPV of 10% (95%CI 7-14%) and NPV of 98% (95%CI NR). 	Power calculation: NR MiR-test is a serum-based miRNA panel including 13 miRNAs, including miR-92a-3p, miR-30b-5p, miR-191-5p, miR-484, miR-328-3p, miR-30c-5p, miR-374-5p, let-7d-5p, miR-331-3p, miR-29a-3p, miR-148a-3p, miR-223-3p and miR-140-5p.
Biomarker - extracellular RNA (miRNA, lncRNA, or circular RNA)	Systematic review - miRNA-21 as biomarkers for detecting colorectal	Multiple countries NR 11 studies included	N = 2139* Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified	Uptake: Not applicable Compliance: Not applicable Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs RNA biomarkers: NR - Detection rate: NR 	Power calculation: NR The specimens included tissue (12 out of 14 cohorts) and serum.

<p>(Saheb Sharif-Askari et al., 2020)</p>	<p>adenocarcinoma</p>		<p>*Pooled from all 11 RCTs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR - Survival: The meta-analysis revealed that high level of miR-21 was associated with worse overall survival (HR 1.75; 95%CI 1.23-2.51; $P = 0.001$). Despite a trend between miR-21 overexpression and disease-free survival, it was not statistically significant (HR 1.21; 95%CI 0.91-1.60; $P = 0.19$). 	
<p>Biomarker - liquid biopsies (Campi et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Systematic review – Novel liquid biomarkers and renal cell carcinoma</p>	<p>Multiple countries 2016-2019 6 case-control studies included</p>	<p>N = NA Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified</p>	<p>Uptake: Not applicable</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs liquid biomarkers: Inconclusive - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: NR 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>Liquid biopsies including urine, plasma and serum was utilised for assessing the extracellular RNAs or metabolites.</p>
<p>Others (Yang et al., 2019)</p>	<p>DNA quantitative cytology for detection of endometrial cancer</p>	<p>China 2013-2017 1) Non-menopausal women (NR)</p>	<p>N = 575 Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: general female population</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: NR</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer/pre-cancerous lesion incidence: Among 575 women enrolled, 47 endometrial cancer cases were 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>All participants went through endometrial DNA quantitative cytology tests and hysteroscope plus dilation and curettage.</p>

		2) Menopausal women (NR)		<p>confirmed, 30 were diagnosed with atypical hyperplasia, 382 were with benign lesion and 116 were normal.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: The accuracy of DNA quantitative cytology for diagnosing endometrial cancer was 85.57%, with a sensitivity of 87.01%, specificity of 85.34%, false negative rate of 12.99%, false positive rate of 14.66%, PPV of 47.86% and NPV of 97.07%. In terms of detection in menopausal women, the accuracy of DNA quantitative cytology was 89.95%, with a sensitivity of 97.73%, specificity of 87.59%, false negative rate of 2.27%, false positive rate of 12.41%, PPV of 70.49% and NPV of 99.22%. For detection in non-menopausal women, the accuracy of DNA quantitative cytology was 83.42%, with a sensitivity of 72.73%, specificity of 84.42%, false negative rate of 27.27%, false positive rate of 15.58%, PPV of 30.38% and NPV of 97.07%. 	This study was aimed to compare the efficiency of DNA quantitative analysis with the clinical histopathological results in terms of endometrial cancer detection.
Others (Wen et al., 2021)	Systematic review – Urinary volatile organic compound (VOC) analysis for	Multiple countries 1999-2019 13 case-control studies across 5	N = 1266* of which 700 were diagnosed with cancer Mean age NR Follow-up NR Population: not specified	<p>Uptake: Not applicable</p> <p>Compliance: Not applicable</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence vs VOC contents: In total, 48 urinary VOCs belonging to 11 chemical classes were found associated with cancers. Twenty-nine urinary VOCs were identified for PC, most of which decreased in the urine of 	Power calculation: NR Across 13 studies, 10 studies analysed the urinary samples with gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS); 3 used selected ion flow tube mass

	cancer diagnosis	cancer types included	*Pooled from all 13 RCTs	<p>cancer patients compared to non-cancer patients. Distinct set of VOCs were identified for GCs with 19 out of the 21 cancer-associated VOCs different from those of PC, most of which increased in cancer patient compared to non-cancer patients. For leukaemia/lymphoma, 6 VOCs were found mostly increased in the urine of patients except for anisole. In the case of bladder cancer, formaldehydes were reported as VOCs associated with the malignancy whilst no urinary VOC was found associated specifically with LC.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detection rate: NR - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: Within included studies, VOCs associated with PC and GCs demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity for cancer detection. 	<p>spectrometry (SIFT-MS); a single study used field asymmetric ion mobility spectrometry (FAIMS). Nine out of 13 studies analysed VOCs within the headspace instead of the fluid phase of urine.</p>
--	-------------------------	-----------------------	--------------------------	--	--

^a < 20 pack-y

^b ≥ 20 pack-y

^c > 2 h-day for at least 10 y

^d ≤ 10 y since quitting

^e Quit after age 50 and < 10 y since quitting

^f ≥ 20 pack-y in the last 10 y or quit < 10 y

^g ≥ 30 pack-y

^h 15 cigarettes/d for ≥ 25 y or 10 cigarettes/d for ≥ 30 y

ⁱ 15 cigarettes/d for >25 y or 10 cigarettes/d for > 30 y

^j ≥ 15 cigarettes/d for ≥ 20 y

Abbreviations and acronyms	
	<i>Uptake</i> : Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial <i>Compliance</i> : Percentage of trial population providing samples for analysis N=Total number in trial; I=in intervention group(s); C= in control group; S=No. screened
5-mdC	5-methyl-2' deoxycytidine
AI	Artificial intelligence
APC	Adenomatous polyposis coli
AUC	Area under the curve
BC	Breast cancer
BE	Barrett's oesophagus
BEST3	Barrett's OESophagus Trial 3
BMI	Body mass index
BMP3	Bone morphogenic protein 3
CAI	Colonoscopy with air method
CC	Cervical cancer
CIN	Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia
CLC	Colorectal cancer
CLDN11	Claudin 11
COSMOS	Continuous Observation of Smoking Subjects trial
CpG	Cytosines followed by guanine on the same strand of DNA and connected by a phosphate
CRC	Colorectal cancer
CTCF	CCCTC-binding factor
CWE	Chromoendoscopy & water exchange
dG	2'-deoxyguanine
DTS	Chest digital tomosynthesis
EAC	Oesophageal adenocarcinoma
EC	Oesophageal cancer
ECLS	Early Diagnosis of Lung Cancer Scotland
ELISA	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
GC	Gastric cancer
GI	Gastrointestinal cancer

HR	Hazard ratio
HPV	Human papillomavirus
IBP	ITALUNG Biomarker Panel
ICER	Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio
IDH1	Isocitrate dehydrogenase 1
IT	Information technology
LBC	Liquid-based cytology
LC	Lung cancer
lncRNA	Long non-coding RNA
LOH	Loss of heterozygosity
Lung-RADS	Lung imaging reporting and data system
LYG	Life-years gained
m	Month
MGMT	O-6-methylguanine-DNA methyltransferase
miRNA	microRNA
MSC	miRNA signature classifier
MSI	Microsatellite instability
NA	Not applicable
NDRG4	N-Myc downstream-regulated gene 4 protein
NPI	Nottingham prognostic index
NR	Not reported
NSCLC	Non-small-cell lung cancer
OR	Odds ratio
Pap-smear	Papanicolaou cytology
PC	Prostate cancer
PG	Pepsinogen
PLCO	Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial
PPV	Positive predictive value

PSA	Prostate specific antigen
QALY	Quality adjusted life years
RAR-b2	Retinoic acid receptor b
RASSF1A	Ras association domain family member
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
ROC	Receiver operating characteristic
RR	Risk ratio
SDC2	Syndecan 2
SEPT9	Septin 9
SMD	Standardised mean difference
SOS	Studio Osservazionale
TFF3	Trefoil factor 3
TRIPOD	Transparent Reporting of a Multivariable Prediction Model for Individual Prognosis or Diagnosis
VOC	Volatile organic compound
WBC	White blood cells
WE	Water exchange colonoscopy
y	Year

2.1.2 Imaging and artificial intelligence

Technologies	Trial citation	Trial Details	Participants	Outcomes/Results	Notes
AI & imaging	Freeman et al. 2021	Systematic review of detection accuracy of standalone AI	Total number (no. screened): N = 131,822	Uptake: Not applicable Compliance: Not applicable	

		<p>algorithms or AI-assisted radiologists in ca breast mammography</p> <p>UK study including studies from multiple countries</p> <p>2010–2021</p> <p>12 retrospective studies</p> <p>Endpoints: 1. Test accuracy 2. Ca breast type detected</p>	<p>Population: women screened within digital mammography programmes</p>	<p>Outcomes: Sensitivity/Specificity: For larger retrospective studies (pooled n = 79,910), specificity of standalone AI systems was lower for 94% (34/36) systems vs. single radiologist detection and 100% for two radiologist consensus. Smaller laboratory studies (pooled n = 1086) reported AI to be more accurate than a single radiologist. Harm-benefit: AI used to triage for radiological review screened out 45–53% of women at low risk but also up to 10% of radiologist detected cancers Incidence/Stage: One AI system detected fewer cases of DCIS than radiologists (83.5% vs. 89.4%) and more invasive BCa (82.8% vs 76.7% & 79.7%) and more ≥ Stage 2 cancers (78.4% vs. 68.1%). Two other AI systems detected less ≥ Stage 2 cancers Mortality: NR Cost-effectiveness: NR</p>	
<p>Imaging One-time 2nd-generation NBI vs WLI Gastric cancer</p>	<p>Yoshida et al. 2021</p>	<p>Open-label crossover RCT</p> <p>Japan</p> <p>2014–2017</p> <p>Endpoints:</p>	<p>Total number (no. screened): 4575 (4472)</p> <p>Population: High-risk of GC*</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: n = 2234/2258 (99%) in primary WLI group and n = 2238/2265(99%) in primary NBI group</p> <p>Outcomes:</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y [revised after interim analysis]</p> <p>*High risk defined as 20–85 years with either a:</p>

		<p>1. Detection rate of EGC</p> <p>2. PPV; observation time; missed ECG in primary exam</p>		<p>Incidence/Stage: EGC incidence rate was 44 (1.9%) vs 53 (2.3%) for primary WLI vs NBI. Overall rate of lesions detected at secondary examination was 25% (n=36/145) with no significant difference between groups. Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: PPV for EGC in suspicious lesions was 13.7% (50/372) vs 20.9% (59/282), for WLI vs NBI ($P = 0.015$).</p> <p>Mean observation time was 233 sec and 253 sec for WLI and NBI respectively ($P < 0.001$).</p> <p>Cost-effectiveness: NR</p>	<p>(1) history of endoscopic resection for an oesophageal cancer or gastric neoplasm;</p> <p>(2) current oesophageal cancer or gastric neoplasm;</p> <p>(3) history of chemotherapy and/or radiation therapy for oesophageal cancer.</p>
<p>Imaging</p> <p>One-time LCI+WLI vs WLI</p> <p>Gastric cancer</p>	<p>Gao et al. 2021</p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>China</p> <p>Data collection dates: NR</p> <p>Endpoint: Detection of gastric neoplastic lesions</p>	<p>Total number (no. screened): 2383 (2335)</p> <p>Population: High-risk of EGC*</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: 96% (1110/1160) in WLI group and 100% (1125) in LCI+WLI group were observed.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <p>Incidence/Stage: EGC incidence was 4.3% (50/1110) in WLI group vs 8.0% (98/1125) in LCI+WLI group: a detection rate difference = 3.7% (95%CI 1.36–2.75, $P < 0.001$). Detection of type IIb lesions and high-grade precursor lesions was significantly higher in LCI+WLI group (both $P = 0.01$).</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: NR</p> <p>Cost-effectiveness: NR</p>	<p>Power calculation : Y</p> <p>* Definition of high-risk based on the Consensus on Screening and Endoscopic Diagnosis and Treatment of Early Gastric Cancer in China (2014)</p>

<p>Imaging</p> <p>One-time BLI-b vs WLI</p> <p>Gastric cancer</p>	<p>Dohi et al. 2019</p>	<p>Crossover RCT</p> <p>Japan</p> <p>2013-2017</p> <p>Endpoints:</p> <p>1. Detection of EGC by primary imaging exam</p> <p>2. Detection of EGC by secondary imaging exam</p>	<p>Total number (no. screened): 629 (596)</p> <p>Population: High-risk of EGC (atrophic gastritis with intestinal metaplasia or surveillance after endoscopic resection of EGC)</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: 100%; n = 298 in primary WLI group and n = 298 in primary BLI-b group were observed using both imaging technologies.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <p>Incidence/Stage: EGC incidence was 7.0% (21/298) in primary WLI group vs 8.7% (26/298) in primary BLI-b group.</p> <p>The real-time detection rate of primary WLI was 50.0% vs 93.1% for BLI-b. BLI-b had significantly greater detection of smaller/earlier stage GC (<10 mm and 10—20 mm; lesions with depth of invasion of T1a) plus other pathomorphological types (open atrophic border; lesions in lower 1/3 of stomach; flat lesions; well-differentiated adenocarcinomas.)</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: NR</p> <p>Cost-effectiveness: NR</p>	<p>Power calculation : Y</p> <p>BLI-bright mode = addition of a control for the 2 lasers along with white-light-emitting phosphors</p>
--	-------------------------	--	---	--	--

<p>Imaging</p> <p>One-time WLI+NBI vs WLI+Lugol chromoendoscopy</p> <p>Oesophageal cancer</p>	<p>Gruner et al. 2021</p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>France</p> <p>2011–2015</p> <p>Endpoint:</p> <p>1. Specificity of detection of oesophageal SCC and HGD</p> <p>2. Sensitivity (PPV, NPV)</p>	<p>Total number (no. screened):</p> <p>334 (316)</p> <p>Population: History of SCC of UAD tract and scheduled for gastroscopy</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: n= 8 and n = 11 did not receive the allocated Lugol and NBI examination, respectively. Overall compliance of 315/334 = 94%.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <p>Incidence/Stage: 18/106 (17.0%) of suspected lesions detected by Lugol were confirmed as SCC (14), HGD (1) and LGD (3). Lugol detected 7 additional neoplastic lesions after WLI. 22/61 (36.1%) of suspected lesions detected by NBI were confirmed as SCC (20 T1, 2 T2). 21 of these lesions had been detected by WLI. There was no statistically significant difference in number of patients with HG lesions detected between Lugol and NBI groups (8.4% vs. 10.8%; <i>P</i> =0.58).</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: Specificity was greater with NBI than Lugol (<i>P</i> =0.002). In per-patient analysis, sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV were 100%, 66.0%, 21.2%, and 100%, respectively for Lugol vs 100%, 79.9%, 37.5%,and 100%, respectively for NBI.</p> <p>Cost-effectiveness: NR</p>	<p>Power calculation : Y</p>
<p>Imaging</p>	<p>Ferreira et al. 2021</p>	<p>RCT</p>	<p>Total number (no. screened):</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: NR</p>	<p>Power calculation : N</p>

<p>One-time BLI-b vs LCI vs WLI</p> <p>Colorectal cancer</p>	<p>[conference abstract]</p>	<p>Brazil</p> <p>Endpoint: Detection of CRC adenoma</p>	<p>168</p> <p>Population: average risk of CRC adenoma</p>	<p>Outcomes:</p> <p>Incidence/Stage: Overall detection rate was 60.1%: 55.5% for WLI; 55.5% for BLI-b; 68.3% for LCI ($P=0.03$). All technologies were similar at detecting lesions <5mm dia, but LCI had superior flat-lesion detection ability.</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: NR</p> <p>Cost-effectiveness: NR</p>	
<p>Imaging</p> <p>TD vs standard online CTC</p> <p>Skin cancer</p>	<p>Ferrándiz et al. 2017</p>	<p>RCT</p> <p>Spain</p> <p>2015</p> <p>Endpoint: 1. Diagnostic performance 2. Cost-effectiveness</p>	<p>Total number (no. screened): 454 (454)</p> <p>Population: adults accessing primary care with concerning skin lesions</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: 100%; All $n = 226$ in CTC group and $n = 228$ in TD group were examined.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <p>Incidence/Stage: Proportion referred for in-person evaluation was 45.1% (95%CI 38.7–51.6) for CTC vs 20.9% (95%CI 15.0–25.4) for TD ($P < 0.001$).</p> <p>Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: Sensitivity and specificity were significantly higher for TD (92.9% & 96.2%) vs CTC (86.6% & 72.3%). The accuracy index was 94.3% for TD and 79.2% for CTC ($P < 0.001$): OR of correct diagnosis using TD = 4.04 (95%CI 2.0–8.1; $P < .0001$).</p> <p>Cost-effectiveness: TD was the dominant strategy, with a lower cost-effectiveness ratio</p>	<p>Power calculation: NR</p>

				(65.13€ vs 80.84€/accuracy units). The time dedicated by the TD operator in managing teleconsultation was 7.2 mins (95%CI 6.8–7.6) for CTC and 8.9 minutes (95%CI 8.3–9.5) for TD ($P < 0.001$).	
<p>Imaging</p> <p>Initial round of Helical CT screening from NLST</p> <p>Lung cancer</p>	<p>NLST dataset</p> <p>Hostetter et al. 2017</p>	<p>Modelling study of personalised malignancy risk</p> <p>US</p>	<p>Total number (no. screened): 53,454 (26,722)</p> <p>Population: 55–75 yrs, smoking history ≥ 30 pack-years in CT arm of NSLT</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: Data from $n = 26,722$ in CT group of NSLT.</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <p>Incidence/Stage: 5840 had lung nodules of any size at initial screening, with 465 cancers in same lobe as largest nodules: a prevalence of malignancy in the nodules of 8.5%. Nodule size predicted malignancy risk; prevalence of cancer in nodules ≤ 4mm was 3.16% vs 21.79% in nodules > 8 mm. Additional significant risk stratification discriminators were smoking history, sex, and nodule location. Mortality: NR</p> <p>Harm-benefit: Using personalised malignancy risk model, 54% of nodules > 4 and ≤ 6 mm were reclassified to longer-term FU than recommended by non-personalised criteria. 27% of nodules ≤ 4 mm were reclassified to shorter-term FU</p> <p>Cost-effectiveness: NR</p>	<p>Power calculation: Y for underlying NLST</p>

<p>AI in conventional imaging</p> <p>Lung cancer</p>	<p>SOS</p> <p>(Chauvie et al., 2020)</p>	<p>Italy</p> <p>Non-randomised study</p> <p>2010-2018</p> <p>1) Binary visual analysis</p> <p>2) Lung-RADS classification</p> <p>3) Logistic regression (LR)</p> <p>4) Random Forest (RF)</p> <p>5) Neural network (NNET)</p>	<p>N = 1594</p> <p>Mean age 63.2 (45-75 y)</p> <p>65% Male</p> <p>≥ 1 y follow-up</p> <p>Population: former^d or current smokers^b</p>	<p>Uptake: NR</p> <p>Compliance: NR</p> <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer incidence: A total of 32 lung cancer cases were diagnosed, one of which was not identified via DTS. - Detection rate: Over 3 rounds of DTS screening, results of 234 participants were positive. - Stage: NR - Cancer and all-cause mortality: NR - Sensitivity/Specificity: The corresponding sensitivity of method 1 to 5 was 95%, 65%, 20%, 30% and 90% with comparable specificity (93-100%). The PPV of binary visual analysis was the lowest (14%) followed by Lung-RADS (19%), LR (29%), and then RF (40%) whilst NNET had highest PPV of 95%. 	<p>Power calculation: NR</p> <p>Report was developed in accordance with TRIPOD guidelines.</p> <p>This trial was aimed to evaluate whether AI can enhance the sensitivity and specificity of DTS in lung cancer detection.</p> <p>DTS was performed using Discovery XR650 (GE Healthcare) with tube voltage of 120 kVp.</p> <p>Both semantic variables and radiomics features were used to develop a LG-based prediction model and machine learning.</p>
--	---	---	---	---	--

Acronym	Full Description
	<i>Uptake:</i> Percentage of invited population agreeing to participate in the trial <i>Compliance:</i> Percentage of trial population completing the baseline screening
BCa	Breast cancer
BLI-b	Blue laser imaging - bright mode
CRC	Colorectal cancer
CTC	Clinical teleconsultation
DCIS	Ductal carcinoma in situ
DTS	Chest digital tomosynthesis
EGC	Early gastric cancer
HGD	High grade dysplasia
LCI	Linked colour imaging
LGD	Low grade dysplasia
NBI	Narrow band imaging
NLST	National Lung Screening Trial
NPV	Negative predictive value
PPV	Positive predictive value
QUADAS-2	QUality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies-2
SCC	Squamous cell carcinoma
TD	Tele-dermoscopy
UAD	Upper aerodigestive (tract)
WLI	White light imaging

2.2 Bottom line results

Based on data from the 19 trials and 10 systematic reviews of case control/diagnostic accuracy studies included in the rapid review some key findings relating to the evidence on efficacy, harm-benefit and cost-effectiveness may be summarised as follows.

Biomarkers:

Biomarker panels tend to show better specificity in cancer detection than single markers. (Anghel et al. 2021; Carozzi et al. 2017 a/b; Chu et al. 2018; Hulstaert et al. 2021; Tarney et al. 2019).

Biomarkers not only facilitate cancer detection, but can also enhance detection of pre-cancerous lesions, e.g., Cytosponge®-TFF3 for Barrett's Oesophagus (Fitzgerald, di Pietro, O'Donovan, Maroni, et al., 2020; Fitzgerald, Di Pietro, O'Donovan, Muldrew, et al., 2020; Swart et al., 2021) and saliva cytokines for oral cancer (Chiamulera et al., 2021).

Across various cancer types, the biomarkers for colorectal cancer screening are the most intensively studied, including genomic, epigenetic and protein markers detected in blood, stool, urine and tissue (Anghel et al., 2021).

Imaging and artificial intelligence:

Novel image-enhanced endoscopy can improve early detection of upper GI-tract lesions in high-risk populations. Studies exploring detection rates as compared to standard white light imaging have suggested improvements with narrow band imaging (Yoshida et al. 2021), blue laser imaging-bright (Dohi et al. 2019) and light linked colour imaging (Gao et al. 2021).

There is small-scale evidence for superiority of blue light imaging in bright mode over linked colour imaging in the detection rate of gastric cancer (Dohi et al. 2019) but the reverse has been demonstrated for colorectal adenomas (Ferreira et al., 2020).

Retrospective evidence, and lack of prospective evidence, suggest that current AI is not sufficiently specific to replace radiologist reading in breast screening programmes. A **systematic review** (Freeman et al. 2021) tested accuracy of standalone AI algorithms or AI-assisted radiologists to detect breast cancer in digital mammogram screening or test sets. In a retrospective evaluation including 79,910 women, 34/36 (94%) AI systems were less accurate than a single radiologist's original decision; all were less accurate than consensus of two or more radiologists. Five smaller studies (1086 women, 520 cancers) at high risk of bias and low applicability evaluated AI systems as more accurate than a single radiologist reading a test set. In three studies, AI used for triage screened out 53%, 45%, and 50% of women at low risk but also 10%, 4%, and 0% of cancers detected by radiologists.

3. Discussion

3.1 Summary

This rapid review provides evidence for the potential of new technologies in cancer screening, notably the use of biomarkers and imaging techniques. It is clear from the results of the search carried out for this review that research on imaging (including digital pathology) and biomarkers for cancer detection is a rapidly advancing field with a large number of ongoing studies (this study set is available from the authors).

The research landscape for circulating tumour DNA (ctDNA), circulating tumour cells and proteins, and DNA methylation markers for cancer screening was discussed in detail at the workshop (available on SAPEA website) where it was noted that large prospective studies are underway.

As noted in workshop 3 (available on SAPEA website) research is ongoing to test the effectiveness of AI-based cancer screening tools and explore how best to embed them into routine screening and clinical care. Two studies (outside the scope of this rapid review since not embedded in trials) were discussed that indicate that algorithms can perform as well as human radiologists. However, a recent systematic review of AI-based breast screening tools, that met the inclusion criteria, concluded that overall they were not currently sufficiently specific to replace human assessment of scans, and that more research is needed to demonstrate effectiveness, particularly in prospective real-world trials (Freeman et al., 2021). This is a promising area for future research and practice.

3.2 Strengths and limitations of this Rapid Review

3.2.1 Strengths

This review summarises a valuable sub-set of the evidence base. It emphasises the findings from studies within recent randomised and other controlled clinical trials, providing the evidence with the least potential for bias, supplemented with data from published systematic reviews of multiple case-control or diagnostic accuracy studies.

3.2.2 Limitations

In order to complete the review in a timely fashion a pragmatic and precise search strategy was employed. It is possible that additional studies within controlled trials would have been identified should there have been time for a detailed and sensitive systematic search.

It is acknowledged that other types of non-trial evidence are relevant to the topic, notably individual studies of 'real life' screening cohorts. In all, 101 cohort or dataset studies with ≥ 100 subjects were retrieved by the search and full details are available from the authors of this report.

The timeline also precluded any statistical or meta-analysis of findings. No formal critical appraisal was carried out although information is provided on whether the trial included a power calculation. Data extraction and summary were undertaken by different reviewers and, although reviewed by another author, these have not been independently checked for accuracy and consistency.

4. References:

1. Aalami, A.M., et al., *Urinary Angiogenin as a Marker for Bladder Cancer: A Meta-Analysis* Biomed Res Int, 2021. **Article ID 5557309** DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2021/5557309>.
2. Anghel, S.A., et al., *Promising epigenetic biomarkers for the early detection of colorectal cancer: A systematic review*. Cancers, 2021. **13(19) (no pagination)** DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/cancers13194965>.
3. Campi, R., et al., *Novel Liquid Biomarkers and Innovative Imaging for Kidney Cancer Diagnosis: What Can Be Implemented in Our Practice Today? A Systematic Review of the Literature* Eur Urol Oncol 2021. **4(1)**: p. 22-41 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.euo.2020.12.011>.
4. Carozzi, F., et al., *Selection of subjects at high-risk for LDCT lung cancer screening using a molecular panel: results by the ITALUNG biomarker study*. Journal of thoracic oncology, 2017. **12(1)**: p. S570-S571 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jtho.2016.11.717>.
5. Carozzi, F.M., et al., *Multimodal lung cancer screening using the ITALUNG biomarker panel and low dose computed tomography. Results of the ITALUNG biomarker study*. International Journal of Cancer, 2017. **141(1)**: p. 94-101 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijc.30727>.
6. Chauvie, S., et al., *Artificial intelligence and radiomics enhance the positive predictive value of digital chest tomosynthesis for lung cancer detection within SOS clinical trial*. European Radiology, 2020. **30(7)**: p. 4134-4140 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-06783-z>.
7. Chiamulera, M.M.A., et al., *Salivary cytokines as biomarkers of oral cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. BMC Cancer, 2021. **21(1)**: p. 205 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12885-021-07932-3>.
8. Chu, G.C.W., K. Lazare, and F. Sullivan, *Serum and blood based biomarkers for lung cancer screening: a systematic review*. BMC Cancer, 2018. **18(1)**: p. 181 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12885-018-4024-3>.
9. Dohi, O., et al., *Blue laser imaging-bright improves the real-time detection rate of early gastric cancer: a randomized controlled study*. Gastrointestinal endoscopy, 2019. **89(1)**: p. 47-57 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gie.2018.08.049>.
10. Ferrándiz, L., et al., *Internet-based skin cancer screening using clinical images alone or in conjunction with dermoscopic images: a randomized teledermoscopy trial*. Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology, 2017. **76(4)**: p. 676-682 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2016.10.041>.
11. Ferreira, L.E., et al., *Can new image-enhancing technologies improve adenoma detection rates in cancer screening colonoscopies? A randomized clinical trial*. Gastrointestinal endoscopy, 2020. **91(6)**: p. AB232-AB233 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.gie.2020.03.1769>.
12. Fitzgerald, R.C., et al., *Cytosponge-trefoil factor 3 versus usual care to identify Barrett's oesophagus in a primary care setting: a multicentre, pragmatic, randomised controlled trial*. Lancet, 2020. **396(10247)**: p. 333-344 DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)31099-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)31099-0).
13. Fitzgerald, R.C., et al., *634 results from the Barrett's oesophagus trial 3*

- (Best3): A randomised controlled trial comparing the Cytosponge™-Tff3 test with usual care to identify oesophageal precancer in primary care patients with chronic gastroesophageal reflux. *Gastroenterology*, 2020. **158**(6): p. S-136- DOI: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0016-5085\(20\)31020-9](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0016-5085(20)31020-9).
14. Freeman, K., et al., *Use of artificial intelligence for image analysis in breast cancer screening programmes: systematic review of test accuracy*. *BMJ*, 2021. **374**: p. n1872 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n1872>
 15. Gao, J., et al., *Linked Color Imaging Can Improve Detection Rate of Early Gastric Cancer in a High-Risk Population: A Multi-Center Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial*. *Digestive Diseases & Sciences*, 2021. **66**(4): p. 1212-1219 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10620-020-06289-0>.
 16. Gruner, M., et al., *Narrow-band imaging versus Lugol chromoendoscopy for esophageal squamous cell cancer screening in normal endoscopic practice: randomized controlled trial*. *Endoscopy*, 2021. **53**(7): p. 674-682 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1055/a-1224-6822>.
 17. Guo, Y., J. Long, and S. Lei, *Promoter methylation as biomarkers for diagnosis of melanoma: A systematic review and meta-analysis*. *Journal of Cellular Physiology*, 2019. **234**(5): p. 7356-7367 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/jcp.27495>.
 18. Hostetter, J.M., et al., *Personalizing lung cancer risk prediction and imaging follow-up recommendations using the National Lung Screening Trial dataset*. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 2017. **24**(6): p. 1046-1051 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocx012>.
 19. Hubers, A.J., et al., *DNA hypermethylation analysis in sputum of asymptomatic subjects at risk for lung cancer participating in the NELSON trial: argument for maximum screening interval of 2 years*. *Journal of Clinical Pathology*, 2017. **70**(3): p. 250-254 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/jclinpath-2016-203734>.
 20. Hulstaert, E., et al., *Candidate RNA biomarkers in biofluids for early diagnosis of ovarian cancer: A systematic review*. *Gynecologic Oncology*, 2021. **160**(2): p. 633-642 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ygyno.2020.11.018>.
 21. In, H., et al., *Serum pepsinogen as a biomarker for gastric cancer: a nested case-control study using the prostate, lung, colorectal, and ovarian (PLCO) cancer screening trial data*. *Journal of clinical oncology*, 2021. **39**(3 SUPPL) DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2021.39.3_suppl.188.
 22. Kazarian, A., et al., *Testing breast cancer serum biomarkers for early detection and prognosis in pre-diagnosis samples*. *British Journal of Cancer*, 2017. **116**(4): p. 501-508 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/bjc.2016.433>.
 23. Saheb Sharif-Askari, N., et al., *Integrative systematic review meta-analysis and bioinformatics identifies MicroRNA-21 and its target genes as biomarkers for colorectal adenocarcinoma*. *International Journal Of Surgery*, 2020. **73**: p. 113-122 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2019.11.017>.
 24. Sturgeon, S.R., et al., *White blood cell DNA methylation and risk of breast cancer in the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal, and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial (PLCO)*. *Breast Cancer Research*, 2017. **19**(1): p. 94 DOI:

- <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13058-017-0886-6>.
25. Sturgeon, S.R., et al., *Prediagnostic White Blood Cell DNA Methylation and Risk of Breast Cancer in the Prostate Lung, Colorectal, and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial (PLCO) Cohort*. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention*, 2021. **30**(8): p. 1575-1581 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965>.
 26. Sullivan, F.M., et al., *Earlier diagnosis of lung cancer in a randomised trial of an autoantibody blood test followed by imaging*. *European Respiratory Journal*, 2021. **57**(1): p. 01 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1183/13993003.00670-2020>
 27. Sun, N., et al., *Utility of isocitrate dehydrogenase 1 as a serum protein biomarker for the early detection of non-small-cell lung cancer: A multicenter in vitro diagnostic clinical trial*. *Cancer Science*, 2020. **111**(5): p. 1739-1749 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/cas.14387>.
 28. Swart, N., et al., *Economic evaluation of Cytosponge R-trefoil factor 3 for Barrett esophagus: A cost-utility analysis of randomised controlled trial data*. *EClinicalMedicine*, 2021. **37**: p. 100969 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2021.100969>.
 29. Tarney, C.M., et al., *Biomarker panel for early detection of endometrial cancer in the prostate, lung, colorectal, and ovarian cancer screening trial*. *Gynecologic oncology*, 2019. **154**: p. 42-43 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ygyno.2019.04.102>.
 30. Wen, Q., et al., *Urinary Volatile Organic Compound Analysis for the Diagnosis of Cancer: A Systematic Literature Review and Quality Assessment*. *Metabolites*, 2020. **11**(1): p. 17 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/metabo11010017>.
 31. Yang, B.H., et al., *The value of DNA quantitative cytology test for the screening of endometrial cancer*. *Cancer Management and Research*, 2019. **11**: p. 10383-10391 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2147/CMAR.S225672>.
 32. Yoshida, N., et al., *Early gastric cancer detection in high-risk patients: a multicentre randomised controlled trial on the effect of second-generation narrow band imaging*. *Gut*, 2021. **70**(1): p. 67-75 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/gutjnl-2019-319631>.
 33. Yu, Y., et al., *Long noncoding RNAs as diagnostic biomarkers for the early detection of digestive tract cancers: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. *Revista Espanola de Enfermedades Digestivas*, 2020. **112**(10): p. 797-804 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.17235/reed.2020.5450/2018>.
 34. Zhou, X., et al., *Association of APC gene promoter methylation and the risk of gastric cancer: A meta-analysis and bioinformatics study*. *Medicine (Baltimore)*, 2020. **99**(16): p. e19828 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000019828>.

5. Rapid review method

5.1 Eligibility criteria

Inclusion:

- Studies within a randomised controlled trial (RCT) or controlled clinical trial² or a systematic review published since 2017
- ‘New technology’ interventions including: Artificial intelligence, machine learning, genetic markers (including ctDNA, mRNA), imaging, urinary markers, f(a)ecal markers, volatile compounds, auto-antibodies.
- Screening for first (early) diagnosis of any cancer in the general population
- Inclusion of data on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost-effectiveness relating to targeted screening methods using new technology(ies)
- All locations, all languages but to emphasise the findings from EU studies within the narrative write up

Exclusion:

- Studies looking at new technologies to
 - Support decision making/informed choice
 - Aid cancer detection (post screening)
 - Aid cancer detection in symptomatic patients
 - Assess prognosis
- Studies to explore implementation factors such as adherence to testing
- HPV testing and/or further testing for those with HPV positive status (trial data in RR2)
- Helicobacter pylori testing
- MRI for breast cancer (trial data in RR2) and prostate cancer (trial data in RR1)
- Cytology for anal cancer
- Conference reports
- Non-English language studies
- Studies based on large screening cohorts or datasets

6.2 Literature search strategy

Searches were carried out for publications from 2017 onwards using title and Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) searches of the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CCTR), Medline, Embase, the ICTRP trials register and Clinicaltrials.gov.

Search terms

² Quasi-randomised and other controlled trials where randomisation is not explicit, but cannot be ruled out

Text words: (cancer* AND (screen* OR early detection)) in title

MeSH terms: (exp Neoplasms/) AND (early detection of cancer/)

Combined with

(machine learning OR artificial intelligence OR biomarker* OR AI OR ctDNA OR mRNA OR microRNA OR DNA OR imaging OR urinary marker* OR faecal marker* OR fecal marker* OR VoC* OR volatile compound* OR antibod* OR anti-bod* OR cytosponge) in title

In Medline using above terms [AND randomized controlled trial.pt OR controlled clinical trial.pt OR pragmatic clinical trial.pt OR systematic review.m_titl OR exp mass screening/ OR trial.m_titl OR cohort.m_titl];

In Embase using above terms [AND exp mass screening/ OR systematic review.m+titl].
Randomized controlled trial.pt OR trial.m_titl OR cohort.m_titl

Additional search methods: The workshop on the topic was attended by one of the review authors to note any additional studies meeting the inclusion criteria.

6.3 Resources list

Clinical trials.gov

Cochrane Library [Cochrane Reviews/Cochrane Central Register of Controlled trials]

Health Technology Assessment

Embase

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

Medline

US Preventive Services Taskforce (USPSTF)

6.4 Study selection process

Results from the literature searches were imported into EndNote 20, where duplicates were removed. Titles and abstracts were screened for inclusion followed by full text screening. Both screening stages were undertaken by a team of reviewers according to the eligibility criteria in Section 5.1.

5.5 Study selection flow chart

5.6 Data extraction

Data from main trial report(s) on efficacy, harm-benefit or cost effectiveness were extracted into a summary table for each cancer by a single reviewer (Section 2.1).

5.7 Quality appraisal

In this review, most of the included data was from diagnostic accuracy studies within a trial or from systematic reviews of diagnostic accuracy studies. Each included study was identified as a systematic review; or an RCT or controlled clinical trial (CCT) according to the study design as provided in the database(s) within the evidence table (Section 2.1) along with a note as to whether a power calculation was included as part of the trial. No other formal critical appraisal was carried out.

5.8 Synthesis

The findings are summarised in a narrative report, drawing from the summary tables with brief findings based on the consensus from the included studies.

6. Additional information

6.1 Conflicts of interest

None

6.2 Acknowledgements

This template is based, with permission, on the rapid review template used within the Palliative Care Evidence Review Service ([PaCERS](#)) and the Welsh Covid 19 Evidence Centre.

7. About the review team

The Specialist Unit for Review Evidence (SURE) is a team of experienced systematic reviewers and information specialists at Cardiff University who conduct all forms of systematic and other evidence reviews, and teach evidence review methods. The team work across all topic areas and also specialise in health and social care. Staff have carried out a number of reviews for SAPEA, working closely with Academia Europaea and experienced reviewers within the University's Library Service. Reviews are carried out in close collaboration with subject specialists for each review topic. For these rapid reviews the subject specialists are Dr Hui-Ling Ou (Cambridge University) and Dr Nicholas Courtier (Cardiff University).

SAPEA is part of the European Commission's Scientific Advice Mechanism, which provides independent, interdisciplinary, and evidence-based scientific advice on policy issues to the European Commission.

SAPEA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 737432.

www.sapea.info
@SAPEAnews